

جامعة بيروت العربية
BEIRUT ARAB UNIVERSITY

**“The Dilemma of Political and Social Relations Between the Chinese
Government and the Uyghur People During Deng Xiaoping’s Reign”
(1978 - 1989)**

from

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Submitted as part of the requirements for the Master's degree in Modern and
Contemporary History

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Beirut 2024

Dedication

In this paragraph I will strive to be as precise, specific, and practical as Deng Xiaoping was in China's leadership. Starting on the personal level, to my mother, Rajaa Al-Banna, all my thanks, love, and devotion to you, my teacher and my friend, I would not be who I am today if God replaced you with someone else. Here I was able to accomplish this research through your mental and physical toil. Secondly, my sister, who is dear to my heart and mind, engineer Ghina Dhani, your love, joy, and endless and unlimited support had an impact on this work and in the pursuit of my career. I also want to thank my dear friend Sarah Khafaja, as she was the daily support on this arduous journey and the positive energy without which tasks cannot be accomplished. As for the academic level, I send the kindest and most precious waves of sincerity to my professor, Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Quzi, Head of the History Department at the Faculty of Humanities at Beirut Arab University. Professor Al-Quzi, I see him as many students of ancient history saw the first teacher, Aristotle. He was the one who directed the compass and opened new horizons in the journey of gaining scientific skills,

sharpening motivation, treating weaknesses, and transforming my passion as an enthusiastic “amateur” to a serious and realistic student and a humble seeker of knowledge in a small part of the folds of this vast subject. As for Professor Dr. Rama Daraz, without her patience and effort, I would not have completed this work successfully. Many days I knocked on her door and she always provided help and guidance tirelessly. Thanks are due to Professor Khaled Al-Kurdi and Professor Nafez Al-Ahmar for reading the thesis and participating in the discussion of this scientific research.

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Introduction

During the period in which I was busy completing this study, I read an article that Uyghur researcher *Rahilä Dawut*, Professor of Anthropology at Xinjiang University, had been sentenced and imprisoned for life by the Chinese government under the pretext of “endangering state security and spreading separatist ideology.” Without a doubt, the news of her life imprisonment and depriving the research world of her knowledge grieved me. I wondered why, routinely and repeatedly, the mouths of the cultured and educated elite that seek the truth and search for knowledge in the East and West, in the past and present, and in regimes that impose atheism and ultra- religious societies alike, are always sealed?

This is evidence that China is pressing forward to limit the Uyghur culture and hide everything related to their identity from the world by silencing the educated elite. I hope this research will constitute a simple and humble step in the journey of exploring Uyghur culture, which is still neglected and considered an uncharted territory in our Arab world. In this

regard, I must mention that when I told my professor, Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Quzi, that I intended to study the Uyghur people in China, his initial response, or “prediction” rather, was that I shall save every online article, book, or study that I read into the device I use. Today many of the studies used in research have been removed from the Internet, and if I had not saved them, it would have been impossible to complete the study.

1. Study summary

Following Deng Xiaoping resignation from his official post in the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) following the Tiananmen Square events in Beijing, this incident occurred on a bus in the city of Ürümqi, the capital of the Xinjiang region in western China: “A young Uyghur woman boarded the bus with a baby in her hand, and no passenger gave up his seat for her. In the past, the Uyghurs always offered their seats to the elderly, women, and children, but now the buses are full of Han people, for whom it is uncommon to give up their seats on buses to women or the elderly. The sight of the girl with the baby angered an Uyghur policewoman who shouted at a

Han passenger who expressed his annoyance at the baby's screaming: "We gave you our entire land, Xinjiang, and yet you can't even offer your seat to a baby!"

This incident, which may seem commonplace to some, is an indication of the social and demographic metamorphosis in Xinjiang, or East Turkestan, during the period of the 1980s which witnessed intense levels of migration. This research probes the Uyghur people in Xinjiang during the reform period, from 1978 when Deng Xiaoping came to power in China until his resignation in 1989, in both political, socio-economic and cultural themes. The research also reviews the interconnection of each of the preferential policies enacted by the government for the benefit of the Uyghur people, with the aim of Sinicizing and integrating them into Chinese society, with the consolidation of the condescending look that the Han people direct towards the Uyghur people in which they view from the perspective of "the other."

2. The Importance of the Study

In contrast to the cultural, civilizational and social harmony that has eternally existed historically in Central Asia and western China between the various civilizations and peoples that lived there, that region during the 21st century is witnessing a cultural genocide and a process of “forced ethnic and cultural assimilation” that the Chinese regime is exerting on the Uyghur minority, and thus extinguishing the ethnic diversity that China has historically enjoyed. This research is specifically related to the Uyghurs, a Turkic people who migrated during the middle of the ninth century AD from the Mongolian steppe and settled in the regions of western China, which are also known today as East Turkestan or Xinjiang in the Chinese tongue. The research concentrates on studying Uyghur history and culture during the 1980s decade in what was christened as the period of Chinese reform and openness.

The importance of the topic lies in presenting an objective scientific study that aims to highlight the distinction of the Uyghurs who branch off

from the tree of Turkic peoples emerging in Central Asia, and who have not yet been integrated into the modern Chinese state, unlike other minorities living within the borders of the People's Republic of China (PRC). As for the Uyghurs, they constitute one minority out of 55 officially recognized Chinese minorities living within China along with the Han group which comprises the overwhelming majority that makes up the Republic of China, thus completing a total of 56 Chinese ethnic groups. By virtue of the cultural, religious, ethnic, and civilizational distinction of the Uyghur people, and because of their conspicuous difference from the majority of the Han group in clothing, food, appearance, lifestyle, and many other features, the broader segment of the Uyghurs suffer injustice and discrimination under the Chinese communist regime, and the majority of them harbor separatist ambitions or call for full-blown autonomy.

The importance of linking the 21st century “Uyghur question” with the Chinese reform period that occurred after the death of the revolutionary Chinese leader Mao Zedong can’t be emphasized enough. The 1980s in China comprised a period of renewal, reform and openness led by the Secretary-general of the Chinese Communist Party, leader Deng Xiaoping.

And in order to understand the gravity of the 21st century Uyghur Question in what is known as "Xinjiang", the researcher must assess carefully the reign of Deng Xiaoping and the impact of his policies on the Uyghur minority, which has been Chinese citizens from the inception of the People's Republic of China and subject to the Communist party's decisions. These renewed policies of China under the leadership of Deng, known as Dengist policies, have unbolted the sealed doors that were totally suppressing the ethnic and religious privacy of minorities within China, as many studies have led to the conclusion that the reform policies of Deng during the eighties of the last century contributed in the creation of a climate for the Uyghurs that harbors separatist ideas. Although it signaled prosperity, openness, and reform, unlike the preceding period of the Cultural Revolution of 1966-1976 and the subsequent period, understanding the 1980s decade in China by the research elite is a basic prerequisite in order to understand the imposed challenges and try to identify solutions to them. Among those challenges, we mention persecution, torture, and dissolution through forced abortion or birth control, albeit the chief challenge that face Uyghur people is the "Sinicization of Uyghur society, that is, imposing characteristics on it that transform its entity to become similar to Chinese society, and robbing it

of its historical features that distinguished it from the Chinese people, whether in terms of religion, customs, traditions, etc...

3. Reasons for Choosing the Subject of Study

During the 2010s, stories of detention and “re-education” camps in Xinjiang, similar to the Nazi concentration camps during World War II, were extensively reported in news bulletins and social networking sites, especially in the Arab world which was interestedly following the events of the Arab Spring/Autumn wars in Syria and Libya and the Rohingya Genocide in Myanmar. On the other hand, this research focuses on Xinjiang during the 1980s, which did not know sorrow, grief, torture, and arbitrary arrests like the 2010s, but rather experienced openness, comfort, and relative prosperity for the Uyghur people during what was termed as the reform period in China under the leadership of the reformist and progressive Deng Xiaoping.

The nucleus of this thesis synthesized after I had written a research paper on China during the reign of leader Deng Xiaoping who assumed

power in 1978, that is, two years after the death of leader Mao Zedong, and then retired from power after the infamous Tiananmen Square protests that rocked China in 1989. It was Deng who built modern China, reformed the Chinese economic system, opened the Chinese market, and strengthened the private sector without neglecting the role of the public sector within what was known as the “socialist market economy.” I had written another research, but this time about the Uyghur people, and within this research I conducted a brief study on their history, kingdoms, and religions in an attempt to examine their uniqueness that distinguishes them from the rest of the Turkic peoples in Central Asia.

In this regard, and because I need to widen my knowledge about the Uyghur people and to accurately comprehend Deng’s era in China, especially after assuming a leadership role in the region and its transformation in the 2010s into a global superpower competing with the West, I chose for my thesis to constitute a midpoint between these two researches. I needed to delve deeper to try to fathom the challenges that faced the Uyghurs, even during Deng’s era that was characterized by openness, reform, and acceptance of others, and this last feature is rarely

found in the totalitarian regimes, such as the Chinese one. And in regards to official references employed in this research, I relied mainly on the 1982 Constitution and the Autonomous Regional Law issued in 1984.

I searched in the library of the Beirut Arab University for topics related to the Uyghur people, but I did not find any book or research that dealt with their history, thus, my motivation levels to pursue the search surged. The second factor that prompted me to focus on the subject of the Uyghurs during the reform era is the scarcity of online studies written in Arabic language that address their history during the period of cultural openness and political reform that allocated a margin for them to exhibit their identity and culture. Most studies chiefly focus on the systematic persecution practiced by the government during the 2010s, and neglect research into their modern history during the 20th century after the communist government “peacefully” annexed East Turkestan in 1949 following its victory over the Nationalist faction in the Chinese Civil War of 1927-1949. This intense priority in researching the issue of political persecution of the Uyghurs during the 2010s can be understood due to the religious connection that brings most Arab researchers together with the

Uyghur people, or to the closeness of the Turkish Uyghur language written in Arabic script to the Arabic language itself. As I closely follow international news, I was struck by Chinese leader Xi Jinping's visit to the Xinjiang region and his urging of local leaders to maintain "hard-won stability" by applying "Sinicization of Islam," a new term being circulated in China in order to impose a modern variety of Islam, devoid of its teachings and rules and compatible with the character of Chinese society.

While I was preparing for this research by examining books, letters, articles, and periodicals related to the modern history of Xinjiang, it was evident that most of them referred in a superficial and brief manner to the reform period in Xinjiang, and few expanded to detail all or most dimensions: political, economic or social. Once I decided on the topic of Uyghur in Xinjiang during the reform period, the scarcity of comprehensive references that include all the information needed for the study and the problem of organizing scattered points and ideas across a vast number of books represented a tremendous challenge and a deep ocean that I had to overcome. One of the first judgments that I formed during the process of collecting and organizing information dispersed over a wide body of books

and information is that positive news, that is, non-negative news, is not viewed as news worth writing about or studying. This bias is supported by the abundance of available references that study the woes and misfortunes of the Cultural Revolution in Xinjiang during the period stretching from 1966 to 1976, or highlight the suffering of the persecuted Uyghurs in concentration camps after Xi Jinping took power in 2012. In addition, most books and articles focus on directing a negative view of China's policies in Xinjiang, while presenting The Uyghurs as victims to a higher degree. This comes along with the almost complete absence of studies that cast a positive look at some of China's policies towards the Uyghurs, such as preferential policies that spur them to keep pace with the rest of China's nationalities in the process of scientific and practical development, or even probing the cultural and religious openness that has been achieved during the 1980s. So a fear crystallized in me of bias towards the Uyghurs without presenting China's official narrative in return, thus weakening the research and stripping it of the quality of objectivity that the researcher must present in studying a problematic topic, and this matter prompted me to pursue this research even more.

4. Research Problem

This research addresses the period of cultural openness that the Uyghur people enjoyed during the reign of Deng Xiaoping. The overwhelming majority of the Han Chinese people blame Deng Xiaoping, Hu Yaobang and other reformers who established the principle of openness, inclusivity and tolerance towards ethnic and religious minorities. The research problem posture itself to the researcher examining the Uyghurs who indulged in a period of relaxation during the 1980s, it is possible to consider the margin of freedom and cultural laxity allowed by Deng and other architects of the Chinese openness in that period as a foundation for the Uyghurs to pursue their goal of secession and independence from China instead of being satisfied with the autonomy guaranteed by the Chinese Constitution. It must be noted that Uyghur separatism, although not born of that period, gained momentum and became more evident during the period of political strife that began in Xinjiang in the mid-1980s and expanded in the 1990s, culminating in the bloody events of the 2009 Ürümqi riots that caused death and violence.

5. Study Hypotheses

1. The first hypothesis: The degree of relative political openness that China experienced during the era of Deng Xiaoping throughout the 1980s was insufficient for the Uyghur people who aspired for independence and strived to establish a national state that mirrors the First Republic of East Turkestan (1933 - 1934) and the Second Republic of East Turkestan (1944 -1949).

Uyghur dissidence, a product of insufficient levels of reform and openness according to Uyghur standard, shifted the period of the mid-1980s into a period of political chaos and popular discontent in Xinjiang.

2. The second hypothesis: The preferential policies, which the government enacted for ethnic minorities in an attempt to “spur the minorities that lack Chinese civilization to progress”, prompted the Han people to express their dissatisfaction with their government’s decisions. The Han opposed and criticized the birth control policies, which were more harsh on the Han group than the rest of the minorities, and the educational policies that prompted the government to provide more facilities to minorities than the Han people.

3. The third hypothesis: The failure of the reform policies in assimilating the Uyghur group within the Chinese society forced the leaders who ruled after Deng to tighten the degree of openness and employ instead forced assimilation in order to demolish the margin available to express identity, culture and religious freedom, while focusing at the same time on economic development to eradicate any separatist sense in Xinjiang.

4. The fourth hypothesis: The last and most important hypothesis, as I think, is the difficulty of restoring today the momentum of the previous separatist movement, which has begun to fade with the advent of the new Chinese leadership under Xi Jinping. It seems that the future outlook for the possibility of Uyghur independence appears negative in light of China's transformation into a global giant that imposes hegemony in Asia, the Pacific Ocean, the Indian Ocean, Africa and the Middle East. The latter region enjoys extraordinary importance in relation to China, as Arab and Muslim countries, and many of its political and media figures, are chasing their political and economic interests while aligning themselves adjacent to China's propaganda on the issue of human rights that Western countries have long raised against China on "The Uyghur Question" before the Human

Rights Council and the United Nations. This Arab and Islamic abandonment, even Turkish one starting from the 2020s, will impede the Uyghurs from seceding from China in the foreseeable future. Rather, that goal has turned into a pipe dream, and today exists merely in the imagination of most Uyghur men and women who are indignantly witnessing Xinjiang transformed into a major Han hub, while they themselves are transformed into cheap labor serving the Han and the Uyghur class allied with them and with the government.

6. Study Objectives

This research presents a brief “who’s who” on the Uyghur people and Xinjiang region, while mainly focusing on the 1980s era in regards to assessing the level of political, economic and cultural reform that was allocated to the Uyghurs during that period through the four chapters of the thesis. As for the fifth and last chapter, the issue of the condescending look of the Han people towards the Uyghur people is addressed, and that is not limited to the 1980s or any period of time. This stereotypical view, that

continues until the twenty-first century, has existed since the age of the ancient Chinese dynasties and is directed at most of the “nomadic” peoples living on China’s borders. Through this research, I will try to uncover the relationship between the Han’s condescending look towards the Uyghur people, which emulates the Europeans’ orientalist view of the Islamic/Arab world that commenced after Napoleon’s campaign to Egypt in order to “civilize the East,” and the preferential policies enacted by the Chinese government to benefit the Uyghurs and the rest of the minorities in the aim of inducing them to “follow the Chinese scientific development” via Sinicization programmes.

7. Study Methodology

A case study dealing with an ethnic/religious minority that enjoys prominent characteristics and then probing this minority’s relationship with the host country during a period of cultural openness requires a broad process of critique to identify patterns. The researcher must maintain a clear objective approach in dealing with the research in order to examine the topic

from many angles and avoid bias. In this regard, sociologist Howard Becker commented on the issue of bias when studying peoples, saying: “We have a deep sympathy with peoples who we study, we do not present a balanced conception during the study.” In analyzing the relationship between the Uyghurs and the Chinese government during the reform period, there is no consensus that winds up between the Chinese, Uyghur and the Western researchers who studied Xinjiang region in the 1980s/1990s when China used to issue permits for Western scholars that aimed to study Chinese minorities. Because of this diversity of opinions, the researcher must adopt the analytical historical method in addition to the critical method in order to explain events that occurred during various periods of Uyghurs’ existence in this region that is incorporated by the PRC, and to find a correlation between the policies and practices of the Chinese government and the challenges facing the Uyghurs across successive historical periods.

8. Study Limitations

Place: Xinjiang Autonomous Region / East Turkestan

Time: Beginning in 1978 when Deng Xiaoping assumed power in China and ending in 1989 when he resigned after the Tiananmen events. I chose the years 1978-1989 for two reasons:

Firstly, Because they designate the period of Deng Xiaoping's reign.

Secondly, The 1989 Tiananmen Square events in China had a tremendous impact in reverting China to its repressive policies, especially throughout Xinjiang, and this requires further analysis.

9. Study Terminology

Xinjiang region - Uyghur people - Nationalism - Political reform - Cultural openness - Cultural revolution - Marxism-Leninism - Socialist market economy - *Minzu* ethnic minorities - Tiananmen Square events - Preferential policies for ethnic minorities - Arabic text - Islamic unity - Islamic Revival - Jadid Reformation movement in Central Asia - Sinicization programs - Internal colonialism - Condescending look- Chinese Orientalism - *Minkaohan* - *Minkaomin* - People's Republic of China (PRC) - Chinese Communist Party (CCP)

Map #1

A map of Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region that shows some of its cities.

<https://www.studyinchina.com.my/web/page/9-things-you-dont-know-about-xinjiang>

Map #2

A map showing the administrative sectors of Xinjiang Region.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371267365> How Do Geographical Factors Affect the Distribution of Intangible Cultural Heritage A Case Study of Xinjiang China/figures?lo=1

Chapter 1

History and Identity of the Uyghurs in Xinjiang

I An Overview of the Uyghur People

1. Introduction to the Uyghur People
2. Uyghur Nomenclature: an Aspect of Continuity
3. The Uyghurs : Twenty-First Century Scene

II An Overview of Xinjiang

1. Introduction to Xinjiang
2. Nomenclature: a Tool for Control and Assimilation
3. The Region's Geopolitical and Economic Value: The Control of Wealth

III Han Migration to Xinjiang

1. Immigration: a Tool for Assimilating Minorities
2. Han Migration during the Reform Period

Conclusion

Chapter 1: History and Identity of the Uyghurs in Xinjiang

I. An Overview of the Uyghur People

1. Introduction to the Uyghur People

The ancient Chinese civilization exhibits a register full of achievements through which China was positioned on the international map in ancient and contemporary history. The list goes on with China's contributions to philosophy, science, arts and literature, the discovery of gunpowder, the development of porcelain, the use of the abacus, compass, silk and paper making.¹ On top of all of these colossal contributions to human civilization, there is one essential moral addition: The rich diversity, whether religious or ethnic, that China experienced during a period ranging

¹In 751 AD, The Abbasids were victorious over the Chinese Tang Dynasty at the Battle of the Talas River in Transoxiana in Central Asia. In the aftermath of this battle, the Abbasid Empire captured many Chinese prisoners of war, some of whom taught Arab Muslims the process of papermaking. What seemed like an ordinary event turned out to be one of the most glorious historical breakthroughs, allowing the beginning of the monumental translation movement that enriched the Islamic Golden Age: The Muslim Arabs learned papermaking in the eighth century, and then they also transferred that newly acquired skill to the Mediterranean region (**Bloom,2017,p.51**).

between two and three thousand years. Within that ancient civilization, many cultures and ethnicities fused within the Chinese political entity and society, to mention a few: the Turks, Vietnamese, Koreans, Manchu, Mongols and others, even two of the imperial dynasties didn't descend from the Han ethnicity but were Mongols² and Manchu³. Upon its establishment, the People's Republic of China officially recognized the presence of 55 minorities within its borders (**Zang,2012,p.83**), and if we excluded the contemporary political persecution of the Uyghurs and the Tibetans that started early in the Republic's history, critics of the Chinese nation would be at disadvantage in accusing China of racism and discrimination in reference to China's splendid history of pluralism and acceptance.

When the PRC was founded in 1949, the government classified ethnic groups based on an overwhelming majority of the Han that constitute 92% of China's population, compared to 55 ethnic minorities who make up the

²The Yuan Dynasty was established by the nomadic Mongols who ruled parts of China from the early 13th century to late 14th century. It was Kublai Khan, the grandson of Genghis Khan, who founded the Mongol Yuan dynasty which is classified among the Chinese imperial dynasties' registry. That dynasty set about copying a Chinese-style administration that was characterized by a central bureaucracy and a rationalized taxing system, making it a Mongol dynasty in identity, but with a Chinese political and cultural character (**Britannica,2023**).

³The Manchu Qing Dynasty, the last of the imperial dynasties in China, extended its rule from 1644 to 1911. During the Qing era the empire's territory tripled in size from what it was under the previous Ming dynasty, even the same could be said about the population that tripled from approximately 150 million to 450 million, while many non-Chinese minorities within the empire were sinicized (**Britannica,n.d**).

remaining percentage and are randomly distributed over most of China's provinces (**Dabphet,2020,p.56**). Of these minorities, the Chinese government classifies the Uyghur people as a national minority “*Shaoshu Minzu*”, although this classification conceals the fact that the majority of the Uyghur people live in one region and constitute the majority of the population there (**Thum,2018,p.1**), or this was the case before the government imposed demographic change policies during the mid-21st century. Benefiting from preferential policies enacted by China, the Uyghurs are considered the most ultra-nationalist minority in the Republic of China (**Zang,2012,p.83**). Uyghurs represent a nomadic people who depend on agriculture and live in oases; in addition, some merchants and craftsmen are settled in their cities and form a particular group through language and cultural elements (**Cappelletti,2020,p.35**). The Uyghur people are a Turkish Muslim people who follow the Sunni sect (**Zang,2012,p.83**), and constitute the most sizeable minority in Xinjiang; according to statistics for the year 2020, it was found that out of 20 million people in the region, 12 million of them are still of the Uyghur nationality (**Kamalov,2021,p.1**). This number is considered significant despite the fact that in recent decades many Uyghur individuals have fled to the United States, Europe, Turkey and Central Asia

(**Anderson,2012,p.68**), where the number of them fleeing China exceeded the threshold of one million people (**Cappelletti,2020,p.36**). The vast majority of the Uyghur people speak the Uyghur language, a dialect of the eastern branch of the Turkic language family (**Anderson,2012,p.68**), which is written in Arabic script, while a sizeable portion of them do not read, speak, or write the Chinese language but rather cling to their traditional ways of living and communicating (**Zang,2012,p.83**). True that Uyghurs are related to the Turkic peoples native to Central Asia, but in reality they don't have a clear identity and represent a mixture of Indo-European, Mongol, and Turkic peoples, and this is distinctly reflected in their language and customs (**Cappelletti,2020,p.35-36**). It is possible to consider Uyghurs' formation as a "distinct ethnic group" not only due to their contact with the peoples of Central Asia but also through their geographical proximity to China (**Kamalov,2021,p.1**). Uyghurs' first ethnic layers that calcified in their characteristics were formed in the Tarim Basin, and they were the product of the homogeneity of many peoples, cultures, and religions (**Dalati,2019**). That is especially true for the blend of the Indo-Iranian peoples with the Turkish ones, so that the Indo-Iranians were formed from the Tocharians, who were the oldest inhabitants of the Tarim Basin, in addition to the Saka

tribes, the Sogdians, and others. As for the Turkish component, it was formed from the Avars, the Huns, and others (**Kamalov,2021,p.4**). This combination is reflected in their cosmopolitan culture which incorporates remnants of Shamanism⁴, Buddhism⁵, Manichaeism⁶, and Confucianism⁷, where all of these religions were practiced by the Uyghurs at one time and infiltrated the Uyghurs' Islamic customs and traditions during the Chinese communist rule (**Thwaites,2001,p.209**). However, the Chinese communist influence clashed during the 1980s with the “Islamic revival⁸” which played

⁴A religion that believes that shamans can communicate with the other world and the spirits residing in it and can heal the sick. The word shaman is derived from the Jurchen language that was used by the ancestors of the Manchu peoples who inhabited Manchuria. A text also appeared in China in the twelfth century AD, which considers that the word shaman is derived from the Jurchen language and means a sorcerer or wizard (**Sinor,1990,p.419**). Shamanism arose at the time of the hunting-gathering and foraging societies and continued in some herding and agricultural societies after the advent of agriculture. It is associated with animism, a belief system in which the world is home to a large number of spiritual beings who may aid or hinder human endeavors (**Eliade&Diószegi,2023**).

⁵Buddhism, a religion and philosophy that developed from the teachings of the Buddha, surged in northeastern India sometime between the late 6th and early 4th centuries BCE, a period during which the region experienced significant social change and intense religious activity. Buddhism, like many of the religions that developed in northeastern India at that time, was shaped by the presence of a charismatic teacher, and by the teachings disseminated by him to the base (**Britannica,2023**).

⁶It is a dualistic monotheistic religion that has believed in the concept of a struggle between light and darkness since time immemorial. Founded by the Prophet Mani in Iraq within the Sasanian Empire in the third century AD, Manichaeism has spread in Central Asia and Chinese Turkestan, i.e., Xinjiang (**Soucek&Soucek,2000,p.49**). When the Uyghurs settled in East Turkestan in the eighth century, one of their local leaders adopted Manichaeism, and it remained the state religion until it faded away. It is probable that Manichaeism remained present in East Turkestan until the Mongol invasion in the thirteenth century (**Britannica,n.d**).

⁷A worldview, social ethics, political ideology, scientific traditions and way of life. Sometimes viewed as a philosophy and sometimes as a religion, Confucianism can be understood as a comprehensive way of thinking and living, entailing reverence for ancestors and a profound human-centered religiosity. It was founded by Confucius in the 6th and 5th centuries BC and has been followed by the Chinese people for more than two thousand years (**Weiming,2023**).

⁸Many researchers in the Middle East posit that the Islamic revival since the 1970s emerged directly following the defeat of the Arab nations by Israel in 1967. This resounding defeat led to a crisis of Arab identity, a greater interest in fundamentalism, and a “return to the mosque” based on “the desire to link the present to historical and traditional values”. Furthermore, this defeat contributed to a sharp decline in Arab nationalist sentiment and a new search for an ideology of victory and success (**Finley,2013,p.274**). This frustrating phase in the Arab world was rocked in the following decade by the Islamic Revolution in Iran in 1979, which overthrew the Shah's regime in Iran and contributed to the revival of Islam as a political force in the entire region (**Clarke,2011,p.75**).

a major role in defining the ethnic identity of the Uyghurs within the framework of their relationship with the Han Chinese and the PRC, as claimed by many Western scholars (**Zang,2012,p.82**). Although the majority of them call for the independence of East Turkestan by itself, some of the Uyghurs are politically divided between Islamists who call for Islamic unity with the rest of the Islamic Ummah and Turkic nationalists who call for Turkic unity. Additionally, Uyghurs represent the sole significant Turkish-speaking Islamic ethnic group in Central Asia that lacks its own sovereign nation, with Xinjiang, officially recognized as an autonomous region, being their homeland (**Bellér-Hann,2022,p.93**).

2. Uyghur Nomenclature: an Aspect of Continuity

The subject of nomenclature deepens the ambiguity in the process of researching the origin of the Uyghur people. In brief, the naming of the Uyghur is divided into two different meanings: the first is the “ancient Uyghurs” who inhabited the Tarim Basin after the fall of the Second Turkish Khaganate, and the other is related to the contemporary inhabitants of the Xinjiang province in China who came to be known as “Uyghurs” at the

beginning of the twentieth century (**Kamalov,2021,p.2**). The term "Uyghur" is linked to the Uyghur kingdoms that were present before Islam penetrated the region, and while this name had a fleeting presence up until the twentieth century, it was not commonly used as the official designation (**Thum,2014,p.175**). During the gradual conversion to Islam in the area, the ethnic name Uyghur, typically associated with the Buddhist Kingdom of Qocho⁹, was not used to designate the new converts to Islam who lived in the south. And during the fifteenth century in the Turpan Depression¹⁰, the use of the Uyghur name was completely dispensed until the twentieth century, where at that time the Uyghurs identified themselves either socially or geographically, that is, based on their social status or the geographic origin of the oasis they lived in (**Finley,2013,p.3**). Some of the labels common during this period were "Muslim," "Turkish," "*Yerlik*," which means local in Turkish, or "Altishahri," which means a person whose origins go back to the historical Altishahr region (**Thum,2014,p.149**). In this context, Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle

⁹A multi-ethnic, multilingual political entity that emerged in the Turpan Depression, it provided a standard for openness and ushered in an era of peaceful coexistence among many religions in that region (**Kamberi,2015,p.5**) except for the Islamic religion, which it fought off its borders for quite some time. The kingdom expanded the territory it controlled and seized the city of Gaochang, known as Qocho, south of the Tianshan Mountains. This city bore the name of their kingdom and became the winter headquarters, while the city of Beshbalik remained the summer headquarters (**Brose,2017,p.8**).

¹⁰A deep mountain basin in the Xinjiang region of northwest China that eventually descends to 155 meters below sea level, thus forming the lowest point in China (**Britannica,n.d**).

University and an expert in Uyghur studies, suggests that Han historians may have concealed archival evidence demonstrating that the educated and cultured class of the Uyghur community continued to identify as Uyghurs during the historical period when the name seemingly vanished from the 15th to the 20th century (**Finley,2013,p.4**), as part of a strategy to mask their identity.

The Uyghurs only began to unite against external political entities after the Qing dynasty encouraged significant Han migration into Xinjiang in an effort to solidify its presence in the region during the mid-1800s (**Smith,2002,p.4-5**). As a result, the Uyghurs' perception of themselves as a cohesive community, distinct from other Central Asian¹¹ ethnicities, was reinforced by the anticipated danger from eastern China (**Thum,2018,p.2**). In 1910, one Uyghur writer wrote a book under the pseudonym The Uyghur Child: "*Uyghur Ballisi*," and during the 1920s, political and social organizations began using the name Uyghur, and at that moment the discussion centered around the possibility of including all residents of the

¹¹The degree of distinction from the rest of the Central Asian Turks is reinforced in a text found from the eighteenth century, where at that time the Uyghurs used to call themselves "Muslim," so that the writer of this text asks, "Can we Muslims become prisoners of the Kyrgyz?" It should be noted here that the Kyrgyz, from whom the author stripped off their Muslim identity, were, at that time, not only followers of Islam but also followers of the same Naqshbandi Sufi order as the Uyghurs (**Thum,2014,p.149-150**).

Xinjiang of all nationalities into that name, or people whose origin is from Altishahr only (**Thum,2014,p.175**). In 1921, the poet *Abduxaliq Uyghur*¹² composed his poem “Wake Up,” calling on the Uyghur people to shed their negativity and ignorance and to begin embracing responsibility for their own lives and their nation. Through that poem, *Abduxaliq* employed the name Uyghurs, and he also developed a national narrative for his people based on modernization and education, and not just about preserving traditional Uyghur culture (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.7**). The term Uyghur began to be employed officially during the reign of Sheng Shicai¹³ in the 1930s, such that an article appeared in Kashgar's official Turkish-language newspaper, *New Life*, urging readers to use the Uyghur name, which means "unity" or "union," as a "noble national designation" (**Thum,2018,p.6**). This official publication, according to the point of view of American historian Owen Lattimore, a specialist in Chinese and Central Asian history, contributed to the spread of nationalist awareness among the Uyghurs (**Finley,2013,p.92**). In 1985, Canadian researcher Justin Rudelson, professor of anthropology at Tulane University, conducted a field study in the Turpan Depression, the

¹²Uyghur thinker, intellectual, and nationalist (1901-1933). He toured Europe and Russia and learned many languages; there he decided to return to Xinjiang and promote the modern values of freedom and democracy inside his Uyghur community; he was executed during the reign of Sheng Shicai (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.6-7**).

¹³A Han Chinese warlord (1895-1970) that ruled Xinjiang from 1933 to 1944 and was close to the Soviets and the Kuomintang. During his reign, the Uyghurs suffered from brutal political repression (**Smith,2000,p.15**).

result of which was that out of eighty-one people studied, seventy-six of them considered “Uyghur” to be among their three most prominent identities, followed by “Muslim” and the oasis from which the person originates (Thum,2014,p.176). From the 1930s until Rudelson's research in the 1980s, the term used by Uyghurs and by Western scholars to name the Uyghur people remained unknown. In contrast, the Chinese state has assigned various labels to the Uyghur people throughout the last few decades, starting with feudal elements and “ethnic” nationalists in the 1950s and 1960s, moving to counter-revolutionaries in the 1970s and 1980s, and separatists in the 1990s, but from 2001 onward, the majority of Uyghurs have been designated as “terrorists” (HRW,2005,p.7).

3. The Uyghurs : Twenty-First Century Scene

The Uyghur author *Yarmuhämmäd Tahir Tughluq* highlights a particular facet of the 21st-century dynamics involving the Uyghurs, the Chinese government, and the Han majority, referencing a notable statement in his book “Look Ahead, My Son” *Oghlum Aldinggha Qara*: “We are all fighting for our place in this modern world, and regardless of how the world

has evolved, we still prefer our old-fashioned jacket to others' shiny robe." **(Steenberg,2021,p.171)**. This phrase illustrates the relationship between the Han and the Uyghurs as follows: what the Han see as laziness, inertia and reluctance to embrace development and progress among the Uyghur in their work, study, food, clothing, nature, beliefs, daily work, and ways of living, the Uyghurs, in return, see it as accurate adherence of religion and preservation of the traditions, cultural heritage, and common identity, and this matter is necessary for them to persevere in this changing world. Although Chinese Muslims constitute the largest Muslim minority in East Asia, their necessity for survival becomes evident as they perceive themselves as particularly susceptible to dangers that threaten their existence and faith **(Gladney,2003,p.452)**. The dangers linger in the shared memory of the Uyghurs as they reflect on their persecution during the Cultural Revolution¹⁴, which lasted from 1966 to 1976 and saw the diminishment of all types of political and cultural diversity **(Gladney,2003,p.460)**. Back then,

¹⁴The Great Proletarian Cultural Revolution, as it was called, aimed to "purge" powerful officials of questionable loyalty who were residing in Beijing. In May 1966, during a session of the Politburo, Mao launched a campaign to purge those he called Khrushchev's minions and the counter-revolutionary bourgeoisie by utilizing enthusiastic university students who attacked and humiliated Mao's opponents, especially intellectuals, government officials, army officers, and craftsmen. Furthermore, the Red Guards, most of whom were teenagers, also subjected teachers and even their parents to brutal torture sessions for mere intellectual or ideological deviation from the ideas accepted by the Politburo. Following the death of Mao Zedong in 1976, the Cultural Revolution ended prior to Deng assuming power in late 1978, when the new administration initiated the policy of "Boluan Fanzheng," which literally means "eliminating chaos and returning to normal," in order to get rid of the disturbing scenes and chaotic policies practiced during the Cultural Revolution **(Wang,2020,p.135)**.

the aim was to sever the relationship between the Uyghurs and Islam, and this could be achieved by demolishing mosques and burning the Quran. The regime's apprehension lay in the idea that China's ethnic, social, and religious variety could threaten the nation's existence; consequently, their solution was to mold China into a rigidly uniform communist entity. In reference to the collective memory of the Uyghurs, it must be mentioned that Uyghurs self-perceive themselves as heirs to mighty kingdoms and empires¹⁵ that once existed, and that these potent entities contested Chinese hegemony during some period in medieval history. While Uyghurs' strenuous efforts for secession and independence from China during the mid-20th century led them to doubt the feasibility of the "shared history" that the Chinese government is trying to impose to promote integration and assimilation **(Castets,2015,p.223)**. The idea of "shared history" is only a means to the "Han acculturation," an end that the government aspires to enforce by dissolving Uyghur culture within the Han majority. As for the majority of Uyghurs, Islam not only remains an indispensable component of their culture and traditions, but rather a societal refuge and a stronghold of resistance against this "acculturation" process that is imposed by the

¹⁵The Uyghur Khaganate during the 8th and 9th centuries, and the Qocho Kingdom from the 9th century until the 14th century.

government (**Calabrese,2017**). The official imposition of acculturation is coupled with a recent burgeoning nationalist tendency among the Han people, which requires diminishing ethnic and cultural differences with other peoples in China where anyone who is viewed as the “other” in China will suffer, not just the Uyghur people (**Gladney,2003,p.460**). In contrast to their Hui¹⁶ Muslim counterparts, who have assimilated into Chinese society and occupy a different position on the political spectrum, the Uyghurs have not integrated into the socialist framework or the broader community of Chinese ethnic groups (**Calabrese,2017**). True that many of the Uyghurs express their desire to create a separate state (**Gladney,2003,p.466**), there remains a thriving Mandarin¹⁷-speaking Uyghur elite that is integrated well into Chinese society.

Three pivotal events occurred during the period that followed the fall of the Soviet Union¹⁸ in the 20th century; these climactic occurrences altered

¹⁶Hui, pronounced "Khwei," are Mandarin-speaking Chinese Muslims who are among the 55 officially recognized minorities in China, and they are distributed across various Chinese provinces, especially the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region. Hui are more comfortable with their Islamic identity and are fully integrated into Chinese society while maintaining their religious rituals, unlike the resilient Uyghurs (**Mukherjee,2010,p.425**).

¹⁷The mother tongue of two-thirds of the population of China, Mandarin Chinese is spoken throughout the north of the Yangtze River and in most parts of China (**Britannica,2023**).

¹⁸With the advent of the Perestroika and the Glasnost, and later the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989, it became clear that the Soviet Union would soon go quietly through the night. After the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, the United States remained the sole world leader.

the political trajectory of the Uyghurs and impacted their pursuits, whether beneficially or detrimentally, in seeking independence from China. The first event, the momentous one, was the independence domino of the Central Asian countries¹⁹ in 1991, supplying Uyghur groups aspiring for independence with a hefty morale boost (**Gladney,2003,p.457**). The second event was NATO's intervention in Bosnia²⁰ in 1995 and in Kosovo²¹ in 1999. This matter proved that human rights outweigh state sovereignty on the international stage, and in addition, it injected Uyghurs with a dose of hope that NATO could intervene in China if it had intervened militarily in a European country to protect a Muslim minority. However, NATO's military intervention also sounded the alarm bell among the Chinese decision-makers and caused them to focus their attention to solve the Uyghur Question (**Bovingdon,2004,p.11-12**). The third and final matter that struck the Uyghur cause with a fatal blow was the September 11 terrorist attacks, which shifted the status quo in the entire world and reduced the possibility of the International Community participating in a military operation to support the

¹⁹Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkmenistan.

²⁰The Bosnia and Herzegovina War (1992-1995), a war among multiple wars that occurred following the collapse of the Yugoslav Federation, was an ethnic/religious conflict between Muslim Bosniaks, Orthodox Serbs, Catholic Croats, and the former Yugoslav army. After years of bitter fighting, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) imposed a final ceasefire between the warring factions (**Lamp,2023**).

²¹Kosovo War (1998-1999), an ethnic/religious war between Albanians and Serbs in the province of Kosovo, which later gained independence from Serbia and became a partially recognized state. The conflict also ended after NATO's intervention in favor of the Albanian Muslims (**Britannica,2023**).

Uyghur minority (**Bovingdon,2004,p.12**). Indeed, the “global war on terror” was declared immediately after the attacks and it may have encouraged Beijing to respond to Western political and human rights entities that opposed it by tightening its grip on Xinjiang, thus reducing the already diminished levels of autonomy exercised by the Uyghurs in their homeland (**Bovingdon,2004,p.48**). This is in political analysis, but when studying people, they must be explored within a collective framework; in most cases, the groups’ actions are emotional, impassioned, ill-considered, and illogical. Most revolutions and uprisings occur in environments in which the people are incensed and exasperated, waiting for any simple, accidental, or meager event that would cause the powder keg to ignite. The Uyghurs’ political class did not read the geopolitical situation well after the September 11 terror attacks, and they continued injudiciously to project their desire for an independent identity separate from the Chinese modernist scheme imposed by the Chinese government²².In their attempt to promote a modern social and political system instead of the one imposed by the Chinese government, the

²²The ongoing meddling by the Chinese government in personal choices, exemplified by the detrimental "one-child policy," has created challenges for many working women in China, particularly in terms of marriage and starting families during the 2010s and 2020s. The Chinese government interfered in nature’s processes and started hunting swallows, where nearly two billion sparrows were killed during the period preceding the great Chinese famine in the late 1950s. This necessitated an abnormal increase in the number of locusts, leading to devastating losses in crops and thus the exacerbation of the famine due to environmental imbalance. For this, and for many other reasons, I find it always interesting and enticing to study Chinese modern history.

Uyghurs strengthened their Islamic and national identity to combat the neo-colonialist projects coming from the Chinese capital, Beijing (Castets,2015,p.223).

II. An Overview of Xinjiang

1. Introduction to Xinjiang

Regions and territories derive their significance when several factors are present, including moral, political, and economic importance. The significance of a region—both morally and historically—resonates within the collective consciousness of its people, shaped by their presence in that area during a specific historical period. The second importance is geopolitical and the third importance is the richness of the region in economic resources such as oil, gas, and uranium. In every instance, Xinjiang encompasses all the previously mentioned significance—historical, geopolitical, and economic—while also holding a sentimental and romantic²³

²³Originating from the German principalities, Romanticism was a cultural movement that took shape and diffused into several European cultures in the early 19th century, significantly impacting literature, music, and fine arts across the continent (Wolf,1940,p.145). Following the Age of Enlightenment, Romanticism dominated European society during the first half of the 1800s, drawing from cultural interactions with the East that prioritized the value of the

value that linked it to the Silk Roads²⁴. Recently, numerous studies have focused on the Silk Roads as scholars and researchers seek to comprehend how various historical cultures from distant regions combined to create a unified human civilization, facilitating the exchange of sciences and knowledge along the routes linking East Asia to West Asia, Europe and Africa. This romantic template of the Silk Roads generated a curiosity among scholars to come to Xinjiang and study it as a valuable crossroads between many different regions and civilizations, rather than considering it as a deprived backyard of a powerful country like China, marred by backwardness and lacking in relevance (**Bellér-Hann,2022,p.96**).

Positioned at the center of the Silk Roads, Xinjiang served as a pivotal connection between Central and East Asia, functioning as a significant gateway for both regional and global trade for approximately two millennia

individual and his spirit, especially concerning emotions and feelings, as opposed to the Enlightenment's emphasis on intellect and material matters. This movement arose in response to the industrial revolution, which desensitized workers, treating them like machines, and its effects were evident in the rise of nationalism among people during that era.

²⁴The Silk Roads, not the Silk Road, because the trade that the Chinese conducted with the Near East and Europe through Central Asia did not pass through one specific road, but rather through several interconnected ones (**Millward,2007,p.29**). And since these roads contributed to the spread of papermaking, it is possible to term them paper roads or papermaking roads, where papermaking had a greater impact on human history and caused many more changes, especially in the Islamic world and Europe, than silk, which was neither a cheap nor accessible commodity for the masses. Silk roads also contributed to the spread of Buddhism in Asia and China, coming from India through them.

(Arya,2010,p.189). Cross-border foreign ideologies, religions, and influences became among the most crucial “imports” that reached the people living around the desert oases in that region who earned their livelihood through agriculture. In Xinjiang, religions penetrated the region by religious scholars who disseminated ideas to the people living there throughout these centuries **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.12-13)**. The Central Asian region was considered pivotal to the ancient world²⁵ in regards to world trade, despite the fact that after the discovery of the Americas during the late fifteenth century, transatlantic trade between Europe and America flourished in its place. And in the heart of Central Asia, the region of Xinjiang, or East Turkestan by its ancient name, occupied a link that connected the East and West in that ancient world. While the intermittent control of successive Chinese empires over that region should also be considered a reflection of the ebb and flow, or the strength and weakness, of China’s historical hegemony and influence over the Central Asian region **(Han,2010,p.246)**. Where Inner China in the Far East of Asia meets Central Asia, the Middle East, and Europe, East Turkestan remained a pivotal region at the crossroads of multiple cultures, affected at different times by different cultures

²⁵The part of the world consisting of Europe, Asia, and Africa that Europeans knew before Christopher Columbus's expedition to the Americas **(Cambridge-dictionary,n.d)**.

(Finley,2013,p.245) to become cosmopolitan in its structure, a melting pot of the east and the west.

Radical transformations occurred within Central Asia during the 20th century, for example, the “Great Game”²⁶ between Tsarist Russia and Great Britain and the collapse of the Qing Empire²⁷ and the rise of the Soviet Union, affecting East Turkestan at various levels. Due to its remote location as a border region, East Turkestan fostered a stronger sense of connection between the region and its native Uyghur population than with any other groups in the more central areas, who might be more open to Chinese cultural and political assimilation. Through China’s imposition of political dependency on this region and its inhabitants, the linguistic, cultural, and religious difference emerged between them and the people in inner China, and in return, the umbilical cord was cut between Uyghurs and their Central Asian counterparts, who share closer historical and cultural ties (Bellér-Hann,2012,p.204). Thus, Chinese hegemony, especially during the

²⁶A geopolitical confrontation between Russia and Britain in Central Asia known as the "Great Game" (Kamalov,2021,p.4). This name was given by British Lieutenant Arthur Connelly in 1834 when he visited India and warned his government that Russia could influence Britain’s interests in the region (Figs,2011,p.49).

²⁷The 1911 revolution in China overthrew the Chinese Empire and ended the rule of the Qing dynasty (Dillon,1997,p.81). Before the revolution occurred, the Chinese Empire continued for more than two millennia under the name of several dynasties, and after the revolution, a republic was established that was marred by chaos for a long period.

Communist era, succeeded in isolating Xinjiang from external influences coming from Central Asia and India, and in turn directed it into China. It became possible to summarize the history of Xinjiang after 1949, the year in which the Chinese People's Liberation Army "peacefully" annexed the region into the burgeoning Republic of China, as a history full of attempts by the Chinese government to overcome non-Chinese external influences, which have always been able to penetrate the region. It is important to remember that the geographical features of the region make it easier for outside influences to enter, which means that Xinjiang, also known as East Turkestan, has consistently absorbed various external cultures and ideas (Clarke,2007,p.64).

2. Nomenclature: a Tool for Control and Assimilation

Countries retain many tools in order to modify the situation of a specific region or territory with the aim of annexing it or presenting it as belonging to it historically. Among these tools, a state could distort the historical narrative of that region or displace many of its original inhabitants while seeking the settlement of other people in it to assimilate the few

remaining. Moreover, states may counterfeit or forge documents, data, and reports that indicate or prove the existence of a particular group of people on this land different from its real native population. In regards to the latter governmental option, the Information Office of the Chinese State Council in July 2019 issued a document stating that the Xinjiang region has been part of China since the Han Dynasty²⁸, while a lengthy process of migration and integration shaped the Uyghur people and formed their ethnic culture. It also claimed that Islam was not the original or only belief of the Uyghurs, but the expansion of the Arab empire forcefully imposed Islam on them and brought it to that geographical area (**Euronews,2019**). Following the Mongol domination²⁹, Xinjiang became increasingly shaped by Islamic Sufism and the intense competition among various Sufi sects, reaching its height in the 17th century. During this chaotic period, the Qing dynasty³⁰ managed to

²⁸The Qing dynasty was founded in 206 BC and lasted for about four hundred years until 220 AD. It is one of the greatest imperial dynasties that ruled eastern China, and that dynasty formed what later became considered Chinese culture, to the point that the word "Han" became synonymous with a person of Chinese origin (**Britannica,n.d**).

²⁹The Mongol dominance over the Uyghur kingdom in East Turkestan can be categorized into two segments: the initial phase involves the influence of the Kara Khitai, a Mongolian state with Chinese influences, while the second phase consists of the Mongol Empire established by Genghis Khan, which spanned from China to the Islamic East. The Mongols were influenced by the Uyghur culture, which can be considered a sophisticated and advanced one. Starting from the 13th century, the Mongols began using the Uyghur script in their writings. Genghis Khan also asked Uyghurs to teach his children through the Uyghur scripts (**Drompp,2005,p.199**). After more than a century of Mongol hegemony, the Chagatai Empire annexed the Kingdom of Qocho during the mid-14th century. The Chagatai Empire is one of 4 kingdoms that inherited the Mongol Empire, which was dissolved during the mid-14th century.

³⁰Throughout the centuries, the terms "China" and the geographical area known as "China" became interchangeable, as the region was originally referred to as the "Great Qing," which signifies the Qing dynasty, ruled by the Manchu people from Manchuria in modern-day northeastern China. The Qing dynasty tried hard to uproot their nomadic character and adapt to the aspects of Chinese civilization (**Zhao,2008,p.50**).

incorporate the region in 1759 (**Bellér-Hann,2022,p.94**). Known as East Turkestan, this region has a Persian origin meaning "Land of the Turks," which Turkish and Russian nationalists used to define the Tarim Basin and Dzungaria in the east as distinct from West Turkestan, which is located west of the Pamir Mountains³¹ (**Dwyer,2005,p.51**).

Continuing its plan to sinicize the annexed East Turkestan region, the Qing Dynasty changed the name of the area to better align with the newly constructed sinicized identity of its local inhabitants. So all the names by which that region was called, such as East Turkestan, Chinese Turkestan, and Uyghurstan, were replaced with “Xinjiang,” which means "new frontier" (**Arya,2010,p.189**); thus a new wording was added to that region to reveal it as a distant border of the Chinese Empire rather than an existing and independent region in itself. Following the collapse of the Qing Dynasty in the 1911 Chinese Revolution, the New Republic of China annexed this region as a colonial entity and placed Han leaders in charge, who maintained a delicate tie to the central state authority. In imitation of the Soviet style of

³¹The Pamir Mountains are located deep in the heart of Central Asia and among the Silk Roads, mostly in the present-day country of Tajikistan. Some have suggested it means "roof of the world," while others say it comes from the words Poi Mihra, which literally means foot of the sun, as the locals would always see the sun rising behind the mountains (**Shvili,2020**).

government based on ethnic federalism, the Chinese government renamed the region the "Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region," or "XUAR" (Aljazeera.net,2021). Although Xinjiang is a province-level administrative unit, China doesn't consider it a province but an autonomous region out of respect for the majority of non-Han population, namely the Uyghurs and many other recognized minorities. However, the non-Han populations in Xinjiang and the migrant groups in Kazakhstan, Turkey, Germany, and other locations avoid using the term Xinjiang due to its associations with Chinese imperialist connotations; they seek to oppose the imposed sinicization by referring to the area as East Turkestan instead (Dillon,1997,p.80). Officially, "Xinjiang" is the only designation permitted, while other symbolic names used by the Uyghurs have fallen out of use and are now limited to private discussions and personal contexts. The symbolic names preserved by the Uyghurs pertain to a community that has been denied the political right to sketch a map of their homeland in the 21st century (Thum,2014,p.3) or to assign a name that better reflects their shared history and culture.

Regardless of its nature, if it is a historical region for a people, a frontier territory belonging to a vast empire, or even an autonomous region

stamped by the culture and language of the dominant majority, a look at this region from above may be enough to understand and extrapolate the cultural and religious identity of the native inhabitants of that region. From the numerous mosques to the veiled women, and from the men wearing the Uyghur skullcap, the *doppa*, to the Uyghur writing in Arabic script written on shop windows and street signs, this is only an indication of the identity of Muslim Uyghurs who do not belong to the ethnicity of the majority in the state and cling to their customs while resisting official attempts of integration that endured for quite a while. Revisiting the issue of nomenclature, it's clear that despite the diversity and the "we-vs.-them" mindset in China's interaction with the region's indigenous peoples, one can easily envision the Chinese government's ongoing efforts to assimilate what it regards as the "Islamic border region" into the more robust and dominant Chinese state, even if that term is not officially used **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.267)**. As a result of these adjustment programs, East Turkestan, historically known as Altishahr, meaning "the six cities," has faded from existence and transformed into a new geographical entity aligned with Chinese interests, crafted to reflect the Chinese historical narrative **(Thum,2014,p.4)**. The geographical term "the lands of the West" changed

from being merely a region located in western China to a condescending look by itself that existed historically among the Han regarding most of the “backward” peoples living on the western borders, on whom “Chinese development” must be imposed to motivate them to follow the Chinese development train (Dwyer,2005,p.51). To wind up, the change in nomenclature represents a tool to impose an altered reality that highlights a right acquired through power and dominance, and it also reflects on the imbalanced relationship that links both the authoritarian Chinese state and a weak, dispersed minority that does not possess a unified leadership and is forced to assimilate and integrate into the Chinese society. Thus, this minority was absorbed and lost the symbolic designation of the region that they used to, and still, call “homeland.”

3. The Region's Geopolitical and Economic Value: The Control of Wealth

Although the Chinese consider East Turkestan to be a backward and useless border region inhabited by non-Chinese people in need of a “Chinese civilizing mission,” the decision of the CCP leaders to send the People’s

Liberation Army after the end of the Chinese Civil War³² to annex it “peacefully” in 1949 was a farsighted decision by all standards, and this is evident in its strategic and economic importance within the contemporary period of Chinese rise and Chinese soft power³³. In this context, Mao Zedong³⁴, the Chinese leader, sought to create a mutually beneficial relationship between the Chinese populace and minority groups, based on his point of view. Mao considered that: “The Han people have the largest population and constitute the majority of China, and they can raise the standard of living and socialist awareness of the minorities, while the latter can provide China with its regions rich in natural resources necessary for industrialization and development.” **(Moneyhon,2003,p.491)**. Ethnic minority areas not only possess an abundance of natural resources but also

³²This war began when the leader of the Chinese Nationalists, Chiang Kai-shek, aimed to overthrow the communists in what was known as the Shanghai Massacre in 1927. By crushing the communists mercilessly in Shanghai and initiating a civil war between communists and nationalists, Chiang Kai-shek was able to buy the neutrality of major foreign companies in Shanghai and the sympathy of Chinese business centers **(Gernet,1996,p.634)**. In 1949, the civil war came to an end with the defeat of the Nationalist troops, who then fled to Taiwan. Then, in 1949, Mao Zedong announced in front of millions of his supporters in Tiananmen Square the establishment of the People's Republic of China **(Stewart,2001,p.50)**.

³³The economic dominance through which a country can manage political matters within another country according to its interest. China's soft power was fully demonstrated during the political crisis in Sri Lanka in 2022 and during the Maldives elections in 2023, in which the coalition leaning towards China emerged victorious.

³⁴Chinese theorist, thinker, and revolutionary leader (1893–1976) of the Chinese Communist Party from 1935 and chairman of the People's Republic of China from 1949 until his death. As China emerged from half a century of revolution as the most populous country in the world and launched itself on the path of economic development and social change, Mao occupied a crucial place in the country's renaissance **(Schram,2023)**. He is considered the architect of the "Leap Forward" between 1958 and 1962 and the "Cultural Revolution" between 1966 and 1976, and his policies caused the deaths of 20 to 30 million Chinese during the Great Famine between 1959 and 1961. The strategies implemented by Mao regarding the Uyghurs resulted in the erosion of their cultural heritage and a decline in their religious liberties **(Dabphet,2020,p.55)**.

have critical geographical and strategic significance, enabling China to potentially develop these places into security buffer zones

(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.348). Therefore, the regions that once bordered the Chinese empires are now simply parts of modern-day China and enjoy self-rule in order to appease their residents of non-Chinese minorities.

In addition to four other autonomous regions: Guangxi, {the Zhuang minority region}, Xizang {the Tibet population region}, Ningxia {the Hui minority region}, and Inner Mongolia {the Mongols minority region} **(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.348)**, Xinjiang is located on the northwestern border of China and extends 2,000 kilometers from east to west and 1650 kilometers from north to south **(Dillon,1997,p.80)**. Established in 1955 as “Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region” or XUAR, Xinjiang represents a frontier zone once it was integrated into the Chinese political entity from the mid-18th century **(Bellér-Hann,2022,p.93)**. Xinjiang occupies an area of one million six hundred thousand square kilometers **(Dillon,1997,p.80)**, which makes up about $\frac{1}{6}$ of China's area **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.3)**, making it the largest administrative unit in that country **(Arya,2010,p.189)**, equal to the area of France, Germany, and Italy together **(Shichor,2005,p.125)**.

Xinjiang is bordered by eight countries: Pakistan, India, Afghanistan, Mongolia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Russia **(Dillon,1997,p.80)**. Xinjiang has long drawn Western interest because of its strategic location in Inner Asia and because of the presence of China's Lop Nor nuclear testing site on its territory **(Arya,2010,p.189)**. In addition, the Xinjiang autonomous region is divided into eight provinces, namely Turpan, Hami, Aksu, Kashgar, Khotan, Altay, Tacheng, and Ili. Although Muslims constitute the majority in Xinjiang, they do not form a single solid identity group because there are many linguistic and cultural differences between Muslim ethnic groups inhabiting the region **(Cappelletti,2020,p.34)**. The Xinjiang region is shaped like a diamond, consisting of two basins surrounded by mountains that divide the region into two halves **(Dwyer,2005,p.3)**, the Tarim Basin and the Junggar Basin, located in the south and north of the Tianshan Mountains³⁵, respectively **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.3)**. In addition to the Uyghur and Han people, Xinjiang is home to a number of Turkic peoples, such as the Kyrgyz and the Kazakh,

³⁵Meaning the Heavenly Mountains in Chinese, it is a mountain range in Central Asia extending over 2,800 kilometers from Uzbekistan to China. It is surrounded by the western and northern ends of the Taklamakan Desert on the border of Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan and borders China's Xinjiang, the Pamir Mountains to the south, and the Altai Mountains in Mongolia to the east and north. The area near the Tianshan Mountains is home to several ethnic groups, the largest of which are the Uyghurs in the west and the Kyrgyz in the east; other groups include the Uzbeks, Kazakhs, and Mongols **(Prop,2019)**.

and non-Turkish peoples, such as the Hui and the Mongol Oirats and others **(Dwyer,2005,p.3)**. Xinjiang is also connected to parts of Central and South Asia either by land or by rail lines, making it a vital strategic transport corridor to other parts of Asia **(Mukherjee,2010,p.432)**. Therefore, Xinjiang occupies the center of transportation with Eurasia, and through it, China may revive the Silk Roads³⁶ **(Zanardi,2019,p.1)**, taking advantage of the region's expanded international borders that may create a favorable situation for foreign trade **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.3)**. A geography rich in natural resources mixed with an ethnically diverse population **(Cappelletti,2020,p.2)** obliges Beijing to identify the geostrategic importance of Xinjiang and tighten its grip on it at any possible cost **(Mukherjee,2010,p.432)**.

Xinjiang's economic value is no less important than the geopolitical one. The ongoing efforts by the Chinese government to assimilate and integrate the Xinjiang population, aimed at reducing insecurity and preserving the hard-won stability of the 2020s, highlight the region's economic importance, which supplies a substantial portion of the essential

³⁶People from different places, faiths, and cultures met and traded along the Silk Roads; they entered into agreements and engaged in warfare too. Recently, academic interest in the Silk Roads as a global fulcrum has been revived, and it has reemerged thanks to the growing prominence of China and India in global trade. The global commercial center tilted towards Eurasia after it had been Transatlantic in previous centuries.

natural resources driving China's economic development **(Bovingdon,2004,p.2)**. Moreover, Xinjiang fulfills a significant role in accommodating the resettlement of Han Chinese, allowing for their movement from central and eastern China to help mitigate population strain in those locations **(Dwyer,2005,p.2-3)**. And due to the huge population levels in China, which ranks second in the world after India since April 2023 **(Hertog&Gerland&Wilmoth,2023)**, its economy is always hungry for more energy to meet the sizable needs of its eager population **(Moneyhon,2003,p.496)**. This constant energy demand had obliged the Chinese government to set its sights on this region, which contains some of the largest oil reserves in the world **(Moneyhon,2004,p.4)**. Xinjiang has about 25% of the total oil and natural gas reserves and 38% of the coal in all of China **(Mukherjee,2010,p.432)**. Geological surveys indicate that the Tarim Basin in Xinjiang contains large oil deposits, which some believe are three times more than all of the United States' oil reserves **(Moneyhon,2003,p.496)**. In addition to the fact that about 68 million hectares, or 42% of the total area of Xinjiang, are allocated for the development of agriculture, forestry, and animal husbandry **(Mukherjee,2010,p.432)**, Xinjiang is distinguished by its cotton industry, as

it constitutes approximately 20% of global cotton production (**Qasim,2022**).

American historian Owen Lattimore, a specialist in Chinese and Central Asian history, focuses on the competition between China and Xinjiang; he sees it as a reflection of a competition between Chinese agricultural societies and the nomadic steppe societies of the Chinese West (**Arya,2010,p.191**).

This reinforces the assumption among the Han people that China contributed to the development of agricultural programs in Xinjiang, thus strengthening the theory that the Han are responsible for the development of all peoples living under the Chinese state. While in the economy, the consequences of asymmetric development are nowhere more evident in China than in the Xinjiang region (**Moneyhon,2003,p.496**), where the population distribution of ethnic groups in it roughly follows north-south and urban-rural divides (**Han,2010,p.249**), so that the Han people are among the majority residents of the urban industrial areas of the north (**Moneyhon,2003,p.497**) that teem with natural resources and are closest to Russia (**Freeman,2020,p.317**).

Conversely, in the southern section of Xinjiang, which is an agricultural basin, oil reserves can be found in the Tarim Basin, alongside a thriving community of ethnic minorities, particularly the Uyghurs (**Moneyhon,2003,p.497**). There is no region in China like Xinjiang in which

the importance of assimilation with regard to the economic issue is clearly evident. An economically valuable region like it supplies China with the largest share of wealth and economic prosperity, and this is achieved through the imposition of assimilation³⁷ while depriving the indigenous people of the region of the bounties of their motherland.

III. Han Migration to Xinjiang

1. Immigration: a Tool for Assimilating Minorities

Since the dawn of history, people have migrated from one place to another in search of resources such as water, food, a place of residence, and other necessities of life, where most ancient peoples were not bound by any barriers or borders, so they have traveled anywhere and everywhere. This was the chief contributor to people learning common knowledge and sciences and exchanging cultures between the people migrating and the people residing; thus, the human civilization's development had intensified

³⁷The difference between integration and assimilation can be summed up in that in the first, the minority preserves some of its culture, while in the second, it completely dissolves into the culture of the dominant group.

to what it has reached currently. This migration is considered a natural thing and has always occurred throughout history, but in modern day China and in other places as well, there was another type of migration that was directed, had a clear goal and targeted a specific group. In China, immigration not only began with the establishment of the People's Republic, but coupled with the view of the elite class of the Han people's right to sinicize³⁸, own, inhabit, develop, and cultivate reclaimable frontier lands far from the Chinese interior, the Han migration to Xinjiang began in the middle of the nineteenth century during the Qing dynasty (**Dillon,1997,p.80**). By emulating Stalin's policies that uncovered unpopulated areas in Siberia³⁹, Sun Yat-sen⁴⁰ demanded the opening of the northwestern regions during the reign of the Nationalist Government in order to stimulate Han migration from eastern China to develop the border region that includes Xinjiang (**Mukherjee,2010,p.428**). Like the Qing dynasty and the Nationalists before

³⁸One of the oldest sinicization programs happened during the reign of the Mongol Emperor Kublai Khan, the founder of the Yuan dynasty, which is considered a Chinese dynasty. The status of Mongol invaders evolved from being nomads of the northern steppes to settling in the urban centers of Southern China, and Kublai himself took up the study of Confucian philosophy, ultimately becoming a follower.

³⁹The northernmost region of Asia which occupies an area of thirteen million five hundred thousand square kilometers, and most of the lands in it belong to the Russian Federation. It is one of the largest land areas in the world, and without it, Russia would not be the largest country in the world. Its name in the Tatar language means sleeping land (**Shvili,2021**).

⁴⁰A Chinese leader and politician (1866-1925) who contributed to the overthrow of the Qing empire and served as the first president of the Republic of China. He initiated the discourse of Sino-Centrism, Han nationalism, and that China is made up of one ethnicity and the rest of the national minorities will eventually dissolve and merge within the state of China, a single state for the Han (**Hyer,2006,p.76-77**).

them, in order to impose stability on that border region, the Communist Party called on the Han people to migrate to Xinjiang **(Smith,2002,p.6)**. This central government-sponsored migration to Xinjiang was an essential element in the management of the Communist Party in an attempt to confront the political pressure of the Uyghurs, who constituted the overwhelming majority in Xinjiang **(Bovingdon,2004,p.23)**.

At the time when the establishment of the People's Republic of China was announced in 1949, the Uyghur farmers and oasis residents constituted $\frac{3}{4}$ of the population of the Xinjiang region. At that time, the proportion of Han in Xinjiang was barely a tenth of the aggregate population, while the rest were ethnic minorities such as Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Russians, Mongols, and others **(Lüthi,2013,p.157)**. A year after Xinjiang became part of the People's Republic, it was declared that a program to encourage Han migration to Xinjiang would commence in 1950 **(Moneyhon,2003,p.504)**, with the goal of increasing the Han population and solidifying government control while diminishing Islamic influence and dismantling the traditional social and political structures of the Uyghurs **(Dillon,1997,p.81)**. At the same time, this program sought to economically and socially integrate

Xinjiang and its inhabitants into the developing People's Republic of China **(Zang,2012,p.88)**. "Migration to Xinjiang" remained the key driver of demographic fluctuations in that region; Han migration reached its peak in the early 1960s, only to return and weaken during the 1970s **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.122)**. It also played a role in helping the Chinese government reach its target; as of 1978, the Han population had increased to represent 40% of the region's total population, coinciding with the start of the reform era in China **(Bovingdon,2004,p.24)**, during which Xinjiang ranked second in terms of the most popular destination for Han migrants after Heilongjiang province⁴¹ In the northeast **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.122)**.

A disaster of biblical proportions, the great famine⁴² resulting from Mao Zedong's half-baked policies during the Great Leap Forward⁴³ obliged many famished people from within China to flee into Xinjiang on their own

⁴¹A province in the far northeast of China, occupying the northeastern part of China and sharing an international border with Russia. Its area is four hundred and fifty thousand square kilometers, and its population is estimated at thirty-eight million people **(Sen-Nag,2019)**.

⁴²The deadliest famine and one of the greatest man-made disasters in the annals of human history; the period from 1959 to 1961 saw a total death toll estimated between 16 million and 45 million people **(Ming,Qian,&Yared,2015,p.1573)**. This famine affected the countryside, and the challenges of drought and floods worsened the rural conditions between the harvest periods of 1959 and 1960. Indifferent to the red flags, Chairman Mao's absurd and arbitrary decisions to send peasants to work in the cities exacerbated the horrors of the disaster.

⁴³An economic program and social campaign led by the Chinese Communist Party from 1958 to 1962, which was termed the second five-year plan. The Chinese emulated the Soviet industrialization model with the intention of increasing production, especially steel and iron. Mao was reproached by certain party members for the Great Famine, which led to a temporary diminishment in his powers.

initiative and not by the government programs. The search for food and shelter during those strenuous years proved to be the main catalyst for Han migration, which reached its peak during the first half of the 1960s **(Bovingdon,2004,p.19)**. The Han immigrants who came to Xinjiang during the 1950s and 1960s were known as “early settlers” and “pioneers,” and they laboriously tried to learn the Uyghur language, integrate into Uyghur society, and adapt to its exotic cultural characteristics **(Byler,2018,p.35-36)**. The early settlers were assembled into structured units that enforced stringent manual labor set to the "Red Hymns," which glorified Mao; their shared rice bowls were also portioned to reflect the dire famine conditions prevalent in rural China during that period, implementing the notion that “communism is fair to all its people” **(Byler,2018,p.202)**. Although the government claims that its declared goal of relocating Han youth from city schools to Xinjiang is to develop the region economically and culturally **(Finley,2013,p.23)**, its covert goal was to protect and secure China's territorial integrity, as well as to transform Xinjiang into agricultural colonies **(Byler,2018,p.22)**. In administrative terms, the population of Xinjiang was first categorized not just by family ties but also by ethnicity following the influx of a significant number of Han people. This categorization further extended based on each

person's legal residency status, distinguishing between urban and rural dwellers **(Byler,2018,p.203)**. In the south, where the character is predominantly rural, the first Han settlers constituted a small percentage of the population of those areas and learned to respect the Uyghur customs and traditions; even some children born to Han settlers spoke the Uyghur language fluently **(Finley,2013,p.74)**. Another objective for sending Han settlers to the border was to secure it against any possible Soviet incursion into that region, especially during the Sino-Soviet split **(Byler,2018,p.22)**. Numerous people among the Han settlers who came from inner China suffered purges and humiliation during the anti-rightist campaign and the Cultural Revolution, due to the regime's accusations of their ties to the bourgeois capitalist class **(Lüthi,2013,p.164)**. Some immigrants were among Mao's most enthusiastic blinded partisans, most of whom were university students dressed as “Red Guards” **(Cappelletti,2020,p.44-45)** staying in a Muslim majority region. As a result, it was fitting for Xinjiang to evolve into a battlefield of ideas between the two ideologically opposed factions.

The Han migration did not please the local population in Xinjiang, as those strategic and political goals of the government did not find a foothold

within the special spatial and cultural boundaries of the Uyghurs, who feared that they had become a national minority within their lands **(Zang,2012,p.88)** and looked towards the directed immigration programs as nothing but an attempt to destroy their Islamic culture and sinicize that whole region **(Mukherjee,2010,p.428)**. It is possible to conclude that the region, after the arrival of migratory caravans there, turned into a hub of ethnic and religious strife, and governing it in order to stabilize it was extremely difficult **(Moneyhon,2003,p.504)**. Uyghurs fiercely resisted Han migration to their areas as a way to emphasize their Islamic affiliation **(Zang,2012,p.88)**, which may not be compatible with the special lifestyle of the Han people, knowing that the government has established organized urban projects and followed a policy of settling Han immigrants in areas where there are slim to none Uyghur numbers in order to prevent conflicts and reduce the conspicuous cultural and social disparity between them **(Smith,2002,p.18)**. Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, presented three conclusions emerging from Chinese government policies, which she described as unwise: First, augmenting the burden on the fragile borders between different cultures and ethnicities in Xinjiang and the difficulty of

managing the differences arising from it. Second, as pressure on resources and competition for jobs and education intensified, Uyghurs began to form their own perceptions of inequality in their region (**Finley,2013,p.408**). The ultimate conclusion reached by Finley is that the local competition between the residents of various oases has disappeared and been replaced by a new religious, cultural, social, and economic threat to the Uyghur people, which is the threat of Han immigrants (**Smith,2002,p.5**).

2. Han Migration during the Reform Period

It is possible to point out that the levels of ebb and flow of Han migration directed to Xinjiang, organized by the central government, are a clear reflection of the shape of Chinese society and its economic system. When there was a need to escalate agricultural output to meet the high internal demand during the 1950s and 1960s within the framework of an agricultural Chinese society divided into communes⁴⁴, the Chinese government stimulated internal migration to the countryside. But with the

⁴⁴The commune is similar to a self-cooperative, which is headed by an official who seeks to maximize the crop yield so that the state can distribute it to workers in factories in the cities to feed them. In 1958, the number of communes peaked at 70,000 (**Fairbank&Merle,1992,p.354**).

beginning of China's transformation from an agricultural society to an industrial and commercial society⁴⁵ during the reform period, the economic reasons for government-directed and organized migration to the countryside disappeared, and the numbers of immigrants sharply declined in the late 1970s. In this way, immigration lost a lot of momentum and was limited to the ethnic factor, which the government takes into account to avert any minority from isolating in certain areas and forming a majority there. As an assumption, if the Uyghur people organized their ranks today to demand the independence of Xinjiang as its homeland, millions of Han, Mongolian, and ethnic Turkish groups close to the Uyghurs would oppose their demand **(Bovingdon,2004,p.28)**. This hybridization arises from the immigration program implemented by the government, gaining support from academics in China. For instance, sociologist Fei Xiaotong, former professor of sociology at Peking University, stated the following: “Efforts are being made in Xinjiang to prepare it to become an important socialist economic base in the next century, and this requires financial support from the central government and an additional labor force. The developed regions in the East

⁴⁵An indication of an industrial Chinese economy during the reform period was the slogan "Strong industry, weak agriculture," where agricultural products and their raw materials were assigned reduced prices while manufactured goods' prices were through the roof, so the lion's share of state revenues came from industry **(Shirk,1993,p.109)**.

will assist the West to achieve rapid economic and cultural development, and in return, the West can absorb the population increase in the East and relieve the pressure of high population density.” **(Cappelletti,2020,p.91-92)**.

Since the 1980s, levels of state-regulated migration have declined. Instead, a large number of migrants have moved to Xinjiang on their own initiative. These migrants do not receive state sponsorship but are simply looking for work opportunities and ways to increase their income **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.122)**. In contrast to previous migratory caravans that swarmed Xinjiang in the mid-20th century, economic motivation, surplus agricultural labor, and open market policies remained to some extent the most crucial drivers of Han migration during the reform period **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.122)**. In addition, dodging family conflicts and evading the one-child policy, which was more sternly practiced in Inner China, were among the prime societal reasons that prompted Han individuals to migrate to Xinjiang **(Lüthi,2013,p.157)**. In stark contrast to the population distribution in Xinjiang in the mid-20th century, where only 5% of the population of Xinjiang were from the Han group in 1941 **(Bellér-Hann,2022,p.94)**, their numbers rose eventually to nearly half of

Xinjiang's population by 1979 (**Moneyhon,2004,p.7**). The dramatic increase in the percentage of Han residents in Xinjiang is especially pronounced in Ürümqi⁴⁶, the regional capital, where Han individuals now make up more than 75% of the population, causing the Uyghurs to become a minority there (**Zang,2012,p.89-90**). Until the 1990s, many rural Uyghurs had never met Han people face-to-face (**Byler,2018,p.36**). The ongoing influx of Han individuals into many cities in northern Xinjiang has resulted in the Uyghurs losing their status as the absolute majority; however, the situation varies in southern Xinjiang, which has a more rural landscape, allowing the Uyghurs to retain their majority, particularly in the Tarim Basin, their ancestral homeland (**Thum,2018,p.10**).

The death of Mao Zedong in 1976 and the advent of Deng Xiaoping's reform era divided the Han migration to Xinjiang into two distinct phases, starting with allowing Han cadres to return to Inner China (**Lüthi,2013,p.167**). As a result of lax policies during the Deng era, ten thousand cadres in Xinjiang, the overwhelming majority of whom were Han

⁴⁶The administrative capital of Xinjiang, its name means "beautiful pasture" in the Mongolian language. Ürümqi was an important commercial center during the Tang Dynasty, situated along the Silk Roads, and today it stands out as one of Xinjiang's more prosperous and developed regions, with a majority of its population being of Han descent (**Cappelletti,2020,p.20**).

individuals, were able to return to their homes (**Millward,2007,p.342**) after they had been denied their right to attend the funerals of their family members during the Maoist period. In fact, immigration policy during the reform period was characterized by flexibility (**Lüthi,2013,p.170**) and was facilitated, to a higher degree, by the extension of railway lines and the construction of many new roads in the region that linked villages and cities to each other (**Smith,2002,p.6**). This contributed to the decline in the Han numbers of the aggregate population of Xinjiang, coinciding with the onset of the one-child policy and the implementation of family planning policies (**Finley,2013,p.25**). In addition to reducing migration numbers and transforming Eastern cities into major industrial and commercial hubs, the pinnacle of Deng's political career was the "Four Modernizations": agriculture, industry, science and technology, and defense, once he assumed power in 1978 (**Fairbank&Merle,1992,p.343**). At that time, a sizable portion of Han farmers in Xinjiang had no choice but to turn into "floating residents" and abandon agriculture and move to the prosperous cities of the East (**Hann,2014,p.188**), as well as a fair number of Uyghur farmers as well. Migration patterns throughout China have reversed, moving from the countryside to the cities, unlike the 1960s, and from the west and center to

the east, regardless of the already vast population density in the east. Despite this, Xinjiang ranked fourth among Chinese regions in terms of net immigration influx volume between 1985 and 1995 **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.122)**.

Another aspect included in the list of differences between the two migrations is the conspicuous disparities between the first Han settlers and the 1980s Han economic migrants themselves. Many of the early Han settlers, their descendants, and the majority of Uyghur people demonstrate vocal opposition to the unlimited influx of new economic Han immigrants **(Sautman,1997,p.33-34)** who are participating in infrastructure construction projects financed by the public and private sectors **(Byler,2018,p.204)**. Besides these construction initiatives, the market liberalization and aggravated resource extraction in the 1980s alarmed both Uyghurs and early Han settlers who regarded themselves as part of the local community **(Finley,2013,p.75)**. This modern economic liberalism demolished an anchored edifice of the identity of the early Han settlers in Xinjiang and disrupted their traditional ways of living. After they were excluded from the new available job opportunities that required skills they had never mastered,

the past that was filled with tragedies and poverty became shrouded in nostalgia, and they yearned for the equality within the previous communist system **(Byler,2018,p.203-204)**. As the Han presence expanded in Xinjiang, many became apathetic toward the local culture that should be observed and held in high regard; the new economic immigrants became too big for their boots and no longer felt any need to adapt to local traditions, as previous generations of Han immigrants had done **(Finley,2013,p.408)**. Ironically, early Han settlers were also viewed as much as the Uyghurs as backward peoples who lacked cultural value **(Byler,2018,p.204)**. With complete certainty, the migration of the Han nationality to Xinjiang influenced this region to become what it is during the 21st century, a land divided against itself between the south, dominated by indigenous culture, which struggles to preserve traditions, and the north, rich in demographic diversity, which is gradually moving towards modernity, industrialization, and development. In a nutshell, the Han migration to Xinjiang primarily helped develop the Uyghur identity into what it is today, so the characteristics of narrow oases were abandoned in order to form a complete Uyghur identity, forged by the fear of the Han and by the need to differ from them. It also created and developed the “we-vs.-them” balance between the Uyghur and the Han.

Image #1

In the picture, a young man is squatting and looking into the camera while baking bricks from clay in Xinjiang in the early 1900s.

<https://journals.openedition.org/eps/3772?lang=en>

Conclusion of Chapter 1

The majority of the Uyghur people, a mixture of Indo-European, Mongolian, and Turkic peoples, live in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region in northwest China, making up more than half of its population. Contrary to the official Chinese narrative, they see themselves as the heirs of the former Uyghur kingdoms, but the current Uyghur designation was revived and used beginning in the 1920s. Despite the acculturation process imposed on them by the state, a significant portion of the Uyghurs are still not integrated into Chinese society and exhibit their “Uyghurness” publicly.

The Xinjiang region retains sentimental value for the Uyghurs, as it has been a link to the illustrious Silk Roads and a historical homeland for them since their migration from Mongolia during the fall of the Uyghur Khaganate during the mid-9th century. In China’s perspective, Xinjiang remains a valuable geopolitical center and an oil and natural gas reservoir that feeds the considerable demand found in the cities of eastern China, and thus it is illogical to abandon it to any other party. “Unifying” the Xinjiang region with China in the mid-20th century, and

then directly implementing Han immigration programs to annex it culturally after it had been annexed politically, converted that region into a melting pot of two distinct cultures between the Uyghur and Han people.

Map #3
Xinjiang internal borders within China, and external borders with Central Asian countries.

<https://journals.openedition.org/eps/3772?lang=en>

Map #4
The areas shaded in black are managed by the Xinjiang Production and Construction Corporation.

<https://journals.openedition.org/eps/3772?lang=en>

Map #5

A map showing the distribution of ethnic groups in Xinjiang in 2010. The Uyghurs live in the southwest, while the Han are most numerous in the north.

<https://www.farwestchina.com/travel/xinjiang-maps/>

Image #2

Although he stepped down from his official post after the Tiananmen Square events, Deng Xiaoping remained the Chinese leader until his death in 1997.

https://news.cgtn.com/news/3451444e79677a6333566d54/share_p.html

Image #3

"Tank Man" - the iconic image from the Tiananmen Square events that took place in the PRC in 1989.

<https://www.ida2at.com/what-happened-in-tiananmen-square/>

Chapter 2

Political Reforms in Xinjiang During the Era of Deng Xiaoping

(1978-1989)

I. China's Opening-up Policies

1. Political Opening-up in China: its Path, Leaders, and Impact on Ethnic Minorities

2. The Chinese Opening-up in Xinjiang and Uyghurs' Interaction with it

3. Tiananmen Square Events and the Abandonment of the Opening-up Policies

II. The Political Relationship between the Uyghurs and China

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conclusion

Chapter 2: Political Reforms in Xinjiang

During the Era of Deng Xiaoping (1978-1989)

I. China's Opening-up Policies

1. Political Opening-up in China: its Path, Leaders, and Impact on Ethnic Minorities

Once World War II concluded, Western countries⁴⁷ conducted themselves in a different approach than those taken by the Eastern Bloc countries in many of the policies, practices, activities, ideals, and ideas that distinguished the two blocs from each other during the mid-20th century. Western countries marketed their democracy to the world as a democracy worthy of the Greco-Roman heritage⁴⁸. On top of that, the Western World labeled itself with several titles, including “the free world” and “the civilized

⁴⁷"First World countries" is a term given to Western countries in Central and Western Europe, the United States, and NATO countries during the Cold War.

⁴⁸The "founding fathers" of the United States aspired to build America in the 18th century that would be a worthy heir to the Roman Republic, emulating its political ideals and moral values. Western civilization also considers Greco-Roman civilization as its cornerstone and the origin of democracy in the world, also known as the ancient classical world, which is the historical period that extended from the eighth century BC until the fifth century AD.

world.” Rather, it promoted the idea that its nations were a beacon for those seeking freedom and a refuge for those fleeing poverty, ignorance, backwardness, religious persecution, and political oppression that run rampant on the opposite side of the globe, the countries of the Eastern Bloc and those of the Third World⁴⁹. The policies of Western countries emphasized the importance of political and economic openness, as well as fostering tolerance and religious, ethnic, and cultural pluralism⁵⁰, in an attempt to distinguish themselves from their antithesis⁵¹ existing in the authoritarian countries of the Eastern Bloc, where people were suffering from restrictions and persecution while being hungry for a decent life that mirrors the one that the Western media was publishing about its countries. In China, especially during the 1980s, Western propaganda was able to appeal to the curiosity of the Chinese people (**Cappelletti,2020,p.2**), who had suffered devastation from the ill-considered totalitarian policies during the Great Leap Forward and the resulting Great Famine. Adding insult to injury,

⁴⁹Non-aligned countries that were neither part of the capitalist West nor the communist Eastern Bloc, but many of them were developing countries, most of them located in Africa, Asia, and Latin America (**Britannica,2023**).

⁵⁰Personally, I see pluralism as an overrated ideal that didn't live up to the expectations. Once the globalization system emerged during the 1980s, many individuals failed to normalize connecting with people from different nationalities and religions, and they crawled back to the comfort zone of their own nationalities and religions, and the current identity struggle in Europe is a suitable illustration of this.

⁵¹In his crowning achievement, “1984,” the English thinker and writer George Orwell summarizes popular revolutions as follows: “The masses never revolt of their own accord, and they never revolt simply because they are oppressed. In fact, as long as they are not allowed standards of comparison, they never realize they are persecuted.” (**Orwell,1949,p.207**).

the Chinese were beaten to a pulp by the later widespread oppression during the Cultural Revolution, which only ended with the death of Mao Zedong, the architect of those oppressive and arbitrary policies that ultimately proved to be economically ineffective and socially disruptive. With the death of Mao, the restrictions imposed on public debate in China began to be gradually lifted, and the official media started dressing contemporary politics in clothes of the glorious Chinese past⁵². And by utilizing historical analogy as a form of political persecution, Jiang Qing⁵³, Mao's widow, has been labeled a usurper and has been likened to Empress Lu⁵⁴ of the Han Dynasty **(Thwaites,2001,p.136)**. And in a similar way to Khrushchev's method of de-Stalinization in the Soviet Union, the deregulation was coupled with a general skepticism, or even an undermining, of Maoist policies, which led to a re-evaluation of the party's record on the issue of nationalities and ethnic minorities **(Clarke,2011,p.72)**. The ravages of the Cultural Revolution were

⁵²Revisiting ancient Chinese culture would not have happened during the era of Mao Zedong, especially during the period of the Cultural Revolution when he was able to project his dictatorial authority and purge his opponents, because his policies were based on demolishing the monuments of Chinese civilization and its historical legacy and replacing them with the “Socialist Utopia” that was promised to the world.

⁵³Chinese political figure (1914-1991), she is the third wife of Mao Zedong and one of the most influential women in China during the Cultural Revolution **(Britannica,n.d)**. In 1976, she and 3 of her zealots were arrested and tried in 1981 in what was known as the “Gang of Four” trial **(Thwaites,2001,p.179)**.

⁵⁴Known as Gaohou (241 BC-180 BC), the first woman to rule China historically, she seized power for 15 years (195 BC-180 BC) after the death of her husband, Gaozu, the first Chinese emperor of the Han dynasty. She played the role of regent during her son's reign, seizing actual power and strengthening her position by promoting her relatives to key positions **(Britannica,n.d)**.

enough to elevate the level of dissatisfaction and indignation among the minorities, who felt during that revolution that was led by the mob and the gullible, that it was an attack on their national identity
(Bovingdon,2004,p.20-21).

In an attempt to refute Western propaganda and emphasize the diversity of the Chinese civilization, the Chinese leadership that assumed power after the death of Mao followed a policy of ethnic pluralism, which represented a blessing and a curse for minorities in China at the same time. Although it eliminated any possibility of actual ethnic genocide of minorities, it falsely depicted the Chinese state as a benevolent and just state in regards to the minorities within it in order to conceal the systematic racism that continued to be practiced **(Byler,2018,p.46)**. During the 3rd Plenary Session of the 11th Central Committee of the Communist Party in December 1978, Deng Xiaoping catapulted himself into the helm of the Communist Party⁵⁵, assuming a path that aimed to right the previous wrongs by characterizing a radical shift from the party's minority policies in China

⁵⁵By carefully mobilizing his supporters within the party, Deng was able to outmaneuver Mao's successor, Hua Guofeng, and then oust him from leadership positions without causing him physical harm, paving the way for a precedent in the post-Mao Communist Party that aimed for less harm and humiliation to political opponents. Deng became Chairman of the Central Military Commission until November 1989 but remained China's leader practically until his death in February 1997 **(Fairbank&Merle,1992,p.406)**.

(Clarke,2007,p.42). Deng was born in 1904 in Sichuan Province during the Qing Dynasty and died in 1997. He studied and worked in France during the 1920s, where he learned the importance of modernity and the open economy (Vogel,2012). He became a follower of Marxism-Leninism and joined the Chinese Communist Party ranks in 1924. Curiously, his allegiance to the Communist Party was not because he belonged to a poor or destitute family, as his father was a wealthy landowner, and at that time owning land was a natural matter, unlike the period when the Communist Party took over (Yang,2016,p.11). Once, his father asked him why he wanted to learn in France, and Deng replied that he must learn knowledge and truth in order to save China (Stewart,2001,p.23). The weakness and humiliation that China was subjected to during the century of humiliation was imprinted on the consciousness of that young generation impatient to restore the glories of China, and according to Deng, this was possible through Western science by far. Prior to the 3rd plenary session, Deng became myopic on his objective of seizing the appropriate political moment for chartering the “corrective movement” inside the party and for marketing for the “Four Modernizations” that would produce a “Thermidor” after the horrors of Mao's arbitrary policies (Clarke,2007,p.42). In distinguishing himself from

the authoritarian Maoist administration, Deng inaugurated his reign with the following speech: “Free the mind, unite, and look to the future.”

(Thwaites,2001,p.136). Trying to lead China out of the wilderness of the previous decades, Deng started with a bang when he acknowledged past faults and mistakes, especially the transgressions of the Cultural Revolution, believing that resolving the remaining issues from the past and rectifying a number of unjust matters is necessary to liberate thought and achieve stability and unity **(Vidal,2016,p.4)**. Evaluating Deng’s administration, Ian Johnson wrote in the NY Review of Books: “The reform-era activities that began in 1978 eventually transformed China into one of the world's largest economies and a leviathan of a trading partner, as well as an emerging regional military power.” Nonetheless, political reform, coined as the “Fifth Modernization,” advanced at a significantly lethargic and unsatisfactory speed to the new generation eager for freedom and openness, unlike the rapid economic growth **(FactsandDetails,2021)**. Rather than combating capitalism or the free market like his predecessors, Deng championed economic openness during the Four Modernizations period, quoting the old proverb, “No matter if it is a white cat or a black cat; as long as it can catch mice, it is a good cat.” In Deng’s perspective, the success of the global

capitalist system sufficed, and at this stage China implicitly borrowed the open market policy that had proven fruitful. For starters, Deng considered that economic reform would not succeed without political reform.

(Lim,2014,p.162). Although not an economist by profession, Deng is often hailed as the “architect of economic reforms.” He realized that he could not put the pressing popular trend toward economic de-collectivization on the back burner, so he exploited this economic growth to flex the party’s muscles **(Dikötter,2015)**. When Deng emphasized certain regions to achieve wealth ahead of others, The Central Command⁵⁶ showcased that the emerging ideas in Chinese society can be integrated into socialism **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.10)**. With the introduction of new labels, such as “market economy” and “economic de-collectivization,” classical socialism as we know it was completely blown out of water and replaced with a unique socialism that believes in economic reform, prosperity, productivity, and high economic efficiency **(Moneyhon,2003,p.491)**.

⁵⁶Learning from their previous experience with Mao during the Cultural Revolution, the Communist leadership appointed Chen Yun as an associate to Deng, an economist who would share his decisions and limit his absolute power. Thus, the leadership ensured that Deng would not turn into a one-man dictator like his predecessor **(Vogel,2012)**.

Although Deng Xiaoping was the main driver of the reform movement in China, other figures shared his vision for a reformed China. Take Hu Yaobang⁵⁷ as an example, a General Secretary of the CCP and a reformist leader whose death in April 1989 prompted huge crowds demanding freedom and democracy to arrive at Tiananmen Square to pay their respects, but the mourners quickly turned into demonstrators and occupied the square. During his visit to Tibet⁵⁸ in May 1980, where he was shocked by the extreme levels of poverty he saw in minority areas, Hu proposed a six-point program to address the situation of minorities in China. Among the reform policies that Hu proposed were: activating actual self-governance - developing economic policies that would suit local needs - investing in agriculture - stimulating animal husbandry activities - reviving cultural, educational and scientific projects - initiating programs of Han officials' transfer from minority areas back to their homelands (Dillon,1997,p.81). Although the CCP has been doggedly adamant in its

⁵⁷Chinese revolutionary leader (1915-1989) who served as General Secretary of the Communist Party of China during the reform period in the 1980s. He was born into a poor family and joined the Communist Party ranks early. During the Cultural Revolution, he was purged alongside Deng, with whom he worked collaboratively during the reform period, becoming director of the party's organization department in 1977 and a member of the Politburo, responsible for the party's propaganda (Britannica,2023).

⁵⁸An autonomous region of China consisting of the Tibetan Plateau, it is considered the second largest province in China after Xinjiang, covering more than one million two hundred thousand square kilometers. Tibet is the highest region on Earth, so it is called the "Roof of the World," and it shares with Nepal the largest mountain peak in the world, Mount Everest (Misachi,2021).

efforts to suppress ideas and activities that threaten its political dominion throughout all periods of its existence (**Castets,2015,p.231**), the new policies encouraged by Hu contributed to a reassessment of Chinese history and fostered an atmosphere that allowed the publication of many works that had previously been suppressed (**Thwaites,2001,p.136**). In Hu's view, this enhanced the opportunity to restore trust between minorities and the Chinese government, where all previous offenses would be "water under the bridge" (**Castets,2015,p.231**). These reform policies were put out to pasture after the conservative faction in the CCP and the liberal one, headed by Hu, were at loggerheads, especially during the student unrest⁵⁹ that followed in 1986. The conflict unfolded further in January 1987, when the conservative elements in the party purged Hu Yaobang and removed him from his post as General Secretary of the Party, denouncing him for the introduction of Japanese investment in the Chinese economy, but in reality, his "ideological laxity" was his political undoing. According to party hardliners, this laxity sparked bourgeois liberation in Chinese society in a manner similar to that found in democratic ones in the West, fueling the student unrest that most

⁵⁹Student demonstrations from September through December 1986 in several Chinese cities were predominantly an expression of student complaints about what they saw as negative aspects of the reform, such as high costs of living, profiteering, and corruption (**Clarke,2007,p.66**).

cities witnessed (Clarke,2007,p.67). Others blamed the “critical policies” aimed at the Cultural Revolution that had provided a suitable situation in which it became painless for minorities to display nationalistic and ethnic tendencies that conflicted with the inclusive Chinese national affiliation (Bovingdon,2004,p.43-44). Despite this, Deng considered that there was no ethnic discrimination in China, and if there was ethnic polarization, it was the result of foreign incitement or local separatist elements (Sautman,1997,p.3). Overall, the economic reforms, coupled with the promotion of Han nationalism that Deng marketed, enriched certain cities in the east at the expense of other regions, thus strengthening stark disparities between various ethnic Chinese components and reducing the possibility of any national integration⁶⁰ (Moneyhon,2003,p.518-519).

Image #4

A promotion during the Cultural Revolution featuring both Deng and Liu Shaoqi sketched as crushed capitalist rats.

<https://chineseposters.net/posters/e16-338/>

⁶⁰Due to various religious, historical, and political conditions, integration in China occurs unevenly, with the majority of ethnic minorities experiencing complete assimilation, as opposed to the Uyghurs and Tibetans.

2. The Chinese Opening-up in Xinjiang and Uyghurs'

Interaction with it

By excluding ethnic factors related to the Uyghur people, which the Chinese government took into consideration when making a decision, the period of reform in China as a whole did not differ from the period of reform in Xinjiang. Rather, Xinjiang constituted a microcosm of China that was experiencing a period of opening-up and reform in general during the 1980s. The path of reform policies regarding ethnic minorities was not unidirectional but rather had many fluctuations and zigzags, the result of a complex interaction between the pace of reform that the central government and local leadership deem appropriate and the impact of each policy intended to be implemented on each of the numerous regions of China. In a catch-22 situation facing the new Chinese government, persisting with the harsh policies of the past would likely have caused increased discontent and instability, whereas more lenient policies that foster cultural adaptation and religious freedom might also foment significant unrest at a similar level (Bovingdon,2004,p.21). For instance, it is possible that a certain policy may well suit an area inhabited heavily by Han individuals but at the same time

be inappropriate in another area inhabited by devout Muslims. Once Deng assumed power, the Uyghurs were provided an expanded margin to pen their history according to their point of view while reviving their traditions that were concealed during the previous decade. It should be noted that despite this level of laxity that Uyghurs were granted, their individuals remained far from political leadership positions **(Thum,2018,p.10)** because of the ruling class's fear of the nationalist tendencies harbored by most Uyghur cadres and individuals **(Byler,2018,p.46)**. W.J.F. Jenner, an English sinologist specializing in Chinese history and culture, noted that from the time Deng promoted liberalization in the late 1970s until the crackdown in the 1980s, political debates among leaders raged publicly, leading to periods of both amplified and reduced liberalization levels **(Thwaites,2001,p.206)**. In Hu Yaobang's view, Muslims in Xinjiang posed less of a threat to China than Tibetans because the Uyghurs were leaderless and lacked international support. Thus, Hu proposed enacting more autonomy and reforms in Xinjiang **(Zanardi,2019,p.2)**, which was adopted by the Party Committee in Xinjiang despite the objections of hardliners **(Bovingdon,2004,p.21)**. At the end of the day, the Chinese reform was reflected in both the economic, cultural-literary, and religious dimensions for the Uyghur people.

Concerning Xinjiang, the economy was considered the least significant sector among all those that were encouraged and developed during the period of opening-up. Indeed, it is possible to say that the idea of developing the economy in Xinjiang during the 1980s was officially ignored. Following de-collectivization, the reformist leaders were pondering which paths could be followed and which reforms should be implemented to stimulate the market and achieve rapid economic growth throughout China in order to uplift the biggest possible number of Chinese people out of poverty and establish a competitive economy on a global scale **(Cappelletti,2020,p.29)**. During his 1983 Xinjiang tour, Hu Yaobang pointed out that the people of Xinjiang must accept prioritizing development programs in eastern regions of China, and as for their region, it must wait for the next century until its turn comes and receives a substantial amount of state investment **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.11)**. Coupled by caravans full of Han people swarming Xinjiang to reap the investment benefits and seize job opportunities, some economic governmental projects were financed on a small scale, such as foreign joint ventures to exploit mineral and petroleum resources in Xinjiang, and thus tensions between the Han and the Uyghurs intensified **(Thwaites,2001,p.137-138)**. On the other hand, since the early

1980s, most Uyghur cadres and intellectuals have exhibited a willingness to cooperate with the state to benefit from such small-scale programs to develop Xinjiang and stimulate its economy **(Veg,2008,p.147)**. However, the Chinese government, which was fixated on a bigger nut to crack, the eastern cities, did not seize the historic opportunity to launch the policy of opening Xinjiang to the world until the second half of the 1980s **(Cappelletti,2020,p.49)**. Adding to the fact that the Chinese state missed the opportunity for the Uyghurs in Xinjiang to reap the benefits of Chinese economic opening-up, this missed chance generated a standard, which was the cities of eastern China, with which Uyghur could compare their economical situation and conclude that the government has abandoned the idea of upgrading their region, fueling separatist and nationalistic tendencies among its people even more.

In the 1980s, the Uyghurs enjoyed a certain level of liberty that allowed them to freely practice their religion and express their cultural and literary identities **(He,2014,p.187)**, contrary to the first half of the 1970s, during which Xinjiang witnessed the suppression of freedoms and the disappearance of manifestations of cultural expression. W.J.F. Jenner, an

English sinologist specializing in Chinese history and culture, considered that in the early 1980s, the central government permitted writers to deviate slightly in their writings from the four principles of Marxism-Leninism⁶¹, which were the focus of writings previously: Mao Zedong Thought - Dictatorship of the Proletariat - Socialism - Glorifying Party Leaders **(Thwaites,2001,p.206)**. Examples of the suppression of freedoms and the disappearance of manifestations of cultural expression in Xinjiang during contemporary history date back to the period of the “Anti-Rightist” campaign⁶², when Uyghur culture was restricted and thousands of intellectuals imprisoned. Subsequently, the government launched another campaign between 1961 and 1962, specifically directed against Uyghur intellectuals of dubious national loyalty who had been educated in the Soviet Union **(Veg,2008,p.146)**. Later, during the Cultural Revolution, hundreds of

⁶¹Marxist theorists downplayed the importance of the cultural, psychological, and linguistic factors behind nationalism, considering it a historical phenomenon that would ultimately go quietly into the night **(Hyer,2005,p.18)**. Their view of the social sciences, including cultural studies, history, linguistics, and political sciences, was that they were marginal sciences and that Marxism as an ideology possessed a thorough understanding of the social world **(Greenhalgh,2008,p.55)**. This matter may be discredited by the re-emergence of states on a national basis after the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the involvement of those states and regions, such as the Caucasus, the Balkans, Eastern Europe, and Central Asia, in devastating wars for the same religious, ethnic, and nationalist reasons. This nationalistic reemergence rendered Karl Marx’s conclusion that “socialism has solved the national question” an obsolete statement that could be taken with a grain of salt **(Hyer,2005,p.17)**.

⁶²Due to the excessive amount of vitriol during the “Hundred Roses” campaign, the Chinese leadership quickly retaliated in 1957 with the “Anti-Rightist” campaign. For a period of 6 months, the campaign’s tally totaled about a million people who were accused of being against the party and socialism **(Yang,2016,p.140)**; among them were many intellectuals who were subjected to humiliation and hard labor. Itching for a fight, Deng proved so ruthless and unyielding in purging alleged counterrevolutionaries that Mao felt obliged to write to him to explain that if he killed too many, the Party would lose public sympathy and China would develop a shortage of manpower **(Dikötter,2015)**.

thousands of ancient books and manuscripts that were found in Xinjiang offices and homes were destroyed, and the goal of all of this was to reformulate the historical narrative of the Uyghurs to fit that of China **(Dwyer,2005,p.21)**. As 1979 progressed, the Communist Party modified its policies to right the wrongs committed during the Cultural Revolution and rehabilitate the persecuted intellectuals. But after this brutal level of persecution, it was not easy for intellectuals and writers of ethnic minorities to realize the amount of freedom they enjoyed during the reform period, nor to move forward in demonstrating their unique cultural identity and expressing their political discontent publicly **(Thwaites,2001,p.136)**. A vital aspect in opening Xinjiang to the world during that period was granting foreign journalists permission to visit Xinjiang and learning more about the Uyghurs who expressed their chagrin to the world through their work **(Millward,2007,p.322-323)**. This unprecedented authorization was extended later to encompass foreign researchers, students, and writers, coming from Western and Asian universities and research centers, resulting in an expanded amount of Uyghur/Xinjiang studies that reflects on Uyghur historical and contemporary ways of living, culture, identity, and other elements of knowledge that began to speak volumes of the region and the

people inhabiting it. Lifting the government's media ban allowed foreign news to flow into Xinjiang (**Smith,2000,p.1**) which was previously isolated from the world after the turmoil that the region witnessed in the 1930s and the subsequent Communist takeover in the 1940s (**Thum,2018,p.14**). Once they assumed power, Communists nipped historical research of minorities in its bud; Uyghur historical works published before the establishment of the PRC done by intellectuals and researchers were confiscated, citing incompatibility with the new ideological boundaries of the state that aimed to control Xinjiang (**Tursun,2008,p.91**). Starting from the late 1970s, The Uyghur masses began slaking their thirst for more cultural products from around the world, including American popular music, Bollywood films from India, Turkish food, and reading religious texts from the Middle East and South Asia (**Thum,2018,p.12**). In addition, a number of Uyghur students were brought to Beijing to pursue their studies in law, humanities and social sciences, while in Xinjiang, research centers and cultural offices were reopened and rehabilitated, and even new ones were established (**Steenberg,2021,p.175**). Although the Uyghurs have contributed to an active and exceptional cultural production that has not been achieved in its vitality or magnitude since the establishment of the PRC during the reform

period (**Mukherjee,2010,p.423-424**), it must be noted that the scope of cultural work was limited and restricted to specific aspects. Writers were not allowed to promote certain genres that might contribute to the spread of separatist ideas or those that display cracks in the facade of a “Unified China”. Rather, they were confined to works that would present the Uyghurs as an Islamic fundamentalist group, or a “backward specimen” that lacked the guidance of the Chinese state that would “usher them out of the wilderness” and enhance their economic and social situation (**Thwaites,2001,p.136,138**). Another thing is the imbalance in numbers between the Han and Uyghur intellectuals during the reform era that was dubbed the cultural golden age for the Uyghurs. A more significant presence of Han intellectuals in Xinjiang has intensified Chinese propaganda, which has consistently asserted that the Uyghurs receive support from the government and Han individuals to progress in their development and modernization efforts. In 1983, during a meeting of the Xinjiang Academy of Social Sciences on the topic of “Promoting Uyghur Classical Literature,” which basically should concern Uyghur writers more than non-Uyghur ones, the number of Han intellectuals and scholars reached 149, while the number

of non-Han representatives, that is, Uyghurs and other minorities in Xinjiang, totaled only 11 members (**Thwaites,2001,p.208**).

Many of the imposed governmental reform programs were aimed at uprooting any separatist or nationalist inclination among Chinese minorities that could oppose the official grand narrative, which emphasizes that all those peoples in China are Chinese in their identity and that China is their ultimate and everlasting homeland. Along these lines, the government followed a “carrot and stick” approach in its dealings with ethnic minorities (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.849**) in order to ensure that they follow the broad governmental line set by China, and achieving this can involve acknowledging the cultural traditions of ethnic minorities that the 1980s' modernist perspective classified in a social context, thereby isolating them from political and economic spheres (**Steenberg,2021,p.176**). The reforms carried out by Deng Xiaoping heralded an era of religious prosperity and watered down the state's hostility towards religions (**Erie,2015,p.93**), ushering in a lax period that permitted the practice of religious rites and rituals, contrary to Maoist times. Albeit this, Uyghurs lived through religious laxity, but without taking their eyes off the ever-swinging pendulum of the

Chinese policy that swung between restriction and leniency **(Mukherjee,2010,p.427)**. The policy of religious openness resulted in the proliferation of mosques in the region; some of them were rebuilt while others were constructed, and even prayers and other Islamic traditions practiced in mosques were also restored **(HRW,2005,p.11)**. Remarkably, the numbers of mosques in Xinjiang during the reform era exceeded their number before the establishment of the PRC in 1949 **(Gladney,2003,p.461)**. Religious openness in Xinjiang was unconfined to the spread of mosques; Muslims were also allowed to perform Hajj in Mecca and trade with their fellow Muslims in Muslim countries **(Gladney,2003,p.461)**. Rather, this laxity extended to include party cadres, among whom Han members were authorized to leave Xinjiang **(HRW,2005,p.11)**, and for Uyghur individuals to freely practice their religious rituals **(Castets,2015,p.231)**.

3. Tiananmen Square Events and the Abandonment of the Opening-up Policies

Through the lens of hindsight bias in analyzing the history of the PRC, it becomes clear that the fleeting time when the mainly totalitarian

Chinese regime relaxed its stance on ethnic and religious minorities was likely just a time of experimentation. During this defined period, the state gradually imposed policies distinct from those previously dictated in order to achieve similar results, so the policies could be considered as methods that differ from previous ones that may be unsuitable for the modern period that coincided with the new leadership emerging in China. Two aspects defined the state's policies during the reform era: the state's ultimate goal and the time frame in which the reform era exists. In the first, governments typically seek to maintain stability in order to achieve political and economic prosperity. The objective remained the same, but during the reform period, lenient policies, rather than restrictive and intolerant ones, were experimented with in order to attain the final goal of stability. As for the second aspect, the 1980s witnessed major global transformations, especially in the—geographically and ideologically close to China—Soviet Union, where the official measures⁶³ to uplift it from the muck and mire of the 1970s chaotic policies were at their peak. It was crystal clear: opening up the economy was inevitable, and China utilized it to surf the wave of global openness that focused on the market economy and investment in the

⁶³The crowning achievement of Mikhail Gorbachev's reign in the Soviet Union was Glasnost, which means transparency in political action.

technology sector in order to maintain continuity and preserve internal stability.

When the powder keg ignited in the Tiananmen Square in 1989, it proved that the discontent simmering for some time was fueled by all the humiliation, restriction, and persecution that the Chinese were subjected to during the previous decades. The 1979 fringe “Democracy Wall⁶⁴” movement presaged the Tiananmen Square events. That movement kicked off at the end of the Cultural Revolution; at that time, the literary output known as the “Scar Literature” soared, embracing all literary expressions that indicated the reality of sorrow, fear, torment, anger, and sadness that the Chinese people as a whole experienced during the Cultural Revolution. All these repressed emotions had been present within many intellectuals and students, especially those who had been exiled far from their cities to remote villages (Thwaites,2001,p.136), anxiously biding their time for the spark to ignite and crystallize into a political movement. David indeed does slingshot the Goliath right in the face; the “world spirit” led armless citizens to

⁶⁴A brief period of political liberalization that lasted some time after the death of Mao Zedong, which was called the "Democracy Wall Movement," the first substantive social movement of the post-Mao era (Levine,2013,p.8). In late 1978, "to liberate thought, to provide the best service to the people are the duties of CCP members" were written on a wall in Beijing by civilians. Since then, people have been allowed to scribble their opinions on street walls across the country, a space for expression after several decades of political repression.

dismember the lethargic Eastern Bloc at the final period of the Cold War⁶⁵, and the Tiananmen Square upheaval in 1989 in China was one among many worldwide. Following Hu Yaobang's death in April 1989, thousands of Chinese individuals eager for freedom and democracy, university students in particular, flocked to Tiananmen Square in Beijing to pay their respects, but they instantly started protesting corruption and the overprivileged party officials **(Naughton,2007,p.98)**. The government's first response backfired; at the request of the party's conservative faction, the People's Daily, the state newspaper, issued an editorial pledging a tough stance against the unrest, which it described as part of a conspiracy aimed at overthrowing the party leadership and the regime **(Lim,2014,p.94)**. Rubbing salt in the wound, the demonstrators were far enraged, and their movement gained momentum after the editorial was issued. As for the government's reaction, it was violent, and the brutal repression caused many international observers to reduce expectations for China's future **(Naughton,2007,p.11)**. The Chinese government had no choice but to mobilize approximately 200,000 soldiers to enter Tiananmen Square and flush out protestors by force and put an end to

⁶⁵The Cold War (1945–1990) kicked off after the end of World War II between the two rival global blocs and continued for most of the second part of the twentieth century. The English writer George Orwell coined this term in 1945 to refer to what he predicted would be a nuclear confrontation between “two or three great powers” **(Britannica,2023)**.

this pandemonium. In fact, the Chinese army, with its armored cars, demolished the statue of the Goddess of Democracy, similar to The Statue of Liberty in the United States, an emblem for the students' movement **(Lim,2014,p.19)**. Ergo, the movement's failure was inevitable, and any hope of political reform or political tolerance was uprooted from the minds of the Chinese people after the revolution fizzled out. The Tiananmen Square events set Deng's policies at stake; party hardliners, who were itching for a fight, viewed such permissive policies as "fiddling while Rome burns"⁶⁶. With the situation spiraling out of control, Deng acknowledged his vulnerable position and decided to submit to the wishes of party conservatives who wanted a comprehensive crushing of the demonstrators in defiance of his non-violent ideology on how to address public discontent. Licking his wounds, Deng handed over power to Jiang Zemin⁶⁷ in November 1989, resigning from all official positions in the communist leadership **(Britannica,2023)**. Following the dismemberment of the Soviet Union, the behemoth of the communist bloc, while China gradually kept maintaining stability during the 1990s, the following phrase circulated: "The belief in

⁶⁶An overused historical fallacy against the Roman Emperor Nero (37 AD–68 AD) is that he played the harp while watching the great fire that broke out in the capital of the empire, Rome, in the year 64 AD.

⁶⁷A Chinese politician (1926-2022) who was born in Jiangsu Province and joined the Communist Party in 1946. He served as Secretary-General of the Communist Party from Deng's resignation in 1989 until 2002, and he also served as President from 1993 until 2003 **(Britannica,2023)**.

China was that communism was what would protect China, but now it has become only China would protect communism." **(Smith,2000,p.11)**.

As for Xinjiang, it is no surprise that renewed calls for Xinjiang's independence from China and peaceful demonstrations against ethnic discrimination and economic inequality coincided with the pro-democracy movement in Tiananmen Square **(Smith,2000,p.3)**. In their own political strife, Uyghurs amplified the levels of their distinction from the rest of the Chinese peoples, where local grievances they addressed differed from other groups. For example, family planning policies⁶⁸ and Han migration to Xinjiang were the two most important matters that the Uyghurs demonstrated against during the reform period **(Millward,2007,p.281)**. The comprehensive and overwhelming repression that ended the Tiananmen Square movement had previously been evolving in Xinjiang at several junctions, even within the period of opening up and reform. To begin with, the Chinese People's Liberation Army⁶⁹ (PLA) subdued demonstrations

⁶⁸Due to the family planning law that forced Uyghurs to have a maximum of two children in urban areas, 1985 riots in Ürümqi and demonstrations by Uyghur residents in Beijing and Shanghai broke out in what they believed was social injustice, demanding that the birth control policy be applied solely to the Han in Xinjiang and not to the undersized minority **(Finley,2013,p.142)**.

⁶⁹The unified organization of the Chinese land, sea, and air forces, which is one of the largest military forces in the world. The roots of the People's Liberation Army go back to the 1927 uprising carried out by the Communists against the Nationalists. It was initially called the Red Army, then it developed during the reign of Mao Zedong to become a regular army, especially after World War II **(Britannica,2023)**.

against discrimination in the cities of Aksu and Kashgar in 1980, resulting in substantial numbers of casualties (**Dillon,1997,p.82**). Quelling popular demonstrations in a strategic region on the border, such as Xinjiang, was necessary for communist theorists during the Deng era in order to integrate it into China, in a manner different from Mao's approach, which in return strengthened the isolation of Xinjiang from China (**Clarke,2007,p.40**). Such disturbances and demonstrations in Xinjiang worried the communist leadership, which was hoping to maintain stability and preserve the status quo in Xinjiang. Deng had no choice but to make an inspection tour of Xinjiang in August 1981, and after that tour, it was decided to appoint a more ruthless and decisive regional leader with the aim of advancing the reform agenda in parallel with keeping the region on a short leash. Therefore, in October 1981, Wang Enmao⁷⁰ became the First Secretary of the Xinjiang Provincial Party Committee (**Clarke,2007,p.55**). After the end of his term in Xinjiang in 1985, and in an attempt to pursue the governmental ethnic hegemony imposed on the Uyghurs in order to strip them of their Turkish roots, Wang Enmao declared: "The Uyghurs are not branched from

⁷⁰Chinese civil administrator and military officer (1913-2001). He was born in Jiangxi Province and joined the PLA, becoming a lieutenant general. He was twice appointed Secretary of the CCP Committee in Xinjiang, his first term between 1952-1967 and the second one between 1981-1985. Drawing a line in the sand, Wang made it clear to the Uyghur public on which religious and cultural activities were legal and which weren't (**Clarke,2007,p.57**). In addition, Wang declared his rejection of both Uyghur and Han chauvinism simultaneously (**Millward,2007,p.277**).

the Turkish tree of nations, but rather the Chinese one.”

(Kamalov,2021,p.9). A staunch believer of China’s legitimacy to extend its control over Xinjiang, Wang went above and beyond in promoting the regime’s propaganda in order to achieve stability in the region. But reality had other views, where between the years 1985 and 1989, student demonstrations in Xinjiang intensified, jolting the Uyghurs from the euphoria that stemmed from the cultural revival that the government targeted in Xinjiang between 1978 and 1982 **(Steenberg,2021,p.176)**. Like manna from heaven, the Tiananmen Square protests made Xinjiang’s independence a plausible outcome for some Uyghurs, especially after the participation of some of them in the uprising in Beijing; *Örkäsh Dölät*⁷¹, for example, was even an activist on the front lines **(Smith,2000,p.11)**. In a nutshell, the government found that cultural adaptation as a whole was fruitless and contributed to spreading chaos and unrest across China **(Finley,2013,p.422)**. The shift from cultural accommodation to overt forced assimilation took place in the mid-1980s, but it merely led to the strengthening of Uyghur separatist movements and nationalist fervor **(Dwyer,2005,p.x)**, causing the

⁷¹Uyghur student (1968-) and one of the most prominent leaders of the Tiananmen Square protests. He met with Li Peng, the Chinese head of state, during the talks on May 18, 1989, that preceded the entry of the PLA into the square, where he became notable by reprimanding the head of state live on state television, considering that he does not care about the demands of the students **(BBCNews,2019)**.

Chinese government to appear to be stuck between the hammer of forced assimilation and the anvil of adaptation, which both resulted in the same outcome. By the end of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s, and after the conservative elite once again took control of the party, it became clear to them that the scope of religious freedom that had been allowed had encouraged the Uyghurs to form Islamic and nationalist opposition networks **(Castets,2015,p.235)**. Following the Baren incident⁷², the government took advantage of the situation to uncover these networks, especially after it became known that the separatists had explicitly asserted that Islam would prevail over Marxism-Leninism⁷³. This alarming information led the government to abandon its lenient approach in Xinjiang, resulting in the imprisonment of protesters without any formal charges **(Bovingdon,2004,p.31-33)**. Regarding the rise of separatist sentiment during the reform period, in 1995, a publication from Hong Kong⁷⁴ expressed the

⁷²Armed skirmishes between the Uyghurs and the government in the town of Baren in southern Xinjiang in April 1990 that ended after the government brutally quelled them. During the incident, religious slogans held by the belligerents frightened Han officials from a broader Islamic network that ran deep in the region. Using a pejorative tone, a government official in Beijing commented on the incident as follows: “Ethnic minorities are like galloping horses. No matter how good the food you give them is, they may run away at any time.” **(Finley,2013,p.89)**.

⁷³A philosophical/political doctrine that was the product of Karl Marx providing the general framework and Vladimir Lenin, the first leader of the Soviet Union, adding the means, i.e., the party or the totalitarian state. The totalitarian state must protect the revolution of the proletariat, Lenin thought, unlike Marx, who wanted the communist revolution to abolish the state and its concept and form a stateless and classless communist society.

⁷⁴Hong Kong is a city in East Asia located on the southern coast of China. It is a special autonomous region belonging to China after it was ceded by Britain in 1997. Its population is more than 7 million, living in an area of about a thousand square kilometers, and therefore it is one of the most densely populated cities. Despite this, it is considered one of the most developed regions in the world **(WorldAtlas,2021)**.

following views: “Some local figures in China believe that the system of restrictions and firm control, especially over religious practices, that was imposed during the Mao era provided the only approach by which China was able to impose order and crush any hope of separatism. With the abandonment of these measures, it has become normal to witness activities calling for secession in public without the instigators fearing any punishment.” **(Smith,2000,p.21)**.

Through his research, which focused on the reform era in Xinjiang: “Xinjiang in the "Reform" Era, 1978-91: The Political and Economic Dynamics of Dengist Integration,” Michael Clarke, Associate Professor at Australian National University who specializes in the history and politics of Xinjiang, says that for a period of time and in fluctuating trends, the policies of opening-up and reform demonstrated many dynamics that challenged China’s dominance in Xinjiang **(Clarke,2011,p.72)**. Especially in the period from 1978 to 1982, the Uyghurs, other Xinjiang minorities, and Han settlers interacted with the dynamics issued by Beijing in a way that facilitated unrest and fomented chaos in Xinjiang **(Clarke,2007,p.85)**. Even the 1997

Ghulja incident⁷⁵ represented an additional episode in a series of incidents that had been building up since the launch of the 1978 opening-up policies that aimed to break China's international isolation, which had magnified during the Cultural Revolution (**Dillon,1997,p.80**). In that sense, the market liberalization and the state's shift from socialist development to capitalist accumulation during the reform period had curbed the course of old-fashioned multiculturalism and accelerated the removal of local lifestyle features in Xinjiang (**Byler,2018,p.36**). Uyghurs were encouraged to search for alternative templates that have nothing to do with the PRC in order to highlight their identity and display their culture, such as Turkic nationalism or the Islamic *ummah*, which may be closer to them and able to embrace that identity and culture more than the PRC and the Han society. Likewise, extremism building up on both poles of the conflict in Xinjiang, the Uyghurs and the Han, has generated extremism and spurred fanaticism on the other side as well. Indeed, it is understandable that any person, even if his ideas are moderate initially, could gradually turn into an extremist if he or she viewed extremism, hostility, lack of acceptance, and discrimination

⁷⁵Unrest, riots, and ethnic violence in February 1997 in the city of Gulja in northern Xinjiang, during which a number of Han civilians were attacked and killed in the streets after security forces opened fire on a peaceful Uyghur demonstration (**Finley,2013,p.89**).

emanating from the opposing side. In a weird turn of events, separatism ran wild among Uyghurs during the reform period, which was primarily aimed at integrating the Uyghurs into the state, resulting in a surge of xenophobia among the Han, who started blaming the reform era policies for the uptick in Uyghur separatism. According to a Chinese official in Xinjiang, “If you give them, the Uyghurs, autonomy, they will create East Turkestan. It is like severing the entire Xinjiang region from China and handing it over to Turkey or the Soviet Union.” **(Dillon,1997,p.81)**. Coinciding with a global nationalistic surge at the end of the Cold War and the disintegration of the Soviet Union, the reform era policies cemented the bond between the Han people inside and outside China, dialing up the Chinese/Han nationalism during that era, which in turn raised local nationalism among Chinese minorities too **(Aryodiguno,2021,p.74)**. Perhaps it is not surprising that the youth are more inclined to adopt separatism than the older generations since they sprouted in an era of relative religious freedom and were anchored back to traditions, while daily witnessing the competitive ethnic division with the “we-vs.-them” concept developed between Urban Uyghurs and Han over the last two decades of the twentieth century **(Smith,2000,p.21-22)**. It is unfair and unrealistic to consider the “we-vs.-them” concept was exclusively the

product of the opening-up policies, where it may have developed gradually whenever the two nationalities', Uyghur and Han, coexisted in the same time and place, provided that certain circumstances were present: When Han exercise dominance over the Uyghurs and cause them to feel politically oppressed, or when the Uyghurs fail in general to compete with the cultural, scientific, and social level of the Han or the rest of the existing groups in that specific region. But what we can conclude about the reform era policies in Xinjiang during the 1980s is that, even if they were not the primary driver of this concept of division, they certainly allowed, and may have also encouraged, the Uyghur people to participate in activities, take actions, and spread ideas that might support, enhance, and contribute to this vertical division in the ethnically and religiously diverse society that exists in Xinjiang. Therefore, Michael Clarke, Associate Professor at Australian National University who specializes in the history and politics of Xinjiang, considered that the state's attempts to take into account the concerns of ethnic minorities throughout the 1980s by allowing more freedom in the field of religious and cultural expression had, in the state's perception, backfired at the end of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s (Clarke,2007,p.83).

Image #5

A colorized photograph of girls in folk costumes taken during the arrival of the Swedish expedition to Xinjiang in the early 1900s.

<https://www.varldskulturmuseerna.se/forskning/forskningsblogg/2023/april/missionskyrkans-samling-en/#>

II. The Political Relationship between the Uyghurs and China

1. The Uyghur-China Relationship between Acceptance and Rejection

Nationalism in its current sense arose and developed in the late eighteenth century and early nineteenth century. But under the influence of

the mass revolutionary sentiment sparked by the French Revolution⁷⁶ and the subsequent Napoleonic Wars⁷⁷, which took it upon itself to spread the revolution and its ideas in Europe during the nineteenth century, nationalism was catapulted into a new world order in European societies. At that time, national consciousness among peoples turned into a reality among the chaos fomented by that revolution and the wars that followed, yet, in the times leading up to that, national or ethnic awareness was not prevalent on a large scale. During the diverse Chinese imperial era, different peoples were referred to according to their geographical origin or their appearance and remarkable characteristics, so that the concept of ethnic/national awareness in its current form was unheard of (**Cappelletti,2020,p.278-279**). Even Xinjiang was referred to as “the western region” by the Chinese during the era extending from the Han dynasty to the Qing dynasty, where the Chinese grip on that region fluctuated between strictness and leniency according to the strength or weakness of the authority of the dynasty ruling China at the time (**Aryodiguno,2021,p.68**). This variation lingered during the Chinese

⁷⁶From 1789 until Napoleon seized power in 1799, France witnessed a series of revolutionary movements that shook its societal core and beat the crumbling Ancien Regime to a pulp. It was undeniably the most important revolution the world had ever seen, with its far-reaching consequences and outlasting influence (**Britannica,2023**).

⁷⁷A series of wars (1801-1815) between Napoleonic France and other European powers that produced a brief French hegemony over most of Europe that ended with Napoleon's defeat at the Battle of Waterloo in 1815, his second handover of power, and his subsequent exile to the island of St. Helena (**Britannica,2023**).

Republic era, from 1911 until 1949, where the struggle between the Soviet Union and China weakened the latter's clench on Xinjiang **(Freeman,2020,p.318)**. Once CCP took over, at times it began imposing strict policies that fragmented ethnic identity, while at other times it pushed softer methods that allowed minorities to feel as if they possessed a dual identity **(Arya,2010,p.198)**. Moreover, Uyghur and Han historians' approaches had bifurcated into two different approaches when studying the history of the Uyghur people and their methods of interaction with the colonizers arriving from the Chinese east. Contradicting the state-supported model of Uyghur history pushed by most Han historians, many Uyghur historians have promoted that the Uyghur people developed uniquely and independently from their neighbors in China **(Tursun,2008,p.92)**.

As the world transitioned into a unipolar system post-Soviet Union, the nature of conflicts changed from East-West confrontations to rivalries among various nationalities within the nation-states they resided in. Unlike republics, which is the name the Soviet Union administered to its nationalities, China utilized the term "race" in order to exhibit that the affiliation of the Chinese races to the Chinese nation is inevitable

(Hyer,2005,p.18,19). The nation-state in China demonstrated its resilience in dealing with minorities in Xinjiang **(Beller-Hann,2012,p.219)**, and a part of that solidity was the belief of Muslims in Xinjiang in the values of equality and acceptance of autonomy for minorities that the early communist era called for **(Gladney,2003,p.461)**. Even Mao declared that Muslim minorities would immediately become part of the Chinese Federation of their own free will **(Finley,2013,p.70)**. And with the escalation of persecution during the Cultural Revolution and the Anti-Rightist campaign that preceded it, the relationship that brought together the Muslims of Xinjiang with the Chinese Republic faltered, and that faith turned into disappointment for many of them **(Gladney,2003,p.461)**. Also, minority cadres in the party got a taste of the state's persecution, as nearly one hundred thousand of them were subjected to political labels accusing them of promoting local nationalist sentiments and working against socialist values, discharging them from their official posts **(Bovingdon,2004,p.29)**.

Even during the reform period, and although the practices of persecution and harassment diminished within the policies of the new leadership, the crystallization of national consciousness among the Uyghurs

through policies of adaptation placed the Uyghurs and the Chinese government on a collision course (**Hann,2014,p.204**), christening Xinjiang “the political number one calamity” of China with regard to its internal situation (**Dwyer,2005,p.3**). The enlargement of national consciousness among the Uyghurs has rendered the process of their integration into Chinese society a complex matter, especially if we add to it two other factors: the demographic dissolution of the Uyghurs in their region and the economic exploitation of the region’s resources due to the caravans of Han settlers arriving there (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.349**). Marginalizing, and isolating, Uyghurs in the Chinese society produced an equation between the two, the Uyghurs and the Chinese government, which is formulated as follows: The government believes that the Uyghurs outside the integration process are a terrorist separatist threat to China that endangers it to lose the largest administrative unit among all its regions. As for the Uyghurs, they consider China a colonial power, and therefore its control of their region lacks legitimacy (**Thum,2018,p.1**). Aiming to exploit the region’s resources, the government employed the Uyghur social and economic elite (**Freeman,2020,p.318**) which inhibited the transformation of Uyghurs into a political group working to restore the interests and rights of the Uyghurs

(Bovingdon,2004,p.2), as well as linking the government and the overwhelming majority of the people who were the target of integration within the Han society through mixed marriages and the imposition of Han culture on them, that is, the acculturation program **(Cappelletti,2020,p.136)**. In the face of the acculturation project, the Uyghurs, on the other hand, exploited some cultural and religious differences to manage the patterns of their interaction with the Han by means that would preserve their own culture **(Smith,2002,p.3-4)**. For instance, The Chinese language which was learnt by a significant portion of the Uyghurs, constituted an adaptation method in a society rich in linguistic diversity in Xinjiang. Nonetheless, successfully adapting through means of language managed the relationship between the two groups exclusively in the period preceding the reform period, because during the mentioned era Han settlers who coveted economic opportunities spread in Xinjiang unconcerned with communicating with Uyghurs in any language **(Finley,2013,p.365)**. As a result, decision-makers acknowledged in the late 1980s that autonomy, which fit Chinese society in general, was unsuitable for the Uyghur people due to certain cultural and religious considerations **(Bovingdon,2004,p.13)**.

This was relative to the refusal and failure of integration between the Uyghurs and the Han, but space was also found in Xinjiang for acceptance and coexistence between the two groups, especially among one segment of the Uyghurs, which viewed the relationship between the Uyghurs and the Chinese government from a general strategic perspective and not through a colonizer-victim lens. Some of them argue that it was illogical and self-harming to seek secession from China at its peak when it had become a global power⁷⁸ (**Finley,2013,p.420**), while others defeatedly claim that the goal of self-determination has become hopeless after the termination of the reform period and that the Uyghurs must accept the idea of their people coming under the whip of the Chinese state (**Thwaites,2001,p.186-187**). Poverty and political oppression of the times that predated the reform era would lead observers to safely assume that the elderly group of Uyghurs, who were enjoying the bliss of religious freedom and social stability at that time, were closer to accepting Chinese hegemony than any other age demographic (**Smith,2000,p.17**). Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, mentions a phrase used by Uyghur people she met while inspecting Xinjiang: “Without

⁷⁸In 2010, China seized the second position in the world from its Asian rival, Japan, to become the second largest economy in the world after the United States and the largest trading country (**Dollar,2016,p.197**).

the nose in the middle, the eyes will eat each other up,” where the nose was referred to as the Chinese state, while the eyes were a reference to the Uyghur people originating from various oases and regions (Finley,2013,p.419). Across the political spectrum, Uyghurs are grouped into three different clusters with regard to their relationship with the Chinese state, from accepting total integration with China to demanding complete independence from it. On the integrationist side, a minority of the Uyghurs consider China’s aspirations to be in common with their own, and that group's utmost hope is that the government removes the remaining hurdles that thwart an effective and complete integration process between the minorities and the Han. Positioned at the center of the political spectrum is the numerically sizable Uyghur bulk that demands the establishment of genuine autonomy in Xinjiang, and their basic demand is that the system of autonomy guaranteed in the 1982 Constitution⁷⁹ and in the 1984 Regional Autonomy Law⁸⁰ be tangibly and effectively executed in the real sense of the word that would help preserve the Uyghur identity and culture. On the other side of the political spectrum, there is a group of Uyghurs that would defy

⁷⁹The Chinese constitution's 1982 version continues to be the most crucial administrative amendment, acting as a watershed moment between all the amendments designed to distance the country from the Cultural Revolution and to reframe China's image globally.

⁸⁰An administrative draft concerned with minorities and their regions with the aim of implementing the system of regional autonomy stipulated in the constitution issued two years earlier (Moneyhon,2003,p.512).

anything less than the right to self-determination and complete independence from China. Although many of them are secularists, still among this group are the Islamists that have employed a political discourse that is compatible with the independence route but is at loggerheads with the Chinese regime that is intolerant of its goals and its rhetoric (**Moneyhon,2004,p.14-15**).

This is with regard to the relationship of the Uyghurs and the Chinese state on the part of the Uyghurs. As for the Chinese state, it formulates its policy regarding the Uyghurs on the principle that Xinjiang is an irreversible Chinese region. In China's point of view, it faces a triple-tier ideology in Xinjiang: extremist, separatist, and terrorist ideology that is void of ethnic, religious, and cultural diversity and echoes back the region's independence slogans all the time (**Aryodiguno,2021,p.68**). On top of that, China claims that it targets individuals, and not the whole Uyghur group, who do not adhere to the central government's project and who believe in a political and social model different from the one imposed by the state, and they may be among Uyghurs or any other minority (**Cappelletti,2020,p.22**). And that's why a group of Uyghur individuals who did not adhere to the Chinese dominion over Xinjiang started fleeing outside China in the 1980s, and their

destination was either Turkey, Central Asia, or some Western countries **(Dabphet,2020,p.69)**. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, China emerged as a regional powerhouse and gained a foothold in the countries of Central Asia after the establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization⁸¹. In attempting to woo countries in Central Asia, China pledged to provide substantial loans and generous aid to member states that would support China's internal fight against the separatist forces and would offer a helping hand in suppressing the politically active Uyghurs⁸² that had fled there **(Bovingdon,2004,p.23)**. "In general, Muslims are a political dilemma for non-Islamic countries, and they are unable to integrate with the culture of the nation-state in which they exist." The Uyghurs that are integrating well into Chinese society have rendered the mentioned prevailing assumption out of touch **(Gladney,2003,p.452)**. Here comes the conclusion of Professor Samuel Huntington, the American political scientist and former director of the Harvard Center for International Affairs who authored the "Clash of Civilizations" book, that instead of interstate wars, the post-Cold

⁸¹The Shanghai Five was established in 1996 between China, Russia, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan, and in 2001 Uzbekistan was added to the organization that became the Shanghai Cooperation Organization **(Bovingdon,2004,p.23)**.

⁸²With the expansion of Chinese hegemony globally and regionally, China has succeeded in demanding the extradition of suspected Uyghur separatists from many member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, as well as countries such as Pakistan and Nepal, in which China maintains strategic and economic importance **(Bovingdon,2004,p.23)**.

War landscape will be marked by civilizational conflicts where people from diverse backgrounds struggle to coexist. This hypothesis can be effectively examined alongside the Uyghur nationalism movement, which integrates aspects of Turkish and Islamic culture with the Han culture dominant in China (Hyer,2005,p.26).

2. The Security/Military Situation

Mentioning previously the relationship between the Uyghur and Han nationalities in Xinjiang, it must be noted that this relationship is not an equal and balanced relationship. The population of the Han exceeds one billion people, while the Uyghurs have not crossed the threshold of fifteen million. Regarding power on each side of the equation between the two, the People's Liberation Army, which is the official army in China and whose mission is to implement the orders of the Chinese government and the Communist Party, must be taken into account. This vast military organization is certainly a tool in the hands of the Han majority, or of the government that rules in their name, and aims to impose the Chinese scheme in Xinjiang. The presence of the PLA in Xinjiang started following its

victorious campaign, led by Peng Dehuai⁸³, against the Nationalist Kuomintang forces⁸⁴, which resulted in Xinjiang being integrated into China—a region that did not align ethnically or culturally with the Chinese heartland and was marked by considerable social backwardness **(Clarke,2011,p.42)**. In 1962, during the Soviet-Chinese split, the significant number of individuals from Xinjiang's minority groups who escaped to the Soviet Union caused anxiety among China's leadership. The fear that simmered in the Chinese administration was that these people would be trained and armed within the Soviet Union in order to be sent back to Xinjiang to fight and seize it from China's grip. In response, the government closed the border and sent in the army to protect it, then forcibly resettled thousands of minority families away from the northern border region and replaced them with more trustworthy Han individuals **(Bovingdon,2004,p.19-20)**. Despite the tense situation in the north with the Soviets and in the west with India during the 1962 war⁸⁵, the numbers of

⁸³A Chinese Communist military leader (1898-1974) during the Chinese Civil War and Defense Minister from 1954 to 1959. He was purged during the Cultural Revolution and forced to move away from political centers until he died in 1974 since he was the first to criticize Mao's policies during the time of famine.

⁸⁴The nucleus of the Nationalist faction was a revolutionary league that sought to overthrow the imperial regime in China and then became a political party in the first year of the Chinese Republic. From 1928 until their overthrow in 1949 by the communists, with whom they fought a civil war during most of that era, most of China's regions were under the Nationalist control, and then they were exiled to the island of Taiwan after their defeat **(Britannica,2023)**.

⁸⁵More of a border dispute between India and China between the months of October and November of 1962, focusing primarily inside the disputed Aksai Chin region along the borders of the two countries **(Britannica,2023)**.

army personnel and equipment on the border were relatively modest for such a vast region. Rather, it was estimated that China, through such humble defensive reinforcements, would not be able to deter a potential Soviet assault, the possibility of which soared during the Sino-Soviet split **(Millward,2007,p.297)**. During the Cultural Revolution, which brought devastation and destruction to Xinjiang, the army was forced to enter Xinjiang with the aim of restoring security in 1971 **(Zanardi,2019,p.2)**.

1979 emerged prominently during the reform period, distinguishing itself from other years in a remarkable way for Asia overall and China in particular. This year, China attempted a brief military invasion of Vietnam⁸⁶ as part of its intervention in the Southeast Asian war⁸⁷ but later pulled its troops back to China, coinciding with the start of the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan⁸⁸. At the end of 1979, the Chinese regime felt threatened by the

⁸⁶The Sino-Vietnamese War between January and March 1979 was not an actual war but rather a border conflict at most. The escalation of Soviet activities in Vietnam and Afghanistan would have achieved the Kremlin's goal of strategically encircling the PRC **(Clarke,2007,p.46)**.

⁸⁷The Cambodian-Vietnamese War (1977-1991) was more likely to be a proxy war between the Soviets, who supported Vietnam, the victorious side in the war, and China, which aided the Pol Pot regime in Cambodia, which is accused of killing 2.2 million people out of 8 million Cambodians during a period of four years between 1975 and 1979 in one of the largest and most infamous genocides of the twentieth century **(ThePeopleProfiles,2021)**.

⁸⁸The Soviet-Afghan War (1979-1989) was a war between the Soviets and their allies in Afghanistan against the mujahideen, who emerged victorious after receiving support from various countries. The Soviets succeeded in isolating China during Deng's entire era, but in return, the war accelerated the collapse of the Soviet Union **(Freeman,2020,p.322)** which bled white in the mountains of Afghanistan.

Islamic Revolution in Iran, which attempted to transform Islam from a religion and belief into a political force that exposes the borders of countries that embrace Islamic societies to the risk of dissipation **(Clarke,2007,p.46)**. The echo of these conflicts resonated in Xinjiang despite the vast distance that separated it from the location of the war in far southern China and the brief duration of China's invasion of Vietnam. Fearing any Soviet ground incursion into that soft flank of China on the northwestern frontier, China transferred sectors of its army to the Sino-Soviet border in Xinjiang, specifically in Tacheng Province. Although the Soviets did not dare to invade Xinjiang, the region remained strained even after the Chinese withdrawal from Vietnam on March 5, 1979. China did not hesitate to bank on the tense situation to aggravate its grip on Xinjiang: the East Xinjiang Military Region was established to strengthen the defense around the nuclear facilities in Lop Nor, and a defensive belt sprouted around the regional capital, Ürümqi **(Clarke,2007,p.47)**. With the Soviets stymied in the Afghan quagmire, Chinese participation in that war on the side of the Mujahideen evolved from a mere low-tech equipment support into more lethal arms supply and a wider defensive strategic communication between the United States and China that was manifested through a series of high-level

diplomatic meetings between the two states during the 1980s. Xinjiang played its role as a communication hub, where it was decided to establish two American intelligence centers in Qitai and Korla in northern and central Xinjiang to monitor the course of the war in Afghanistan **(Clarke,2007,p.49)**. With the end of the incursion in Vietnam and the Soviet involvement in Afghanistan, the possibility of a direct conflict between China and the Soviet Union plummeted, and the status of the East Xinjiang Military Region declined from a potential war zone to a strategic depth that China could utilize to protect the Chinese interior, which is of paramount importance to the CCP. However, the army withdrew from Xinjiang and returned back to its barracks **(Millward,2007,p.297)**. This alteration in the party's primacy in Xinjiang was reflected in Wang Enmao's reappointment as the Secretary of the Communist Party of Xinjiang in 1981, whose policies were based on achieving the following goals: pursuing economic prosperity, urban growth, and reinforcing the borders in order to stabilize the region **(Clarke,2007,p.56)** that Uyghur discontent simmered through during the early 1980s. After the end of Wang Enmao's reign in Xinjiang in 1985, the military level of the East Xinjiang Military Region was downgraded, and the crisis between the Soviets and China eased **(Clarke,2007,p.65)**. Also in the

same year, the PLA opened military training centers in Xinjiang to equip and train Afghan Mujahideen using Chinese weapons and combat tactics **(Zanardi,2019,p.4)** in their cruise to victory against the Soviets who withdrew from Afghanistan in 1989.

3. Uyghur Discontent During the Reform Period

The militarized presence that transformed Xinjiang into a vast military base during the late 1970s and early 1980s constituted only one aspect among a myriad of factors contributing to Uyghur discontent in the region. Rather, the discontent that emerged publicly in the 1980s was the result of numerous factors, anecdotes, events, policies, and procedures from that period and the preceding periods. First, Wang Feng's⁸⁹ attempt in the first half of the reform period, from 1978 to 1985, to purge the cadres associated with Mao's policies from the party **(Clarke,2007,p.50)** and to impose a sudden relaxation of policies concerning minorities fomented an atmosphere

⁸⁹A Chinese official (1910-1998) born in Shaanxi Province. He joined the CCP and became a high-ranking officer in various provinces and regions, including Xinjiang from 1978 to 1981 **(Clarke,2007,p.44)**. During his administration, he attempted to formulate policies in Xinjiang that would help restrict Mao's extreme leftist tendencies in the region, but he faced strong opposition from both the Han and the Uyghurs. This opposition primarily stemmed from a collective fear of punishment, where the “correct” ideological method today could become a “deviation” tomorrow, and any individual who adhered to those policies would be subject to state punishment **(Clarke,2007,p.45-46)**.

that allowed the ecstatic Uyghur people to demand greater levels of autonomy **(Smith,2000,p.20)**. It is worth noting that Uyghur protests during the early part of the reform period, although limited and sporadic, gradually took on a nationalist character **(Han,2010,p.247)**. Although they occurred during a period of social upheaval across China, the Uyghur demands in Xinjiang were the result of purely regional grievances and produced repercussions that did not extend beyond the borders of Xinjiang **(Clarke,2007,p.68)**. At that time, the government feared that the Uyghurs would emerge as a separatist force with an extremist religious character that did not resemble the religiously moderate Chinese society of that era. This was matched by the Uyghurs' apprehension of a demographic catastrophe that would turn them into a minority in their own region as a result of Han immigration and the loss of their religious and ethnic identity **(Bellér-Hann,2022,p.94-95)**.

Although it did not have the same importance as the Uyghurs' fear of assimilation and absorption of their ethnicity among China's ethnic groups, the economic and social differences between the Uyghurs and the Han that became clear to the Uyghurs during the reform period contributed to

reinforcing their self-perceptions that they were subjected to ethnic discrimination by the Chinese state and that the state had not fulfilled its promises to treat all ethnic groups in China on an equal basis **(Finley,2013,p.19)**. The Uyghurs lagged behind their Han counterparts in the quality of education, the level of poverty in their communities was relatively high, and their youth enjoyed fewer opportunities than the Han to land jobs in Xinjiang **(Moneyhon,2004,p.11)**; all these discrepancies fueled demands for Uyghur autonomy **(Finley,2013,p.19)**. The state initially responded with a serious effort to address this disparity and allow the Uyghurs to revive their cultural and religious practices **(Clarke,2007,p.52)**. However, the state's efforts failed and backfired, as many Uyghurs took advantage of the reform policies and the environment of tolerance to call for a greater degree of autonomy and even secession from China **(Smith,2000,p.20)**. Rather, among these secessionists were some who conjured a state from the historical Uyghurstan, while others demanded a purely Islamic theocracy **(Thum,2018,p.11)**.

Opening-up policies have facilitated the flow of international news into Xinjiang and expanded the circle of interests of the Uyghur people, who

have become conversant in global news **(Smith,2000,p.20)**. These reform policies were “welcomed” by the Uyghurs with a series of demonstrations from 1980 to 1981 **(Smith,2000,p.20)** with greater emphasis on Uyghurs becoming on par with the Han people regarding job opportunities **(Grose,2010,p.100)**. When some Han members in April 1980 beat a young Uyghur man in Aksu in western Xinjiang, a sleeping bear was poked; itching for a fight, Uyghurs conquered the streets and called for violence, sparking riots that lasted for two days **(Clarke,2007,p.50)**. A similar situation unfolded in Kashgar in October 1980, where close to thirty thousand Uyghurs came together in a massive protest to condemn the death of a young Uyghur who succumbed to injuries due to brutal beatings inflicted by Han individuals **(Thwaites,2001,p.138)**. During the trial of the Han assailants the following year, violence swept through the city of Kashgar, throughout which protestors demanded secession from China and the revival of Uyghurstan **(Bovingdon,2004,p.7)**. The year 1981 also witnessed some sporadic demonstrations by Uyghur individuals against Han domination of Xinjiang, during which Quranic verses were used as political slogans **(Thwaites,2001,p.138)**. The leadership that appointed Wang Enmao as the Communist Party Secretary in 1981 was concerned about the use of Quranic

verses in protests, as he managed to flex the muscles of the CCP across Xinjiang, drawing a line in the sand for the local population to demonstrate which religious practices are acceptable and which are forbidden according to the Party's perspective **(Clarke,2007,p.56-57)**.

During the second half of the reform period, that is, from 1985 until Deng's resignation in 1989, the Uyghur people again expressed their discontent and dissatisfaction in the streets and squares, and the riots and demonstrations of Uyghur students amplified **(Zanardi,2019,p.2)**. At that time, the stark contradiction between the state's professed aim of national integration and the significant costs of economic and social development initiatives in Xinjiang was crucial in intensifying the crisis and fostering the Uyghur social movement against the Chinese government **(Clarke,2007,p.63)**. In response, authorities banned numerous religious schools and enforced censorship or imprisonment on authors and writers advocating for an alternative narrative of Uyghur history compared to the official Chinese version **(Zanardi,2019,p.2)**. Moreover, during the reform period, the Uyghurs' desire to manage their natural resources that had been confiscated by the state was at the center stage of the grievances expressed

(**Chaudhuri,2010,p.23**). Resentment was evident among the traditional Uyghur farmers who suffered from the calamitous cash crop policies⁹⁰, and this dissatisfaction was penned in literary publications, magazines, and secretly circulated recordings of songs about the bitter life of peasants during the reform period (**Bellér-Hann,2012,p.210**). Moreover, no public figure was able to secure unanimous support and recognition from the Uyghurs in the way that some novelists, songwriters, and singers did. In this regard, the disparity between the Uyghur conflict and the struggle of the Tibetan population with the Chinese state appears as follows: The Uyghurs possess sizable numbers but are leaderless, unlike the Tibetans, who have a leader⁹¹ but lack substantial numbers (**Smith,2000,p.35**).

In 1985, protests reemerged in Ürümqi as Uyghur students advocated for equal treatment and an end to discrimination faced by the Uyghur people in Xinjiang; however, the authorities retaliated severely, resulting in their expulsion from academic institutions and forced relocation to labor camps

⁹⁰An agricultural crop that is based on the production of one crop in a way that exceeds the farmer's need for trade and profit. It differs from subsistence agriculture, in which the farmer produces a limited amount of food to sustain his family and sells the surplus, if any, to other families to obtain a meager profit (**Al-Abadi,2022**). Asia is prominent for many agricultural cash crops, the most important of which are tea, rubber, palm oil, coconuts, and sugarcane (**Britannica,n.d**).

⁹¹The Fourteenth Dalai Lama was born in 1935 and has been the spiritual leader of Buddhists in Tibet since 1940. He won the Nobel Peace Prize in 1989 for his call for freedom from China through peaceful means (**Britannica,2023**).

(**Thwaites,2001,p.203**). The Regional Autonomy Law, which negates distinctive Uyghur traditions and customs, was activated in 1985 to implement family planning policies for minorities, which had previously only been applied to the Han. This action caused widespread ire among the Uyghur ranks, including protests from Uyghur students in Beijing and Shanghai (**Sautman,1997,p.7**). While in November of that year, Uyghur students protested peacefully in Beijing against the nuclear tests conducted by the Chinese government in the Lop Nor region of Xinjiang (**Bovingdon,2004,p.8**), and in December they demonstrated again in Ürümqi against the regime's decision to dismiss *Ishmael Ähmäd*⁹² from his position as head of the Xinjiang government, and calls explicitly intensified for the expulsion of the Han from Xinjiang (**Bovingdon,2004,p.7**). Environmental awareness was also observed among Uyghur students in 1986 as they denounced the environmental pollution resulting from Chinese industries in Xinjiang (**Gladney,2003,p.461**). The year 1988 saw protests against the book "The White House in the Distance," which featured discriminatory statements regarding Xinjiang's minority groups, like Uyghurs, Kazakhs, and others (**Clarke,2007,p.74**). As for the major episode of the 1980s unrest, it

⁹²A Uyghur politician known for insisting that Uyghurs obtain work first before allowing further Han immigration (**Bovingdon,2004,p.7**).

occurred between May and June of 1989, coinciding with the Tiananmen Square protests in Beijing. If that movement had succeeded, it would have been possible for China to get “Balkanized”⁹³.” At that time, the demonstrators bifurcated into two groups based on why they were protesting: The first were students wanted to make their voices heard and express their solidarity with their Beijing counterparts, while the second group was composed of students from religious study groups in the capital, Ürümqi, who protested another book called “Sexual Customs”⁹⁴ that includes many insulting phrases against Islam and Muslims (Clarke,2007,p.74). The magnified demonstrations of this chaotic year represented the straw that broke the camel's back, and the patience of the government that asserted state control over Xinjiang ran out (Castets,2015,p.235). The government retaliated by striking hard at the illegal groups that spread “rumors aimed at harming national unity,” as it declared (Clarke,2007,p.75).

⁹³The disintegration of a union of countries and their transformation into republics based on race or religion, and their continuation of a cycle of violence and endless wars similar to the Balkan wars in southeastern Europe after the collapse of the Yugoslav Federation in 1992.

⁹⁴Protesters considered the book Xing Fengsu written by two Han authors using pseudonyms as the latest in a series of works aimed at hyperbolizing the shortcomings of Islam and Muslims; the book blatantly expresses that Muslims are sexually obsessed and that they erect their mosques in a way that resembles a female’s body (DelVecchio,1989).

The Uyghurs branched out in their political and social movement during the reform period into two ideologically different camps, depending on the geographical region. In northern Xinjiang, the movement centered around a democratic nationalist method where students and urban intellectuals began demanding higher degrees of autonomy and opposing submission to the Han in Xinjiang. The students aimed to discard outdated concepts such as “class struggle” and “dictatorship of the proletariat” and replace them with progressive concepts inspired by the Western world, such as “rule of law” and “civil society.” (Castets,2015,p.233-234). While in the rural south, the principles of Islam taught in religious schools have dislodged Western values called for in the societies of northern Xinjiang. In addition to intensifying calls that explicitly called for secession from China (Clarke,2007,p.51), southern protestors promoted the idea that Islam must provide principles and values to structure the ideal social-political system. This developed into a scene of struggle that views the values and customs derived from religious schools as the basis for a society freed from the authority of the CCP and its values that oppose the values of the Islamic religion (Castets,2015,p.234). The acceleration of demonstrations and unrest in late 1989, coinciding with the spread of international news through

national and international media, provided a standard of comparison for the Uyghurs with their Muslim brethren in Central Asian Republics as they were in the process of controlling their political structures and economic, social, and cultural resources during the Soviet Union's demise

(Finley,2013,p.170). Lucian Pye, an American political scientist and sinologist who specializes in comparative politics and China affairs, has warned that demolishing cultural differences between minorities and majorities could lead to greater ethnic tensions as considerations of economic and political power rise to prominence, and that tightening financial conditions may in turn lead to an increased minority interest in intensifying their political movement **(Finley,2013,p.402)**. Mutual bias appears in this case, such that, from the perspective of officials, cadres, and state workers, the episodes of regional conflict and the Uyghur political strife were and still are the work of a handful of extremists who are opposed by most Uyghurs **(Bovingdon,2004,p.6)**. While from the Uyghur vantage point, liberalization implemented by the party since the beginning of the reform period in China promised much but delivered little of what the Uyghurs had hoped for in practice **(Clarke,2007,p.50)**. As a result, in their struggle with the state, the Uyghurs surrendered a portion of their identity

and a fraction of their traditions without finding a sense of belonging that would embrace them (**Cappelletti,2020,p.262**). Despite that all oppressed people find solace and comfort in faith and religion, China had transformed Islam from religion and belief into a political force, where theorists of the “clash of civilizations” presented Islam as “Jihad” alone, while communists labeled Muslims as separatists and uprooted all cultures from China, except the Han culture (**Arya,2010,p.201**).

4. Han Discontent During the Reform Period

Like all other ethnic groups globally, among the Han population, there is a diversity in how receptive some individuals are to distinct cultures and peoples. Among those coming to Xinjiang were those who were keen to understand the lives, characteristics, and culture of the minorities present in the region, and there were certainly those who isolated themselves exclusively within their environment and far from all the peoples different from their own who “wouldn’t touch individuals from other ethnicities with a 10-foot pole.” In comparing Uyghurs and Han groups in Xinjiang in general, many Han immigrants hold a more positive view of the Chinese

state than their Uyghur counterparts. Han individuals are grateful to the CCP for investing in the frontier region, albeit to a much smaller extent than in the eastern regions, and supporting its development **(Cappelletti,2020,p.3)**, which was put on the back burner before the reformist leaders took control during the 1980s. Some of the Han people, especially the group that expects everyone to subscribe to the belief of “the superiority of the Han over the rest of the peoples in China,” express their astonishment at the ingratitude shown by those minorities who, throughout the entire 1980s, strived to demand the departure of the Han from Xinjiang **(Finley,2013,p.11)**, which pocketed the state’s consideration due to the presence of the Han in it during the reform period.

Development in Xinjiang during this time was the result of government policies and the work efforts of individuals of all ethnic groups, including the Han people who came primarily to work. These people are frequently abhorrently portrayed in the communist media as labor flocks who can be employed at any time and transported to any place as if they are not human beings with certain desires, dreams, and aspirations **(Byler,2018,p.286)**. Signs of Han discontent in Xinjiang began to cement

with the advent of the reform period. During the Cultural Revolution in China, which afflicted all ethnic groups altogether, expressing discontent publicly was impossible. However, dissatisfaction arose during the reform period, as some Han youth found themselves working in unfamiliar territories under harsh conditions, consuming foreign cuisine, and living in inadequate housing compared to their hometowns **(Millward,2007,p.279)**. Even the architectural style of mosques increasingly resembled the Arabic style, which deepened the Han people's fear of being swallowed by Muslims **(Aryodiguno,2021,p.71)**. Many Han youth felt they did not belong in Xinjiang and wanted to return to the interior during the period when Deng allowed large numbers of them to return to their hometowns **(Clarke,2007,p.50)**. The Indian writer Vikram Seth, who toured⁹⁵ Xinjiang and Tibet during 1981, voiced the Han public discontent in his work. The author notes that certain Han immigrants likened Xinjiang to New Zealand, emphasizing that its geographical remoteness makes it distant from many nations worldwide. Some of these individuals, with a hint of sarcasm, questioned why the country wasn't dispatching Han people to colonize the moon instead **(Finley,2013,p.26)**.

⁹⁵Indian writer Vikram Seth documented his 1981 tour of western China in his 1983 book: From Heaven Lake: Travels Through Sinkiang and Tibet.

Even Xinjiang witnessed protests by Han individuals; in November 1979, approximately 1,500 Han individuals gathered in Aksu and carried out a hunger strike for 100 days, occupying government buildings to force the government to listen to their demands and return them to their provinces. After they broke off the strike and evacuated the buildings following a government decision allowing them to return, the government retracted its decision, arrested some, and canceled their return permits **(Millward,2007,p.280)**. In addition, many Han individuals complained about the government's preferential policies for minorities, specifically in regards to family planning **(Sautman,1997,p.30)**, while voicing their bias against the Uyghurs as primitive peoples inhabiting the frontiers **(Byler,2018,p.288)**. Not only did the Uyghurs feel discrimination, but many Han people felt it too and feared that preferential policies were more likely to be a practice of political correctness⁹⁶ in favor of the ethnic minorities at the expense of the Han group, which began bearing intense hatred for minorities **(Aryodiguno,2021,p.71)** and a fear of losing their dominance in Xinjiang **(Finley,2013,p.77)**.

⁹⁶A term used to indicate the slightest expression of offense in political discourse, especially when describing minorities of race, culture, or sexual orientation. Conservatives opposed it for what they saw as the rise of left-liberal concepts and teaching curricula in Western universities and colleges since the 1990s **(Roper,2023)**.

Conclusion of Chapter 2

Long story short, the "militarization" of Xinjiang hindered the process of Uyghurs' adaptation to Chinese society. In addition to limiting their freedom and ability to move in their original region, the military manifestations deepened discontent among the Uyghurs, who felt strangers in their area and that the already adverse relationship between them and the Han became more strained and complex. Rather, by transforming the Xinjiang region into a military zone, China made it clear to the common Uyghur individual that Xinjiang had become Beijing's backyard in its wars with the Soviets, a testing field and training area for foreign fighters on their land, and that a chunk of their identity related to their land had been erased and a part of their culture had been sacrificed to an imported cause.

This bitterness exists among most members of the Uyghur people, who, instead of living, just continue to exist, but without a homeland, identity, and unique culture that resembles them. The Uyghur political strife during the 1980s did not produce independence or autonomy to a

higher degree; it only robbed the Uyghurs of a period that could have been more suitably exploited to secure a comfortable and prosperous life, during which they remained unfit to connect with others and voluntarily follow the process of modernization instead of being forced to do so, as has happened throughout the coming century. The Uyghur political movement also constituted a wrecking ball that was set to dismantle the political structure of the tolerant reformist leadership while unintentionally muting the voices of the Han people who called for openness to the Uyghurs and adaptation to their culture.

After the existential threat that China suffered during the Tiananmen Square events in 1989, the central leadership preferred to amend its policies to satisfy the actual societal power in China, the Han group, who felt discriminated against by the state's preferential policies. The state gradually abandoned the "better tomorrow" that was promised to the minorities in order to cross into the new world that began to take shape in the 1990s within the framework of political realism, which focuses on policies to meet the needs of the central nationality in the "nation-state." From the state's viewpoint, the priority

of pleasing the national/ethnic majority outweighed both the preferential policies embedded in China's reform agenda and the cultural adaptation strategies aimed at the Uyghurs, who did not extend their hands in meeting the state, which tried to engage with them, albeit insufficiently, through the reform period.

Image #6

Statue of the Goddess of Democracy taken by students as an icon of the Tiananmen Square sit-in, with a portrait of Mao Zedong in the back.

<https://www.frieze.com/article/tiananmens-goddess-democracy-remembering-pillar-defiance>

Image #7

Uyghur women collect cotton by hand during the winter in Kashgar, southwest Xinjiang.

<https://www.alamy.com/stock-photo-china-province-xinjiang-kashgar-uyghur-women-harvest-cotton-manually-105231591.html>

Chapter 3

Socio-Economic Reforms in Xinjiang During Deng Xiaoping's Era

(1978-1989)

I. Socio-Economic Landscape

1. Xinjiang Company for Production and Construction: Economic Facet of Chinese Colonialism in Xinjiang

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Chapter 3: Socio-Economic Reforms in Xinjiang During Deng Xiaoping's Era (1978-1989)

I. Socio-Economic Landscape

1. Xinjiang Company for Production and Construction: Economic Facet of Chinese Colonialism in Xinjiang

The "free market" concept has been at the heart of economic discussions for an extended period, as scholars seek to understand and analyze how global markets function in relation to buying, selling, and meeting the needs of individuals in society, while also exploring what kinds of economies are best suited in absolute or region-specific contexts. This concept is the extent to which a society or a state intervenes in stimulating demand for a commodity or leaves the price to be determined according to supply and demand. Today, it has become self-evident that there is no way forward for states except to intervene to balance the market and prevent a

recession⁹⁷ or depression while trying to thwart any specter of potential crises, and that system is known as neoliberalism. Deng understood the practicality and feasibility of this method, so he limited the socialist ideology exclusively to the political dimension and made China move forward on two wheels: efficient post-reform state institutions and productive private companies that would have been nonexistent in socialist systems had it not been for Deng. Throughout China's reform era, restrictions on private enterprises and government involvement gradually lessened, leading to the privatization of state institutions that were no longer viable, thereby reinforcing the decentralization of state authority **(Brandt&Rawski,2008,p.17-18)**. Even before Deng's reforms, the incorporation of Xinjiang into the PRC brought significant economic benefits to the region, including massive growth in GDP and improved infrastructure **(Bovingdon,2004,p.37)**. While Xinjiang peasants, who were likely the majority of the population, gained more economic control through agricultural land reform policies **(Thum,2018,p.9)**. Beijing's initiatives steered Xinjiang's economic development **(Cappelletti,2020,p.48)**. To

⁹⁷After the Great Depression of 1929 eroded faith in the classical liberal model, the neoliberal system took hold, prompting governments around the globe to implement market interventions to avoid future crises.

achieve this, China set up a semi-governmental organization tasked with urbanization and economic management in the region.

Approximately twenty thousand demobilized PLA soldiers and about eighty thousand soldiers from the local National Army garrison enlisted in the Xinjiang Production and Construction Company that was established in 1954. They began cultivating the land, raising animals, and building roads and irrigation canals in order to integrate a broader number of Han newcomers into the region **(Lüthi,2013,p.158-159)**. In Xinjiang, towns and cities were built from the ground up by this company **(Arya,2010,p.195)** that was mentioned in its motto the following: “Reclaim the land, fortify the border, and fill Xinjiang with Han people.” **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.266)**. According to its founding statement, the Xinjiang Production and Construction Company, abbreviated to XPCC or Bingtuan, settled Han people coming from the Chinese interior in order to protect the western and northwestern areas to secure China's frontier territory **(Lüthi,2013,p.162)**. The XPCC, which is significantly funded and backed by the state, operates primarily as a political organization disguised as a trading company **(Cappelletti,2020,p.9)**, with Han volunteers, who either escaped the famine

or were targeted during the anti-rightist movement, making up 10 to 40 percent of its workforce **(Finley,2013,p.24-25,46)**.

The company operates public institutions in Xinjiang in a manner similar to what the state does, including the prison service and courtrooms. In addition, the XPCC develops pipelines, improves roads and railways **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.268)**, and constructs and controls playgrounds, schools, nurseries, and scientific research centers **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.16)**. The company, perceived by the party as a tool for controlling frontier areas, has expanded its reach by constructing new cities like Shihezi in the north, which is mainly inhabited by Han people, and by utilizing rivers to construct reservoirs and hydroelectric power stations **(Finley,2013,p.61)**. Cotton cultivation is part of the company's activities, yet the state has enforced cotton production among Uyghur farmers in the countryside, despite its unpopularity with them. These farmers have been required to sell their cotton at prices beneath the market value, to the company's advantage **(Veg,2008,p.145)**. The state shows no interest in letting the Uyghurs in the south, who find cotton cultivation to be labor-intensive and unprofitable, build up their wealth **(Finley,2013,p.61-62)**. The increase in population

growth and the expansion of competition for cotton production between the company and Uyghur farmers entered Xinjiang into a spiral of reclaiming additional areas of land on a large scale in order to achieve a greater yield of cotton there **(Finley,2013,p.61)**. The prevailing notion is that a cotton-based economy in Xinjiang reinforces the unification of various territories within China, to the advantage of the Han people, who often come out on top in this competition **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.24)**. The matter is not limited to cotton only, but the productivity of most major crops per hectare is higher in the farms of the XPCC than the average regional production per hectare of other lands in Xinjiang. Moreover, the company's agricultural lands are distributed throughout Xinjiang, and the company has an excellent ability to penetrate local, regional, and even international markets **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.23)**. Dominating vast territories in Xinjiang offers a clear advantage to the company in order to survive and continue; four hundred rivers pass through the agricultural and pasture lands of the company, where water is considered the most valuable natural resource in these arid desert areas, and reliance on it is the basis for any agricultural or economic growth **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.22)**. Despite obtaining financial support from Beijing, the annual revenues in Xinjiang are insufficient to cover the budget deficit at

the end of each year; needless to say, the XPCC is the culprit for this mismanagement of public financing in the region **(Cappelletti,2020,p.13)**.

The scene of the barren borderlands awaiting Han migrants who are determined to turn it into a “suitable place” remains an apparent embodiment of the essence of the relationship between the XPCC settlers and Xinjiang **(Lüthi,2013,p.163)**. It is natural to consider the company as the mainstay in the project to colonize the region and integrate it into the national economy and culture **(Cappelletti,2020,p.12-13,124)**.

2. The Socio-Economic Situation in Xinjiang During The Reform Period

Some scholars and writers argue that the poor are not always the most rebellious group in society, nor do they always protest during the worst economic times. Rather, they usually throw caution into the wind once they feel there is a vast gap between their actual economic situation and their expectations. This was the case in Xinjiang during the reform era, where economic disparity constituted a reason for the successive Uyghur calls for secession from China **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.10)**. In a clear confession that

minority areas were mired in poverty during the period preceding the reform era, the state concluded that economic growth and improved living standards would eliminate the spread of separatist sentiment in Xinjiang **(Millward,2007,p.295-296)**, where the individual would stop caring about political issues and be catapulted into a rat race where he would consume and acquire goods around the clock. This actually happened after China transitioned from the 1950s Mao era, in which the value of equality was championed, to the get-rich-quick era of the 1980s Deng era **(Sautman,1997,p.30)**, which witnessed the decline of ideology and the focus on achieving results through pragmatic methods **(Clarke,2007,p.54)**. In its article 122, the constitution stipulates that the state provides minorities with material and technical assistance in order to accelerate their economic and cultural development **(Constitute,2018)**. Thus, the state guaranteed the inclusion of minorities in the economic reform process as a necessary step to maintain the stability of society and the social system in the early stage of the reform period **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.9)**.

After it was dissolved in 1975 due to internal struggles between party factions in the midst of the Cultural Revolution, Deng restored the XPCC in

1981 amid fears of economic stagnation and the spread of fundamentalism in the region (**Erickson,2019**). Since the 1980s, the company has undergone a large-scale reform process that has challenged its nature; the company's farmers, whose number exceeded two million three hundred thousand people in 1982, have been trained to turn into soldiers when necessary (**Cappelletti,2020,p.130,222-223**). By 1983, the state started blowing its own horn, claiming that it had reclaimed approximately a million hectares of agricultural land and built 691 factories and 170 farms (**Clarke,2007,p.60**). That same year, many sectors of the company underwent nationalization, and various components of the company were allocated to multiple state institutions (**Erickson,2019**).

Despite XPCC's state-supported work showcasing the cornerstone of the development in Xinjiang, the economy in this region remained chiefly dependent on heavy extractive industries, and in return, the manufacturing industries were neglected (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.21**). In the late 1980s, regional authorities imposed protectionist measures to restrict import and export between provinces, banning the import of forty-eight commodities to Xinjiang for fear of draining the local economy (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.21-22**).

Despite these measures, the list of industries in Xinjiang expanded to initially include extractive industries such as crude and refined oil, natural gas, coal, electric power, petroleum, chemicals, cement, steel, electrical transformers, sewing machines, and the textile industry, such as wool and silk. In the opening phase of the reform period, the Xinjiang government collaborated on numerous projects with foreign nations, including Japan. However, as the state prioritized the development of the eastern coastal regions according to the Sixth and Seventh Five-Year Plans, Xinjiang and other areas were relegated to a source of raw materials and minerals essential for Eastern China's industrial and consumption needs **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.18)**. In addition, the reformist government passed a law that forced raw material producers to sell a quantity of extracted goods to the state at a low price, negatively impacting the most productive sectors in Xinjiang⁹⁸, the extractive sectors **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.10)**. The goal was to supply the Chinese interior with raw materials, while most of Xinjiang's industrial needs were imported from the country's most developed regions in the east **(Cappelletti,2020,p.9)**. In rural southern Xinjiang, the state has

⁹⁸On July 31, 2020, the US Department of the Treasury's Office of Foreign Assets Control under the Magnitsky Act imposed sanctions on the Xinjiang Production and Construction Company, the company's former political commissar Sun Jinlong, and the Communist Party's deputy secretary, Peng Jiarui. This is due to serious human rights violations, which included mass arbitrary detention and severe physical abuse, among other serious violations targeting Uyghurs **(U.S.Department-of-Treasury,2020)**.

given free rein to handicraft industries, such as daily-use goods, jewelry, knives, carpets, silk, traditional musical instruments, *doppa* hats, and other types of handicrafts. The local ethnic *doppa* hat offers the world a glimpse into the special Uyghur culture and provides a blueprint on how peasants are able to escape poverty when they are provided with credit facilities from the state **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.20-21)**.

Despite the conflict between China and the Soviets hindering trade during the Sino-Soviet split **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.20)**, China's decision to open land crossings in Xinjiang in the 1980s boosted trade and revitalized the historical Silk Roads, notably the routes connecting Xinjiang to Kazakhstan to the north and Pakistan to the south **(Millward,2007,p.289)**. In its quest to seize trade opportunities with the Middle East during the 1980s, Xinjiang received delegations from organizations from that region to discuss trade, investment, and employment opportunities in the Middle East **(Zanardi,2019,p.2)**; the first Islamic joint-stock company in China was established in Ürümqi in 1984 **(Clarke,2007,p.61)**, while projects worth four million dollars in the three western regions of China, including Xinjiang, were financed by the Islamic Development Bank

(Zanardi,2019,p.2-3). After the opening of the Karakorum Road⁹⁹ in 1983, trade between Xinjiang, Pakistan, and Afghanistan consolidated, and bilateral cross-border trade with the Soviet Union resumed, amounting to one billion eight hundred million dollars until 1985 **(Clarke,2007,p.61-62)**. In January 1988, the State Council took a significant step by agreeing to implement a nine-point preferential policy. This policy included tax exemptions, facilitated commercial transactions, and granted greater freedom to the Xinjiang government, all contributing to the rapid growth of foreign trade in Xinjiang **(Cappelletti,2020,p.46)**. The foreign trade landscape in Xinjiang saw significant growth due to government regulations and various entities, climbing from \$17 million in 1980 to \$250 million in 1987 **(Clarke,2007,p.71)** and further up to \$439 million in 1989 **(Millward,2007,p.289)** while maintaining commercial ties primarily with Mongolia and Eastern Europe **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.20)**.

In earlier times, the bulk of the barriers to development in Xinjiang were attributed to shipping and transportation facilities, as goods arrived in

⁹⁹A principal hub along the Silk Roads, Karakorum was the capital of the Mongolian Kingdom from 1235 to 1260 and then the capital of the Yuan Dynasty in the 14th and 15th centuries. The exact current location of this ancient city is unclear, but its ruins are located in the Orkhon Valley **(Migiro,2019)**.

China from the United States faster than they arrived from Xinjiang **(Moneyhon,2003,p.502)**. Developing railways and highway construction during the 1980s expanded Uyghur mobility and spurred trade in Xinjiang **(Moneyhon,2004,p.8)** by linking northern Xinjiang with its underdeveloped south **(Clarke,2007,p.53)**. Once the borders with Central Asia were reopened in the 1980s, many Uyghurs embarked on bilateral trade, exporting textiles and household items west while importing other industrial goods in return; among these was the Uyghur businesswoman *Rebiya Kadeer*¹⁰⁰, who embodied a successful role model in Xinjiang **(Bovingdon,2004,p.38)**, where minor commercial activities were allowed during the 1980s **(Thum,2018,p.11)**. Businessmen, or businesswomen like *Mrs. Kadeer*, have become a common sight throughout China **(Millward,2007,p.292)**, where the reform era catapulted Uyghur entrepreneurs globally after socialist market policies¹⁰¹ were implemented **(Millward,2007,p.288,292-293)**. However, it must be noted that the emergence of a modest middle class of

¹⁰⁰Uyghur businesswoman (1946-), human rights activist, and advocate for Uyghur autonomy in China. She made her fortune during the reform period and was nominated for the Nobel Peace Prize in 2006 **(Britannica,2023)**.

¹⁰¹An economic system that aimed to coexist with the globalized capitalist system in the eighties and nineties by straddling socialism and free enterprise, where enterprises are often publicly owned but production and consumption react to market fluctuations rather than government planning **(Britannica,n.d)**. This system relied on the principle of non-interference in regulating labor market activities within the survival of the fittest context **(Zang,2012,p.87)**.

Uyghur businessmen during that period does not mean that the majority of the Uyghurs enjoyed an economically prosperous life **(Finley,2013,p.76)**.

In Xinjiang, the economy relies heavily on two main pillars—the black symbolizing oil and the white representing cotton—which are critical to the region's development and economic growth **(Moneyhon,2003,p.503)**. Regarding the black pillar, Xinjiang reserves amount to 2.5 billion tons of oil and 700 billion cubic meters of natural gas, but the main problem remains the relatively high cost of extraction **(Finley,2013,p.64)**. Moreover, during the reform period, the production of petrochemicals, textiles, coal, electricity, iron and steel, chemical fertilizers, and cement increased rapidly in Xinjiang **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.18)**, which possesses the largest oil and natural gas reserves in all of China **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.268)**. However, the oil sector in Xinjiang remains restricted by strict supervision from the Chinese government, which only allows limited investments by foreign oil companies **(Cappelletti,2020,p.60)**. But China's contribution to developing Xinjiang's oil economy is clear-cut, as it built oil wells in Karamay in the north and in the Turpan Basin in the south **(Finley,2013,p.64)**, and in its effort to improve the transportation and delivery systems of the oil industry,

China reconstructed the Karamay-Ürümqi oil pipeline in 1982 **(Cappelletti,2020,p.62)**. And in 1989, China established the Office of Oil Exploration in the Tarim Basin, whose mission was to drill for natural gas and oil in the three Xinjiang basins: Tarim, Junggar, and Turpan, with an area of more than 740 thousand square kilometers **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.18-19)**.

By interconnecting historic Silk Roads, Xinjiang's cultural cities like Kashgar¹⁰² and Gaocheng, the capital of the Qocho Kingdom, along with various archaeological sites in the Tianshan Mountains, bolstered tourism in the region during the relatively open environment of the 1980s **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.18)**. In addition, Deng's prioritization of the economy at the expense of security interests in the region has reduced travel restrictions between Xinjiang and Central Asian countries **(Gladney,2003,p.462)**. Since its founding in 1985, Xinjiang Airlines has established thirty-five domestic routes to many vital destinations in the eastern part of China and Hong Kong and six international routes to some cities in Central Asia, Russia, and

¹⁰²The city of Kashgar remains a painful example and a sad story to tell about cities that have lost their cultural heritage due to urbanization. By demolishing the Old City of Kashgar, the cradle of the Uyghur civilization that historically mediated the Silk Roads **(Lipes,2020)**, Beijing has activated its strategy to exercise control over lands, resources, and population, and to demolish the symbol of traditional Uyghur culture in the name of modernization **(Bellér-Hann,2012,p.211)**.

Pakistan (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.9**). Emblematic of a new pluralist spirit emerging during the reform period, visitors arriving at Ürümqi Airport were greeted by a huge mural containing images of people from various ethnic backgrounds (**Millward,2007,p.289**). Through its majestic architectural grace, Kashgar welcomed increasing numbers of foreign visitors to the *Afaq Khoja* Mausoleum that became a landmark in the country's campaign to position this cultural city as a hub for tourism and stimulate economic progress through the tourism sector (**Thum,2014,p.233**). *Rahilä Dawut*, a former professor of anthropology at Xinjiang University, declared that the profits made from the mausoleum are pocketed by Han capitalists who own tourism companies and not by the Uyghur individuals who are given crumbs from their table only. Rubbing salt in the wound, an entrance fee to some shrines is imposed on the local residents who aim to perform prayers and other rituals in their own towns and villages (**Finley,2013,p.67**).

Chart #1

A chart illustrating the energy source distribution in Xinjiang reveals that thermal energy derived from gas and coal dominates the energy landscape, with solar energy being the least utilized. This highlights China's reliance on Xinjiang's finite reserves of oil, natural gas, and coal.

<https://www.powermag.com/energy-industry-xinjiang-china-potential-problems-solutions-web/>

Map #6

A map showing the distribution of unsustainable fossil energy, such as oil, natural gas, and coal, over most of Xinjiang's provinces, both north and south.

<https://www.powermag.com/energy-industry-xinjiang-china-potential-problems-solutions-web/>

The economic situation of Xinjiang during the reform period can be divided into three stages: the first from the late 1970s to 1985, the second from 1985 to 1987, and the third and final between 1988 and 1989.

Xinjiang's relatively poor economic performance in the first phase can largely be attributed to its negligible significance in Beijing's overall economic strategy. During the period from 1981 to 1985, the state's Sixth Five-Year Plan funneled government investments to China's eastern coastal provinces, which were close to the East Asian prosperous economies, widening the economic gap between eastern and western China **(Clarke,2007,p.60-61)**. While in the second phase, extending from 1985 to 1987, Xinjiang witnessed further development in the industrial sector and increased foreign trade and investment. Part of this prosperity was due to the exploration and exploitation of hydrocarbon resources in Xinjiang, which had not been fully exploited until that period **(Clarke,2007,p.70)**. Beijing's long-term plan was to establish special economic zones in Xinjiang; massive investments were pumped into its infrastructure to attract investments and turn the province into a regional economic powerhouse in Central Asia **(Cappelletti,2020,p.49)**. In the last phase, from 1988 to 1989, the central government permitted Xinjiang and other provinces to engage in trade with

the Soviet Union, leading to the establishment of trade relations at the government level and facilitating border trade among individuals and private enterprises (**Clarke,2007,p.72-73**). In 1989, more than eighty institutions from across China provided their support by training qualified minority personnel in Xinjiang, as well as through the Human Resources Project in the region that aimed to merge minority members in China's grand economic scheme (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.8**).

Similarly, Xinjiang was classified into three economic regions during the reform period: the first group consists of cities in the north, including Ürümqi, the second group consists of some regions in northern and eastern Xinjiang, which include Aksu and Tacheng, while the last group is some villages in the Taklamakan Desert in southern Xinjiang, and these three regions can be classified, respectively, as developed, developing, and undeveloped regions (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.17**). When the 1980s began, Xinjiang's economy was comparable to its status in 1960; nonetheless, it saw a substantial 139% growth in per capita GDP throughout the reform period compared to the 1960 figures (**Thum,2018,p.11**). On top of that, some Western scholars have argued that Xinjiang was one of the regions that

received the lion's share of governmental aid¹⁰³ among all provinces, and the number of state-owned institutions there exceeded the threshold of seventy-five percent of the number of all institutions in Xinjiang **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.25)**. Although the overall GDP of China expanded 2.37 times during the reform period, minority areas only saw a 1.69 times growth **(Sautman,1997,p.28)**. In contrast, Xinjiang maintained an average annual growth rate of 8.9% **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.10)**, indicating a favorable economic condition compared to other regions and reflecting Beijing's successful strategies for economic development in Xinjiang during this period **(Cappelletti,2020,p.8)**.

The notable growth rate is contrasted by evident dissatisfaction among the Uyghur population in Xinjiang regarding China's resource exploitation and the lack of equal development and job opportunities compared to Han individuals. Among all of these, the issue that sparked the fiercest opposition among the Uyghur people was the Chinese exploitation of Xinjiang's resources. It should come as no surprise that local disputes frequently center on the land, its resources, and how to divide them among the various

¹⁰³Governmental aid in the form of subsidies is different from governmental investment projects like those spent on cities in eastern China.

communities that inhabit it (**Finley,2013,p.60**). The discovery of oil in Xinjiang during the 1980s was seen as manna from heaven that would push the Uyghurs to believe that they would become wealth owners during the reform period (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.10**), but unfortunately they were disappointed when it became clear that the oil extracted from Xinjiang profited people and entities outside it exclusively (**Sautman,1997,p.34**). The China National Petroleum Corporation and Sinopec, both state-owned enterprises, have taken charge of energy production in Xinjiang (**Arya,2010,p.196**), which supplied the coastal cities that required it to sustain their rapid economic expansion in the 1980s, benefiting from the profits generated by the extraction of energy and minerals in that region (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.21**). Typically, only 2% of its extracted oil remains in Xinjiang for domestic consumption, with most of the oil transported via the Xinjiang-Shanghai gas pipeline to coastal areas (**Liu&Peters,2017,p.270**). While Xinjiang does retain a portion of the taxes on the oil profits, the Uyghurs insist that the region should be entitled to at least the total value of the oil taxes and maybe even some of the profits that are entirely withheld from it (**Bovingdon,2004,p.39**). On the other hand, Wang Lequan, a Communist Party official in Xinjiang during the 1990s and 2000s, responds

that even if Beijing demands a percentage of the taxes imposed on Xinjiang oil, that percentage flows back to Xinjiang in the form of federal subsidies, and even the residents of the Tarim basin receive natural gas for free **(Finley,2013,p.65-66)**. "It is said that the train heading from Beijing to Xinjiang quickly enters Ürümqi making the sound that it is hungry, then leaves and returns to Beijing making the sound that it is full," goes a common joke from that era about resource exploitation **(Finley,2013,p.120)**. The Uyghurs' discontent was not limited only to Beijing's exploitation of oil and other natural resources, but even the high population density in Xinjiang led to an increased burden on food production. To address the food needs of Xinjiang's residents, 100,000 tons of wheat were imported in 1980, and by 1983, around 75% of southern Xinjiang's peasant population was without firewood for six months of the year, forcing many families to limit themselves to cooking just one meal daily in the summer **(Finley,2013,p.67,69)**. Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, said that although the living conditions in Xinjiang have generally improved, local communities feel it has not been sufficient, especially since they realize that the Han population in the north has reaped far more profits than the Southern

Uyghurs (**Finley,2013,p.76**), who interpret Beijing's economic measures as a "Trojan Horse" aimed at their region (**Moneyhon,2003,p.519**).

Chinese Premier Li Peng¹⁰⁴ rejected Uyghur complaints of slow-paced economic development in their regions during the 1980s, and he stressed that Xinjiang lacked the necessary qualifications for rapid economic development, and thus it had to wait until the 1990s to receive generous state funding (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.22**). Many of the grand infrastructure projects initiated by the central government provided job opportunities for migrant workers rather than local workers (**Moneyhon,2004,p.11-12**); banks and other financial institutions in Xinjiang also employed Han individuals in general (**Sautman,1997,p.22**). In the 1980s, the labor market assigned low-paying, low-status jobs to Uyghur workers who flocked to big cities from their rural villages; this magnified their suspicion of whether they were Chinese citizens like the Han in the eyes of the state (**Cappelletti,2020,p.14**), which easily employed Han graduates from within China in administrative positions in the Xinjiang region, while thousands of

¹⁰⁴Chinese politician (1928-2019) who served as Prime Minister of China from 1988 to 1998 and as Chairman of the Standing Committee of the People's Congress of China from 1998 to 2003. He was among the first to call for the forceful suppression of demonstrators during the Tiananmen Square events (**Britannica,2023**).

minority graduates remained unemployed in their own regions **(Finley,2013,p.52)**. The fact that these migrants held positions created by investments made by mainly Han individuals has not helped reduce domestic dissatisfaction in Xinjiang **(Finley,2013,p.54)**. One of the young Uyghurs vented his anger by saying, “I am a well-educated and capable man, but Han-owned companies will not give me a job. However, if you go to the train station, you can see Han people who have just arrived in order to get the available jobs in Xinjiang. It is a wicked policy to dilute us in our region.” **(Moneyhon,2003,p.505)**. Long story short, employment patterns in government and private industries were at best discriminatory against Uyghurs, and depriving Uyghurs of affluent jobs reduced their social mobility during the 1980s **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.121)** which widened the economic gap between the Uyghurs and the Han, both in terms of income and in the quality of life for both groups **(Bovingdon,2004,p.40)**. Han individuals held nearly four-fifths of all jobs in manufacturing, oil and gas, transportation, communications, and science and technology industries, and fully nine-tenths of jobs in construction **(Cappelletti,2020,p.93)**. For example, out of 4,000 technical workers in an oil exploration project in the Taklamakan Desert, only 253 workers come from minority groups, and in

the oil field in the Tarim Basin, relatively few jobs are allocated to minorities overall (**Moneyhon,2003,p.505**). An alternative viewpoint from 1982 indicates that 84.3% of workers in primary industries reliant on raw material extraction, like fishing, agriculture, and mining, were minorities, while only 6.06% of workers in secondary industries associated with manufacturing and converting these raw materials, such as manufacturing, consumer production, and communications, were minorities (**Finley,2013,p.48**). Han individuals often constituted business owners or first-class employees, unlike minorities, who usually filled the rank-and-file levels of the job stratum (**Dabphet,2020,p.68**). Some Han scholars justify this by positing that during the hiring process, employers take into account university entrance examination scores, as China's preferential policies assign Uyghur individuals a pass mark that is typically lower than that assigned to Han students in universities (**Grose,2010,p.100**).

The uneven development path followed during the reform era mostly affected areas inhabited by minorities, and the disparities became even more pronounced with the knowledge that ethnic minorities live in more than 80% of China's poorest provinces (**Cappelletti,2020,p.30**). Ironically enough, an

increasing number of Uyghurs found themselves nostalgic for the Mao Zedong era, driven by the conviction that they experienced greater equality in social and economic conditions during that time than in the reform period, when inequalities became more conspicuous with their Han counterparts **(Finley,2013,p.273)**. Even though life has clearly improved since the Mao era, the dissatisfaction felt is due to the fact that they now have benchmarks to evaluate their social and economic status during the reform period **(Smith,2002,p.36)**. Moreover, the materialism and consumerism that invaded the world in the 1980s and 1990s tainted the Uyghur society that became mostly devoid of its traditions, while the Han culture invaded this society too and began to integrate into the cities of Xinjiang, gradually uprooting the Uyghur culture **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.868)**. A phenomenon has emerged in Xinjiang, such that throughout the world, migrants are usually the ones who begin working from the bottom of the social ladder to advance themselves, but in Xinjiang, things have turned topsy-turvy, where natives were the ones struggling to climb the social ladder there **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.270)**. Showcasing public discontent at the sluggish reforms, the socio-economic disparity between Xinjiang and the eastern regions can be summarized by a phrase that goes: “While the interior regions

have fully embraced capitalism, socialism is still thriving in Xinjiang.”

(Bovingdon,2004,p.22).

3. Agrarian Reforms in Xinjiang During The Reform Period

The Uyghur community, anchored in traditions, lives at the crossroads of the historical Silk Roads. It certainly possesses highly developed commercial skills due to its proximity to the network of trade routes that have stimulated economic, cultural, and even religious interactions between the East and West of the globe for quite some time. But this was not the case with regard to agricultural skills, where the nature of the land, which is more like an arid desert surrounded by rugged mountains, did not help in the formation of fertile agricultural societies such as those found in the Nile Delta or in Mesopotamia. The matter was compounded by the Uyghurs' dependence on subsistence agriculture, which suffices for the individual and the household but falls short of generating enough profits like the cultivation of cash crops. Adding insult to injury, the isolation of the numerous far-flung oases and the lack of key markets that would link them commercially to each other slashed the already meager profits made by agriculture in the rugged

lands of Xinjiang (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.20**). Despite the slow pace of land reform¹⁰⁵ and collective agriculture, Xinjiang was able to perform relatively well compared to other provinces in the wake of the “Great Leap Forward,” which left the famished to arrive in Xinjiang between 1959 and 1961 and take refuge in the farms of the XPCC (**Lüthi,2013,p.160**).

The reform period effectively commenced in Xinjiang in 1980, where the agricultural lands that had been previously gathered were divided, leading to equal distribution of land plots among rural families; however, this was done through long-term leasing rather than outright ownership (**Bellér-Hann,1998,p.7**). These policies, which were approved during the Third Plenary Session of the Communist Party of China in December 1978—the session during which Deng beat everyone to the punch and seized power—severed China from the Maoist legacy, and during that session it was also decided to abolish collectivization in agriculture and eliminate the commune system altogether (**Clarke,2007,p.42-43**). From 1979 to 1980, Wang Feng, the Secretary of the Xinjiang branch of the Chinese Communist

¹⁰⁵From the miniature to the massive: such laws passed by the government aim to reshuffle agricultural lands by shifting ownership from a limited number of affluent landowners to a broader group of impoverished farmers who work the land, thereby setting the economic cycle in motion.

Party, outlined an eight-point strategy, the centerpiece of which was the establishment of a “home responsibility” agricultural system facilitating the reclamation of private land and the raising of livestock for economic purposes in rural communities **(Clarke,2007,p.44-45)**. Although Wang's plan never came to fruition **(Clarke,2007,p.49)** due to the insufficient income produced by farmers, most of whom had only a fraction of land to cultivate **(Bellér-Hann,1998,p.9)**, the “home responsibility” system in the early 1980s was initially welcomed by Uyghur peasants **(Hann,2014,p.186-187)**. De-collectivization in China during the reform period did not mean privatization as universally recognized; the state retained the right to acquire the harvest of the peasants, who were transformed from commune farmers into state serfs, whenever it wished **(Clarke,2007,p.45)**. Alongside adverse weather conditions and the frequent occurrence of natural disasters in certain parts of Xinjiang, skepticism surrounding the validity of Deng's new reform policies—which contradicted classical socialism—contributed to the economic downturn in the region and the early setbacks of these reforms **(Chaudhuri,2005,p.9)**. As if it were barking up the wrong tree, these reforms targeted large agricultural lands, not the Uyghur indivisible land chunks; for the majority of Uyghur peasants,

animal husbandry—rather than agriculture—remained their main source of income (**Bellér-Hann,1998,p.9**). In the end, the agricultural reforms adopted in the year 1980 didn't prove their worth until the mid-1980s (**Clarke,2011,p.74**).

The agricultural reforms in Xinjiang tripled the value of agricultural production between 1978 and 1984, compared to the growth rate from 1958 to 1978. This success is also evident in the per capita income of farmers, which increased from 198 yuan in 1978 to 363 yuan in 1984 (**Clarke,2007,p.68-69**). Likewise, before 1983, Xinjiang imported about 150 million kilograms of food grains each year. Still, in 1986, thanks to agricultural reforms that began in 1980, Xinjiang sold the state 500 million kilograms of surplus grain to support other regions in China. Since then, Xinjiang has been exporting oilseeds, cotton, wool, and fruit, and more than 5,000 companies are working in Xinjiang to produce these goods in a capitalist manner alien to socialist China (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.17**). While the reforms initially contributed to economic growth in Xinjiang and enhanced farmers' autonomy, beginning in the middle of the reform period, peasants were obliged to grow a specific crop and compulsorily purchase grain from

the state. Such policies reset the state to square one, where it restored its control over the peasants' economic activities while asserting itself over the agricultural sector in Xinjiang (**Clarke,2007,p.70**). Interviews conducted by Ildikó Bellér-Hann, associate professor at the Department of Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies at the University of Copenhagen and a specialist in Turkic and Central Asian Studies, in the southern part of Xinjiang indicate that agricultural production here has been partly neglected by the non-interventionist state since the advent of the reform period. At the local level in the south, the state contented itself with providing advice on production methods and introduced new crops by granting incentives. Although they shared dissatisfaction with their northern brothers on fundamental questions, southern Uyghurs were content with the agricultural policies during the reform era (**Bellér-Hann,2012,p.212**).

After achieving self-sufficiency in grains in the 1980s, the party leaders in Xinjiang focused on producing cotton at unprecedented levels, leading to the dominance of the "white and black pillars"—that is, cotton and oil—in the region's development (**Millward,2007,p.299**). Xinjiang is China's largest cotton-growing base (**Liu&Peters,2017,p.268**); it occupies

the first place in cotton production in all of China (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.12**), where, in 1978 alone, fifty-five thousand tons of cotton were produced in Xinjiang (**Millward,2007,p.299**). This relates to China's developmental approach, which intends to cultivate untapped resources throughout all territories (**Liu&Peters,2017,p.268**). Xinjiang's promotion of cotton cultivation and production in the 1980s was aligned with a substantial boom in commercial clothing manufacturing in eastern China, leading the nation to pursue a cost-effective domestic cotton supply to fulfill the escalating global need for T-shirts and jeans produced in China (**Byler,2018,p.38**). Cotton producers in southern Xinjiang encountered significant challenges due to varying purchasing prices and stiff competition from low-cost imported cotton. While only a portion of Uyghur farmers managed to sustain profitability by cultivating a single cash crop, the Xinjiang government benefited by selling cotton at market prices and obtained substantial subsidies from the Beijing government (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.20**). Imported cotton was 15 percent cheaper than what was produced locally in Xinjiang, and the government support that kept the cotton industry going turned out to be very expensive for the central government, so the textile crisis in China left behind a huge stock of cotton piled up, equivalent to the production of

Xinjiang for several years (**Moneyhon,2003,p.504**). A significant number of Uyghur farmers fell into a poverty trap due to their dependency on selling cotton exclusively to state-run companies, mostly controlled by Han, at lowered prices for resale at higher rates to factories in eastern China. Conversely, numerous Han settlers reaped the rewards of employment in the Xinjiang cotton sector as short-term seasonal workers, earning substantial wages and receiving housing support while working in the region (**Byler,2018,p.38**). The cotton industry not only destroyed Uyghur handicrafts and home crafts (**Dabphet,2020,p.68**), rather, it also put the farmers in a poor economic situation without the state, which purchased their production at below-market prices, providing them with subsidies that take their circumstances into consideration (**Bovingdon,2004,p.39**).

4. Women's Work in Xinjiang between Popular Traditions and Societal Transformations

Zang Xiaowei, a Chinese sociologist and professor of social sciences at the City University of Hong Kong, identified an additional reason for the widening income gap between the Uyghurs and the Han in Xinjiang: the

division of traditional gender roles among the Uyghurs. Zang believes that the Uyghur women assume all the household roles and chores so that their husbands can devote all their time and energy to work. The concept of 'motherhood punishment' could result in Uyghur women opting for work breaks, accepting lower-tier jobs, or choosing part-time employment. This deepens the income gap between Uyghur and Han women, and thus between the Uyghurs and Han in general **(Finley,2013,p.59)**. Uyghur women are raised and educated in traditional environments within a strict religious atmosphere where they are supposed to take care of the home and family. They are usually married relatively early, that is, between the ages of fifteen and eighteen, and also after marriage they are not expected to work but rather adhere to household activities **(Cappelletti,2020,p.147)**. During the reform period, the economic necessity required that Uyghur men and women work outside the home as well; many Uyghur women devoted their efforts to obtaining education and taking on jobs outside the home, and in this way they were able to achieve financial and social independence **(Tursun,2017,p.11-12)**. If we pinpoint the compass to southern Xinjiang, the society there highlights more traditional gender roles than those trying to catch up with the modern lifestyle in the north. Work that requires bodily

strength, such as plowing, harvesting, and building, remains defined as men's work. As for women, most of their daily movements are limited to the domestic space **(Bellér-Hann,1998,p.7)**. Uyghur men consider the honor and chastity of their women a pillar that reinforces the patriarchal system in Xinjiang. The fact that women exceed the domestic space and appear in public constitutes a point of contention between Uyghur men and the state **(Byler,2018,p.267)**, which has always encouraged the appearance of minority women in public. This encouragement aims to “slaughter some sacred cows” and demolish any “taboos” that are still lingering among these minorities so that the state can impose cultural integration among the ethnicities and even uproot any societal barriers that prevent minorities from crossing into the more flexible Han society. This does not mean that Uyghur women are happy to be dominated by the Uyghur men and their masculine attitude that manifests male chauvinism. The Uyghur woman is exposed to the chauvinistic behavior of the Uyghur man during several intersections in her life, such as at her father's home, at school, at work, and even at her husband's home **(Tursun,2017,p.21)**. Furthermore, it's important to highlight that throughout the planting seasons, many women quickly join the fields to work alongside their male partners, especially during harvest time,

similar to the early 1980s when women participated in craft industries such as creating the traditional *doppa* hat **(Bellér-Hann,1998,p.8-9)**. Although many of them sew *doppa* hats at home, some Uyghur women come from the countryside to work eight hours, six days a week, at the state-run Kashgar Handicrafts Center. These women are considered¹⁰⁶ a source of livelihood for themselves and their families, which bestows on them a respectful social status, much higher than that of other rural women or city housewives **(Bellér-Hann,1998,p.11)**. Besides the differences in income and types of employment for Uyghur and Han women, there is also a significant disparity in childbirth rates, which significantly impacts women's workload, the nature of this work, and their earnings from it. For example, in 1981, the birth rate of Han women in Xinjiang in the age group from 15 to 19 was only 2.5%, while it reached approximately 33% of Uyghur women in Xinjiang for the same age group **(Sautman,1997,p.8-9)**. The differences in the birth rate could be explained by the educational and professional infrastructure systems that each group enjoys. The resistance against the government's efforts to cap the number of births in rural minority areas is rooted in

¹⁰⁶When Uyghur women were assaulted in factories by Han assailants during the 2010s, Uyghur men felt that the rape of Uyghur women was tantamount to the rape of the entire Uyghur nation. They also felt an insult to their dignity because the attack on Uyghur women embodied an attack on the authority of Uyghur males in their supposed role as “protectors” of the women of their community **(Byler,2018,p.13)**.

religious legislation, making family planning in these traditional societies one of the most challenging tasks possible (**Sautman,1997,p.9**). It is somewhat ironic that, despite the constant emphasis on their physical weakness in folk traditions, women are more self-sufficient than men, and women's value is expressed in terms of the services they can provide in the domestic sphere, which includes social, reproductive, and sexual functions (**Bellér-Hann,1998,p.8**).

5. Urban/Rural Economic Disparities in Xinjiang

“The Chinese empire will collapse from within. The workers and farmers who brought Mao Zedong to power are dissatisfied with the steep gap in wealth levels.” This is how Uyghur activist *Arslan Alptekin* shouted, criticizing the clear economic disparity in China and Xinjiang (**Moneyhon,2003,p.497**). Recognizing that the Uyghurs make up 90% or more of the population in 20 provinces of Xinjiang, the central government concentrated its efforts on 13 of these regions to address poverty during a reform period characterized by rapid economic growth that eluded the Uyghurs (**Moneyhon,2003,p.497**).

The differences between urban and rural areas in Xinjiang are unmistakably stark, with the Han majority concentrated in more developed areas while Uyghurs and other minorities reside in poor areas. In developed cities like Ürümqi, much of the modern sector appears to be Han-dominated, and ethnic profiling is prevalent in employment practices **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.270)**. Uyghurs are often excluded from the industrial labor market and energy services sector in the more developed north, especially in the capital, Ürümqi, and Uyghur migrants from southern Xinjiang are allocated to low-paid service jobs **(Howell&Fan,2011,p.120)**. Some Chinese scholars argue that the distant southern villages and towns are unable to accommodate excess rural labor or stimulate non-agricultural economic activities in the countryside, where most disadvantaged communities are located **(Chaudhuri,2010,p.21)**. There are still districts in Kashgar Governorate where families of four live with an income not exceeding one hundred dollars a year **(Cappelletti,2020,p.20)**. The dire poverty levels in the southern regions coincide with lucrative salaries and burgeoning job opportunities in primarily northern Han cities, including Ürümqi and Shihezi, which feature distinguished services and facilities akin to those found in China's most affluent cities, such as Beijing, Shanghai, and

Guangzhou (**Cappelletti,2020,p.20**). Disparity¹⁰⁷ is also apparent in the financial ability, as the children of Han employees are able to pay university tuition, which may reach two thousand Chinese yuan annually, unlike the children of Uyghur employees who cannot afford it even though they receive government subsidies and their university tuition is limited to 900 Chinese yuan annually due to the preferential policies (**Finley,2013,p.39**).

By building Han settlements near rural Uyghur communities in the north, the state thus aimed to promote economic development and cultural exchange between the two groups, increase financial revenues, meet the needs of the business class for cheap labor, and spread Han culture throughout Xinjiang, which was seen as in dire need of the “superior Han culture” (**Cappelletti,2020,p.123**). Taking advantage of the market adjustments of the reform period, northern cities, such as Ürümqi, Shihezi, and Karamay, became densely populated with Han people. Shihezi benefited the most during that stage among all other cities, and this was evident through the construction of roads, offices, schools, factories, and hospitals.

¹⁰⁷Currently, the total GDP of the three northern cities, Ürümqi, Karamay, and Shihezi, exceeds the total domestic GDP of the entire southern Xinjiang (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.16**). In the midst of the new economic climate that turned against the policies of social justice and equality promoted by Mao, a bourgeois class crystallized among the Uyghurs in the cities, and that class clearly distinguished itself from the rural Uyghur community that still practices a traditional way of life (**Cappelletti,2020,p.99**).

The city received preferential treatment from government subsidies and was upgraded from a city at the district level to a city at the governorate level in 1984 (**Finley,2013,p.45**). In Xinjiang, the southern provinces and counties are notably impoverished, with 19 out of the 27 least developed located in Hotan, Kashgar, and Aksu. These regions, largely populated by Uyghurs, rank at the bottom for economic development among the region's 84 provinces (**Chaudhuri,2010,p.21**). Environmental problems plague Xinjiang too; poor urban planning has led to soil erosion and desertification, exacerbating the divide between the Han-dominated northern regions and the southern Uyghur areas. Additionally, nuclear testing in Lop Nor caused radioactive groundwater contamination (**Bovingdon,2004,p.38**).

Government neglect of the ancient villages in northern Xinjiang caused the depletion of water supplies, which were aimed at the new cities, Shihezi, for instance, which were designed to receive Han migrants. Ambitious irrigation projects were sourced from the rivers of Xinjiang in order to provide irrigation and sanitation to the residents of the new cities (**Finley,2013,p.69**).

Despite the government's preference for the Han regions, the state was able to narrow the income gap between urban and rural areas in the mid-1980s (**Chaudhuri,2005,p.15**). This was the result of agricultural reforms, the

reduction of agricultural taxes, the provision of goods to minorities, and a government aid package exceeding four million dollars in 1980 **(Clarke,2007,p.53)**. In another social contrast, differences can be observed in the average age of Xinjiang residents, which is higher in cities than in the countryside. In 1984, the death rate in Kashgar, a Uyghur-dominated city in southern Xinjiang, was 12.06 per thousand people compared to just 2.17 per thousand people in Karamay, a city in northern Xinjiang populated by Han workers working in oil fields. While part of this disparity arises from the idea that workers are mostly young, the discrepancy in the death rate remains surprising **(Finley,2013,p.56)**. Despite experiencing a higher standard of living during the reform period compared to pre-1949 times, urban Uyghurs felt that the economic development fell short of their expectations. They recognized that the state had opened up the labor market in their regions, yet it was primarily the Han population that reaped the lion's share of the benefits. As for the rural Uyghurs, the situation was different, as they did not come into direct contact with the Han and were unfamiliar with the concept of Han chauvinism, nor did they feel socio-economic inequality like their urban Uyghur counterparts. Rather, their opposition was limited to the issue of birth control and family planning **(Finley,2013,p.413)**.

II. Educational landscape

1. A Historical Overview of Education in Xinjiang

Patterns of disparity indicate that racial discrimination and inequality between the Han majority and the Uyghur minority, especially with regard to socio-economic status, go hand in hand with inequality in levels of educational attainment for disadvantaged minorities. The two variables are closely related; ethnic minorities that performed well in the labor market attained similar levels of education as the Han majority, and this is true for both Koreans and Mongolians, who are among the better-educated minorities. Specific minorities became closer to being economically equal with the Han majority than less-educated minorities such as Uyghurs and Tibetans (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.347**). Linda Benson, a professor of history at Oakland University who specializes in modern Chinese history, argues that the ultimate goal of the PRC's educational policy regarding minority peoples was to integrate all of these groups into one unified socialist state (**Grose,2010,p.97**). The Constitution of the PRC stressed compulsory

primary education for all, so no minority or group was excluded or deprived of their right to educational attainment. Article 19 stated: "The state shall develop socialist educational projects and work to raise the scientific and cultural bar of the entire nation." (**Constitute,2018**). Despite what is stated in the constitution, some believe that the education system in Xinjiang is not only designed to benefit Han students but even aims to "keep the Uyghurs stupid." This is due to the Chinese government's fear that high levels of education among the Uyghurs may provide them with tools to oppose China's control of Xinjiang (**Smith,2000,p.22**).

The study¹⁰⁸ developed by Michal Zelcer-Lavid, a professor of humanities at Bar-Ilan University who focuses on nationalism and ethnic identity in Tibetan and Uyghur minorities, stands out in trying to assess the educational situation of the Uyghur people in Xinjiang during the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The analysis begins by addressing the foundational education structure that prevailed in Xinjiang from the Qing Dynasty until the creation of the People's Republic, which was confined to boys up to the age of ten and was termed the scribe system. Through this

¹⁰⁸Modern education and literary traditions: a comparative view on the development of modern Uyghur and Tibetan literature.

system, children acquired basic knowledge of the Qur'an, knew how to pray, and learned what laws governed the religious and social systems (Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.4). During the period before the People's Republic, Ildikó Bellér-Hann, an associate professor at the Department of Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies at the University of Copenhagen and a specialist in Turkic and Central Asian Studies, estimates that more than 97% of men in Xinjiang were uneducated (Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.4). At the turn of the nineteenth century, the Qing dynasty initiated educational reforms in Xinjiang, primarily establishing a mandatory schooling system that included both Uyghur and Han students. By incorporating the Chinese language and Confucian principles into the curriculum, the goal was to equip the children of the Uyghur elite to serve as liaisons for the state with the local populace. However, the education reform initiative in Xinjiang triggered nationalist reactions and ultimately failed due to resistance from conservative elements within Uyghur society who perceived it as a cultural imposition (Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.4-5). Later, the Jadidist Movement¹⁰⁹ altered the

¹⁰⁹Similar to the Arab Renaissance to some extent, Jadid was a religious and societal reform movement in Central Asia at the outset of the twentieth century that spread to most of the cities of Turkestan and took upon itself the responsibility of raising nomadic life to a higher cultural and moral ideal by opposing the conservatives in southern Central Asia (Saade,2022). The movement scholars published many newspapers and pamphlets, and they also built the first modern theater with the aim of promoting moral behavior. The modernist movement established educational institutions throughout major Turkestan cities, disseminating a range of innovative ideas, such as the liberation of women, public health reforms, and the advancement of modern values (Allworth,2010).

widespread oral education in Xinjiang and established an educational system based on providing students with basic reading and writing skills to eradicate the tradition that had previously spread where villagers had to deal with certain literate people whenever necessary to read written documents **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.12)**. The Jadidist Movement also focused on improving teaching methods, such as requiring teachers to pass exams to prove their professionalism and receive wages for their work instead of receiving gifts, as was the case in the past. The result was a more professional and practical educational system **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.5)**.

When the communist government took control of education in China, it forcibly spread atheism instead of the Islamic religion in Xinjiang. It promoted atheism as a scientific and progressive ideology; science is the truth, while religions, including Islam, are just outdated myths. The state's efforts to portray Islam as a regressive faith destined to fade with the advancement of science and knowledge aimed to illustrate that Muslims in Xinjiang are inferior to their secular, educated counterparts, suggesting that Uyghurs should embrace the Han culture, which is viewed as more enlightened and progressive **(Zang,2012,p.86)**. Anchored in their beliefs,

there is no doubt that most of the Uyghur people rejected the propaganda that tried to strip them of their religious identity and abandoned the system that the nascent Chinese republic tried to impose during that era. Conversely, there was also a Uyghur group that believed the state's propaganda that the official educational system was the way forward **(Finley,2013,p.268)**. In this regard, many Uyghur individuals arrived at the Central Institute for Minorities in Beijing in the 1950s for training and education, thus forming the PRC's first educated generation of Uyghur scholars and intellectuals. However, their academic careers did not thrive long. During the 1960s, China was dominated by leftist¹¹⁰ radicalism¹¹¹; many of the Uyghur scholars were arrested and transported to the countryside to work on the land in order to evolve into good citizens in a classless socialist society. While research and publications on Uyghur culture and traditions largely declined during that period **(Steenberg,2021,p.175)**.

¹¹⁰After the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the term "leftist" changed in the West from Marxism-Leninism to social liberal leftism. This was based on many concepts, including expanding the principle of civil rights to include all minorities in society, accepting different groups socially, racially, and sexually, reviewing the past, and holding accountable leaders of previous wars and national heroes to turn them into criminals. Leftist activism turned into a political trend that is spreading on university campuses among activists from younger age groups that ensnared the majority of Gen-Z and a substantial number of the previous Millennials.

¹¹¹Mao's radical extremism led to the cancellation of sociology, deemed a bourgeois subject by Auguste Comte. Consequently, all related educational and research programs ceased. However, Deng recognized sociology's potential role in modernizing China's education. This led to the subject's rehabilitation, the re-establishment of the Chinese Sociological Association, and a shift away from mixing ideology with politics and educational materials **(Cappelletti,2020,p.117-118)**.

2. Educational Landscape in Xinjiang During the Reform Era

The educational system is one of several systems that the Chinese state optimized during the reform era; since the beginning of the 1980s, the state has followed a “separate but equal” educational system in minority areas, including Han language schools and minority language schools **(Finley,2013,p.37-38)**. Contradicting Mao's skepticism, science during the reform period was considered the key to the future. Consequently, science and engineering became central to education in China, forming the core curricula of Uyghur language schools **(Byler,2018,p.170-171)**. Although curricula were written in minority languages in theory, in practice, this was limited to the humanities and social sciences. This reflected the Han assumption that minority languages were unsuitable for the natural sciences, whose books were automatically translated from Chinese rather than authored and written in the local languages in minority areas **(Finley,2013,p.32)**. In Xinjiang, a paradox persists, where Han schools teach English as a second language after Mandarin, while minority schools teach Mandarin Chinese, which became a compulsory language for first-year middle school students in China starting in 1984, as a second language after

the language of local minorities. Although the state's laws allow multilingualism, multilingualism does not mean equality between the languages, as Han does not learn the Uyghur language the same way Uyghurs learn the Han language (**Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.6**). Even the Uyghurs do not learn the English language necessary in the field of work, which has today become the most demanded language worldwide. Because of their deprivation of studying the English language and the refusal of some to learn Mandarin, which in their view is the language of the colonizer, and also because of their families' need for land labor in rural areas, Uyghurs conquer the bottom of the heap of the labor market (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.349**). This is different for Han individuals, who obtain high-paying and high-status work because of the qualified education they undergo (**Sautman,1997,p.11**).

Overall, statistics collected since 1982 point to positive trends in the diffusion of state-sponsored education in Xinjiang. Dru C. Gladney, a professor of anthropology at Pomona College and a leading expert on the peoples and cultures along the past and present Silk Roads, points out that in the phase extending from 1982 to 1990, the illiteracy rate among the Uyghur

population diminished from 45% to 26.6%, and the percentage of Uyghurs who enrolled in primary schools expanded from 37% to 43% in all of China. However, in universities where minority students must learn Mandarin for admission, the circumstances were disheartening, with the enrollment rate of Uyghurs in bachelor's programs rising from just 0.1% to a mere 2.1% between 1982 and 1990 (**Grose,2010,p.99**). Even the Uyghurs did not constitute the absolute majority of students and members of universities and higher education institutes in their region, as their percentage did not exceed 60 percent in the late 1980s and early 1990s. The irony is that in 1994, 50% of students at Xinjiang University in Ürümqi were minorities, compared to 60 percent back in 1986. Taking the Turpan basin as an example, the percentage of Uyghurs there was reduced to a mere 48% of university students despite constituting 78% of the local population (**Finley,2013,p.40**). An unpublished article has revealed that over 60% of students in certain regions and villages of the Kashgar Governorate drop out due to financial hardships (**Grose,2010,p.99**). While Han individuals in the cities could afford tuition fees, minorities could not, especially during the 1980s, when inflation became severe (**Sautman,1997,p.11-12**). This happened despite the government taking concrete steps to help minorities engage in the

“educational revolution” witnessed during the reform period, which closed the door on the obscurantist approach to fighting science that spread during the Maoist era. Among those steps were approving new laws guaranteeing free education and cancelling secondary fees, which have nothing to do with the main tuition fees **(Groese,2010,p.99)**, allocating three funds to contribute to the education of ethnic minorities, providing free meals to students, and housing in boarding schools in rural areas. Nevertheless, fees still hindered many Uyghur children from pursuing education past primary and middle levels, and the differences between Han and Uyghur populations in education were starkly apparent **(Sautman,1997,p.10-11)**. Parents who enrolled their children in secondary school education to learn Mandarin to enhance their job prospects did not necessarily adopt the Chinese values the state intended for minorities to embrace through education **(Hann,2014,p.195)**.

Adding an additional year to the academic period in order to learn Mandarin is nothing but a stumbling block facing minority students when they enter universities. Thus, minority students lag behind their Han counterparts in a job market that favors fluent Mandarin speakers depending

on job needs. Thus, the income gap between Mandarin and non-Mandarin speakers widens **(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.350)**. Hence, Mandarin-language schools remain the only option for parents in urban centers that aim to enhance their child's future, as these parents can be seen as progressive because they recognize the significance of the Mandarin language in helping minorities navigate the challenges presented by the job market **(Finley,2013,p.40)**. Even though minority communities with educational backgrounds akin to the Han population generally secure comparable levels of employment and types of occupations **(Finley,2013,p.38)**, this does not guarantee that all individuals from these minorities who attend Mandarin schools will land jobs that offer respectable wages and satisfactory benefits **(Grose,2010,p.100)**. It is also possible to conclude that the more integrated the ethnic minority is into Han society and culture, the greater the share of its members who are present in prestigious professions and the lower the illiteracy rate is in its society **(Finley,2013,p.38)**. Many Mandarin-educated minority members, known as the *Minkaohan*, ended up mired in a disadvantageous situation that resulted in losses in either direction during the 1980s reform era. On the one hand, *Minkaohan* individuals have developed a strong sense of inequality between them and the Han people that they felt in

ethnically mixed work environments, job offices, and public places in minority areas. On the other hand, they remained unable to fully participate in the cultural life of their Uyghur ethnic group due to their limited ability to communicate in their mother tongue **(Finley,2013,p.40)**. People generally assume that an educated Uyghur Mandarin-speaking *Minkaohan* is more secular than the *Minkaomin*, who belong to China's minority groups and speak only their mother tongue. Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, refuted this misconception. She considered that many *Minkaomin* are moving toward secularism while *Minkaohan*, due to their exposure to discrimination and their more extensive contact with Han individuals, are regressing to their traditions that adhere to the Islamic religion **(Finley,2013,p.14)**.

Some of the educated, Mandarin-speaking Uyghurs sometimes face persecution and repression from their families and communities, as they often adopt Han Chinese customs in speech, dress, and behavior **(Dwyer,2005,p.37-38)**. They suffer from condescending treatment and racial discrimination in some of the schools that teach Mandarin, which prompted many parents who sent their children to those schools to withdraw them and

re-enroll them in schools that teach their language **(Veg,2008,p.146)**. The combination of discrimination and persecution, along with the prevailing notion that learning is pointless in a region where only the Han thrive, has resulted in almost 50% of rural children in Xinjiang not receiving education beyond mandatory primary schooling **(Veg,2008,p.146)**. As a result, these individuals ended up entering society devoid of professional skills that could raise their status and became easy prey for various extremist ideas **(Hann,2014,p.197)**. During the reform period, preferential policies raised the number of Uyghur students enrolled at all levels of education, but many of them remained dissatisfied with the state of educational development in Xinjiang and complained of very high tuition fees relative to their income. Some of them also protested that pursuing higher education did not guarantee them a prestigious job or high income similar to the Han people **(Grose,2010,p.106)**. In a nutshell, educational reforms have aggravated the levels of social and economic inequality between the Han and ethnic minorities in China since the mid-1980s **(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.351)**. Moreover, China completely eliminated the old Islamic scribe system by developing the education sector in Xinjiang, so the literacy rate of a large part of the Uyghurs increased, and they now have a national awareness and

knowledge of their identity, culture, and history. During that time, the Han people appeared to be supportive of empowering remarkable village students to progress within the Party by encouraging academic endeavors that sought to eliminate the less progressive traits of minority cultures in Xinjiang (Hann,2014,p.203).

Image #8

Burials of *Afaq Khoja* and his descendants in the city of Kashgar, the incubator of the Uyghur heritage throughout history.

<https://www.silkroadhitchhikers.com/?p=1991>

Map #7

Illustrative map of the historical Silk Roads. Between the 3rd century BC and the 15th century AD, the Silk Roads facilitated economic and cultural development across Eurasia while promoting the global spread of religions and ideas through trade.

<https://samatrans.ir/en/history-of-transportation-on-the-silk-road/>

Map #8

A map showing economic differences (GDP per capita) according to ethnic and regional differences in Xinjiang. Uyghur-inhabited areas in the south and southwest suffer the most.

<https://www.geocurrents.info/blog/2013/04/22/xinjiang-china-ethnicity-and-economic-development/>

Conclusion of Chapter 3

By comparing Xinjiang to other provinces and assessing their circumstances against those of the Han people, a typical Uyghur might conclude that the state's shift to an extractive economy to serve eastern provinces, while employing Han immigrants for essential roles, represents yet another chapter in the ongoing discrimination against the Uyghur population across various aspects of life during the reform period. The state advanced various policies to bolster Xinjiang's infrastructure, preparing it for the investments the government and private sector promised during the 1990s. Consequently, the Uyghur people felt that their social and economic circumstances had significantly improved during the reform period, especially when contrasted with earlier times like the Mao era, a period many Uyghurs remember fondly despite its oppressive hardships. Consequently, these policies set the region on a course for stable economic growth in the 1980s, but this was inadequate for the Uyghurs, as they often found themselves comparing their circumstances to the wealthier regions of eastern China in that period.

Focusing on studying the statistics of educational levels during the reform period firmly supports the Han claim that they are the incubator of education and the spearhead of the campaign to spread knowledge in Xinjiang and that the Uyghurs have an existential need for the Han to join them in the path of urbanization. Needless to say, education is the means through which human beings develop and gain knowledge and skills that are a necessity that individuals and groups need to survive and adapt in our difficult and changing world. The Chinese government assumed that education in Xinjiang was partly counterproductive; it enacted laws requiring Uyghur students to undergo compulsory education at the primary level, funded projects to improve educational conditions in Uyghur villages, and also allowed the establishment of schools teaching Uyghurs in their mother tongue for those who wanted to preserve the traditions. All these efforts were in vain after a handful of newly educated peasants showed up and started demanding independence, while others clung to their customs and traditions without paying attention to the path of knowledge that had been achieved during the 1980s. Living their lives in a manner similar to Han individuals, a group of the Uyghur intellectual class believed that their

independent state was on the verge of being achieved during the reform period, so they joined the ranks of the frustrated public that demanded independence.

Chart #2
Percentage of Minorities, Uyghur, and Han of Xinjiang's Total Population.

Year	All Minorities %	Uyghur %	Han %
1978	58.4	45.1	41.6
1980	58.6	44.9	41.4
1985	60.7	46.2	39.3
1990	62.4	47.4	37.6

Source: Copied from Table 2, A Survey of the Economic Situation in Xinjiang and its Role in the Twenty-first Century, Chaudhuri, Debasish, CHINA REPORT 41 : 1 (2005)

Image #9
A noodle maker in Kashgar in 1984.

<https://mceastbay.org/uighur-photos/>

Chapter 4

The Cultural Awakening in Xinjiang During Deng Xiaoping's Era

(1978-1989)

I Cultural landscape

1. A Glimpse into the Cultural Situation in Xinjiang before the Reform Era
2. The Cultural Awakening of the Uyghurs during the Reform Era
3. Poetry Composition during the Reform Period
4. Uyghur Musical Traditions, a Way of Life and a Tool for Resisting

Assimilation

II Linguistic landscape

1. An Overview of the Uyghur Language before the Reform Era
2. Linguistic Modifications in Xinjiang during the Reform Era

conclusion

Chapter 4: The Cultural Awakening in Xinjiang During Deng Xiaoping's Era (1978-1989)

I. Cultural landscape

1. A Glimpse into the Cultural Situation in Xinjiang before the Reform Era

Successive calls during the 2020s demanded that Europe close its international borders and return to isolation. This demand was duly manifested through the recent elections in Sweden and Italy¹¹², highlighting the lack of integration occurring when different peoples, races, and religions coalesced in Europe during the previous decades in the post-globalization phase¹¹³. This lack of societal integration has fomented assumptions that future wars and conflicts will be clashes of different cultures, known as

¹¹²In 2018, the Italian government withdrew from relief and rescue operations in the Mediterranean and denied commercial and non-governmental ships carrying rescued refugees on its shores (**Almustafa,2022,p.1077**). In 2022, the Brothers of Italy party, led by Giorgia Meloni, cruised to victory in the Italian legislative elections because of their ability to unite the extreme right in one alliance that emphasized preventing asylum, as it found listening ears among the Italian voters.

¹¹³Post-globalization is the era following globalization, when society becomes sufficiently globalized and the issue of the nation-state becomes of utmost importance (**Bagrova&Kruchinin,2020,p.8**).

culture wars¹¹⁴, in light of what is known as identity politics¹¹⁵. Fortunately enough, cultural friction wasn't the case for the majority of Xinjiang's history, as it became a sponge that absorbed the cultures of neighboring regions and the stories of their historical heroes. By reading stories copied from the stories of other cultures, "One Thousand and One Nights" from India and the heroics of "Alexander the Great" from Greece bulldozed their way to Xinjiang's local consciousness. As for the Persian legendary *Šāhnāme*¹¹⁶, it circulated in Xinjiang during the period that preceded its accession to China (**Thum,2014,p.17**).

In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, all writings that had been found in Xinjiang for two thousand years began to be neglected.

¹¹⁴Mainly a cultural conflict between two contradictory ideas or beliefs, but it has raged more in the West than in the rest of the world. British historian Dominic Sandbrook considers that the culture war is nothing but a dispute between two opposing sides of the educated elite, while journalist Matthew d'Ancona assumes that the culture war has been strengthened in the past twenty years due to the control of technology that enables and encourages people to gather and isolate themselves in cultural groups where they can opine on controversial cultural topics freely (**Anthony,2021**).

¹¹⁵A term coined with the aim of demanding freedom for a social group marginalized by the rest of society. The second half of the twentieth century witnessed the emergence of political movements that were closely linked to the idea that some people were subject to social oppression; for example, the second feminist movement and the movement for civil rights for African Americans in the United States during the first half of the 1960s (**Political-Encyclopedia,2021**). The cultural conflict in the West is ongoing, fueled by new ideas and events. Conservatives prioritize preserving European traditions, Judeo-Christian values, Enlightenment achievements, and the interests of indigenous people in a monocultural manner. Multiculturalism advocates for openness to all immigrant peoples and cultures, accepting all minorities and prioritizing individual freedom. This creates a dilemma: accept new knowledge-based ideas or preserve pre-modern customs (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.2**).

¹¹⁶An epic poem written by the Persian poet Ferdowsi in 1010. It was inspired by oral narratives related to Persian mythological history that preceded Islam and mixed with Islamic narratives, creating an Iranian identity coexisting between the Persian national component and the Islamic religious one (**Meri,2006,p.261**).

After the near-total Islamization of the region in the late eighteenth century, writings concerning local deities, the Buddhist Sutra, Manichaean teachings, and the Holy Bible, all in Sogdian, Tocharian, Sanskrit, and Chinese, lost their significance to Muslims following the Islamization that had initiated in the eleventh century (**Thum,2014,p.38**). Most of the efforts in the region during that period were directed towards Islamic literature, and it was recited as part of religious rituals or with the aim of entertaining people who could not read and write. Novels centered on early Islamic characters are categorized within the extensive realm of Persian-Turkish literature, and the *Šāhnāme*, along with its heroes¹¹⁷, continued to hold a leading place in Xinjiang, second to early Islamic figures (**Thum,2014,p.33**). For centuries, oral literature has been prevalent among the Uyghurs, encompassing a blend of myths, folk songs¹¹⁸, proverbs, and riddles that permeate all social classes. The costly process of duplicating rare books¹¹⁹ was exclusively for the educated minority who were proficient in Arabic and Persian. Until the

¹¹⁷One crucial hero of the *Šāhnāme* in the eyes of Xinjiang's populace was the legendary Iranian prince *Siyāvash*. He lived in Xinjiang and was buried in Khotan in southeastern Xinjiang. His shrine became a place of pilgrimage for the region's people in the past (**Thum,2014,p.19**).

¹¹⁸In the early twentieth century, Uyghur elites recited orally what was known as “resistance poetry” as a means of disseminating political ideas and encouraging confrontation with Chinese warlords. It was possible to transmit orally transmitted songs to subsequent generations and urge them to resist (**Finley,2013,p.173**).

¹¹⁹The book "*Tarīkh-i-Rāshidī*" was the oldest text written in Xinjiang, and it was inspired by the Persian historical tradition, with which the author wanted to document the history of the rulers of the eastern Chagatai dynasty that ruled the region during the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries (**Thum,2014,p.39**).

mid-nineteenth century, Uyghur literature mostly consisted of translations transmitted orally from the Quran and Hadiths (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.6**).

Before Xinjiang became part of China, its literary culture was closely linked to that of Central Asia, enabling any literate person to reproduce books for sale in the markets, displaying their creations alongside experts who transcribed their technical documents (**Thum,2014,p.76**). According to Ildikó Bellér-Hann, associate professor at the Department of Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies at the University of Copenhagen and a specialist in Turkic and Central Asian Studies, both oral and written cultures existed in Xinjiang side by side in a complementary relationship. This is clearly evident in the activity of storytellers and epics who recited their stories from written Persian sources (**Thum,2014,p.57**). Rian Thum, senior lecturer in East Asian history at the University of Manchester and a specialist in studies of Islam in China, discusses three types of literary collections that circulated in Xinjiang before it acceded to China, beginning with the treatise, a kind of text and handbook devoted to specific professions and crafts that shows how deeply historical practices are embedded in the lives of ordinary people

(Thum,2014,p.31). Secondly, manuscripts¹²⁰ read to audiences in diverse social settings are usually consumed in Xinjiang despite being imported from outside the Xinjiang environment and represent a story or narrative about historical events that occurred in the past **(Thum,2014,p.26,36)**.

Lastly, the *Tadhkira* serves as an encyclopedia that chronicles the lives of numerous heroes, saints, and poets from history, compiled by a single author and arranged in chronological order, primarily disseminated during the Sufi era of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries in Xinjiang

(Thum,2014,p.42). In preceding China's hegemony, the Uyghurs, or most of the ethnic minorities in Xinjiang, produced no kind of narrative fiction, magazines, or prose in its current form, and there were no basic standards for theater in Xinjiang, although some forms of dance and singing had previously existed **(Byler,2018,p.93)**. But even after the establishment of the PRC, writers and poets were forced to adopt the socialist realist style¹²¹ imposed on all literary and artistic works produced under Mao's regime **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.852)**. In general, the literature produced in China was

¹²⁰Thousands of manuscripts, documents, and texts written and copied in Xinjiang survived the turmoil of the last century while others slowly disintegrated in antique shops, tourist homes, and isolated state archives. China burned, confiscated, banned from publication, or destroyed those that did not survive **(Thum,2014,p.27)**.

¹²¹During the Great Leap Forward and the Cultural Revolution, state-imposed ideas of modernity dominated, leading to a politically charged Uyghur literature that disregarded local cultural practices. Customs were viewed as backward traditions conflicting with reason and hindering progress **(Steenberg,2021,p.175)**.

directed by the state according to a specific literary method in a unidirectional manner in order to achieve political gains through the concept of culture in the service of politics. Any literary achievement in Xinjiang during the Mao era showed the influence of totalitarianism driven from above. These creations were devoid of the essence of their local context and any signs of a distinct culture. They were rendered as uninspiring and abstract to support socialism, which favored equal literary production rather than the creativity that can emerge during more open political and cultural moments.

2. The Cultural Awakening of the Uyghurs during the Reform Era

It is acceptable to depict China as a diverse mosaic of ethnicities and nationalities that have assimilated into the modern Chinese state. It is also possible to view China as an enlightened cultural trailblazer that bears the cross of the “educational project” to motivate the minorities on the periphery in order to develop and modernize these areas and their inhabitants. The attempt to enforce cultural values from higher authorities provoked a

backlash from border communities, intensifying the cultural divisions rather than bridging the gap with the majority of Chinese society **(Finley,2013,p.8-9)**. After the ban on cultural discussions and dialogues was lifted during the 1980s, “re-exploring cultural values” spread in China **(Thwaites,2001,p.205)**. Research into the history, literature, and language of the Uyghurs was initiated by Uyghur intellectuals, who also began publishing new cultural literature, leading to the creation of the Xinjiang Academy of Social Sciences **(Tursun,2008,p.91)**. Article 38 of the Autonomous Regional Law issued in 1984 paved the way for this cultural restart, which encouraged the production of more ethnic minority cultures and the dissemination of their languages **(Millward,2007,p.277-278)**. It stated as follows: “Bodies in autonomous regions work to develop literature, art, journalism, publishing, radio broadcasting, the film and television industry, and other cultural projects independently and through the unique characteristics of those nationalities.”

(CongressionalExecutiveCommissionOnChina). While the 1980s were marked by cultural openness, the quest for liberation was secondary to China's primary focus on enhancing ethnic solidarity among its diverse

nationalities, with Han nationalism being central to the government's educational strategy **(Byler,2018,p.93)**.

Classifying ethnic groups and labeling their languages took place in the early 1950s with the establishment of the PRC, but for the comprehensive examination of the history and culture of the Uyghurs, this task waited until the reform era in the late 1970s and early 1980s **(Thum,2018,p.14)**. Uyghur literature flourished again during the reform period, which saw an explosion of publications in the Uyghur language **(Thum,2018,p.11)**. During that era, the Chinese regime began to revive culture throughout China after it was almost beaten to a pulp throughout the Cultural Revolution, during which Uyghur literature was produced in a manner consistent with the policies of that time **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.7)**. In addition, many writers were released from prison, and a new generation of them began to write a different type of literature than had been previously the norm. Literary production did not focus only on farmers and the countryside but also on city dwellers¹²² and intellectuals, as well as

¹²²Some city dwellers in Xinjiang became “cosmopolitans” during the reform period due to their preference for cultural products coming from Central Asia, as well as those from Turkey, the Middle East, and the Anglo-American realm, where they achieved an independent globalized identity that transcended national borders **(Finley,2013,p.13-14)**.

merchants and the nouveau riche who surfed the reform period wave (Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.7). One of the most important political events related to cultural openness was the impeachment of Deng Liqun¹²³ from his role as the party's propaganda officer in July 1985, followed by a philosophical discussion about the validity of Marx's¹²⁴ alienation theory, which posits the worker's separation from society within capitalist systems. The natural result of this reshuffling was the proliferation of new academic and professional associations, the revival of literary and artistic works, and the development of newspapers (Clarke,2007,p.66). In 1980, the Xinjiang People's Press published the first issue of a series called "Xinjiang Historical Materials." *Shinjang Tarikh Matiriyalliri*, a mixture of academic and propaganda historical articles that includes some Uyghur oral history (Thum,2014,p.193). Unsurprisingly, daily newspapers and academic journals released in Chinese were the most prevalent, whereas those published in Uyghur were somewhat fewer, yet they certainly cater to the

¹²³Chinese politician and theorist (1915-2015), known as "Little Deng" and seen as the fiercest conservative critic of Deng Xiaoping's reform policies. He also appeared as one of the biggest supporters of the Chinese state's campaign against the Uyghur separatist movement during the 2010s (Huang, 2014).

¹²⁴A German philosopher (1818-1883) who wrote "The Communist Manifesto" in 1848. He is credited with the Marxist ideology based on the transition of society from capitalism to socialism and then to communism through the revolution of the proletariat. Marx's ideas were a reaction to the failure of the revolutions of 1848, where he viewed that the suppression of those revolutions generated a world order based on the British slavery model, that is, through the control of the owners of the means of production in society, compatible with the Russian slavery model of owning serfs (Tansel,2016,p.19).

needs of the Uyghur population, who favor reading and writing in their native language. In contrast, print media didn't publish in the languages of many non-Uyghur minorities who didn't have access to readable content **(Dwyer,2005,p.45)**. The magazines did not contain only poems, prose, and humorous stories, but the matter went beyond the literary aspect, and many magazines were launched that presented academic articles and research during this period **(Dwyer,2005,p.45)**. In order to teach and educate the Uyghur individual and raise the amount of his knowledge and sciences, these magazines included a wide range of Uyghur writings: texts of ancient manuscripts recovered by scholars, modernist poetry, short stories, and plays by writers who studied in the Soviet Union **(Thum,2018,p.11)**. Novels started to appear among the Uyghurs in the beginning of the 1980s, and by the close of 1985, there were at least ten published. Most were historical in nature, crafted with engaging narratives that unfolded during the same period as the "Xinjiang Historical Materials" series, which helped them gain favor among the Uyghurs **(Thum,2014,p.193-194)**. It's important to recognize that these historical novels evoke a sense of nostalgia for the Uyghurs' glorious past, chronicling the valor of their heroes who were revered in a significant national context during that time, much like the

saints depicted in historical manuscripts from earlier centuries in Xinjiang **(Thum,2018,p.11)**. In total, the number of publications in Xinjiang during the first decade of the reform period, from 1978 to 1987, amounted to 12 periodicals, 19 novels, 62 short novels, and a large number of anthologies, stories, poetry, and plays in the Uyghur language **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.3)**. Compared to the almost complete “desertification” of literary production in Xinjiang in the early and mid-twentieth century, this abundance of cultural and literary works during the reform period is indeed an impressive achievement **(Dwyer,2005,p.46)**.

As part of its neo-colonial agenda, the Chinese government is advocating for the widespread use of the national language, Mandarin, in minority regions, which could lead to conflicts with local languages, potential shortages in literary production in these languages, and even crises in translation and copying capabilities. However, this did not happen in Xinjiang during the reform period. Rather, you see commercial bookstores, both public and private, offering a wide range of books and literary works in the contemporary Uyghur language, as well as offering translations of Chinese texts and famous foreign novels **(Cabras,2017)**. In this regard,

publishing houses benefited from government allocations to publish Uyghur literature over a wide range during the 1980s (Dwyer,2005,p.45). At that time, three major literary works pivotal to Uyghur culture that enriched human civilization were printed: a translation of “*Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk*” by *Mahmoud Kashgari* in the modern Uyghur language, “The Wisdom of Royal Glory” *Kutadgu Bilig*¹²⁵ by *Yusuf Khas Hajib*¹²⁶, and the interpretations of the ninth-century Buddhist manuscript “Encounters with Maitreya” *Maitreya Samiti*. Collectively, these works embody the crowning achievement of the Uyghurs' rich historical and cultural heritage: the corners of the Turkic-Muslim-Buddhist triangle (Dwyer,2005,p.46-47).

In the first years of the 1980s, some literary works appeared that dealt with the biographies of historical heroes among the Uyghurs, the most important of which was the novel “*Satuq Baghra Khan*¹²⁷” by *Saifuddin*

¹²⁵As the first literary publication in Uyghur after the rise of Islam, this book discusses the intricacies of governance and managing government matters, emphasizing the politics between the governor and the governed (Amin,2022,p.2). It is similar to Niccolò Machiavelli's *The Prince*, albeit framed within a Turkish-Persian perspective.

¹²⁶Turkish philosopher and writer (1019-1077), after finishing writing his most famous book, *The Wisdom of Royal Glory*, which took a year and a half, he was appointed as a minister in the Muslim Karakhanids state (Amin,2022,p.2). As part of the initiative to rejuvenate Uyghur culture in the 1980s, the writings of *Mahmoud Kashgari*, *Yusuf Khas Hajib*, and other distinguished authors and scholars known for their ties to ancient Uyghur culture were highlighted, marking them as pivotal figures in the context of Uyghur nationalism. The poet *Abduxaliq Uyghur* is a prominent example in this regard, as his poem “Awake” became a hymn for the Uyghur nationalist awakening in the late 1980s (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.851).

¹²⁷It was named in honor of Sultan *Satuq Baghra Khan* (924-955), a prominent figure mentioned in earlier manuscripts. He ruled the Karakhanids dynasty and was among the first to transition the state from Buddhism to

Azizi, a Uyghur official who was appointed the first head of the local people's authority in Xinjiang. Biographical novels revived the tradition of *Tadhkira* and preserved certain patterns of outdated historical behaviors practiced in Xinjiang in previous centuries, but in the 1980s, it was showcased in a new format suited for a more nationalistic world driven by print **(Thum,2014,p.198)**. Armed with imported concepts of modernity, the work of Uyghur scholars, who explored Uyghur folklore and ethnography¹²⁸, focused on the preservation of oral traditions, epic songs, and folk tales **(Bellér-Hann,2022,p.96-97)**. The study of Uyghur folklore by scholars during the reform period created a template for cultivating a comprehensive idea of customs that respects both the authority of the totalitarian regime and the modernist views that were gaining traction in Xinjiang at the time. Rather than being derived from writings by a specialized elite, these customs and traditions evolved from individual practices to broadly include the daily behaviors of most Uyghurs **(Steenberg,2021,p.177)**. It is worth looking at the work that revived “*Tadhkira*” during the print boom in the 1980s.

Islam, also playing a key role in the Islamization of the first Turkish dynasty in Central Asia. This shift occurred after he was moved by Muslim merchants who halted their trade upon hearing the call to prayer **(Millward,2007,p.51)**. Rather than considering this literary work to be an accurate historical narrative, it is better taken with a grain of salt, where it is described as a fictional biography extensively embellished with dialogue and fictional characters. This work achieved outstanding success among Uyghur readers when it was published in 1987 despite being written in the first years of the 1980s **(Thum,2014,p.164)**.

¹²⁸A descriptive study of human societies through systematic observation of society, the culture of the individual within it, and the total immersion of the researcher in society **(Britannica,n.d)**.

Starting in 1984, the Xinjiang Geographical Index Committee published a quarterly periodical called “Xinjiang *Tadhkira*” *Xinjiang Tǎzkirichilik*, in which local history and culture were documented through various approaches such as biographies, geography, the study of place names, and indexing of historical documents and their dissemination to the public **(Thum,2014,p.197)**. In 1984, *Bulaq* magazine published a poetic *Tadhkira* of the four imams in Islam, and in the following decades, a handful of them were published. However, a mismatch between the *Tadhkira* of the present and those of the past arose, where those of the present were not related to the functions for which this type of literary work was created **(Thum,2014,p.194)**. Some magazines have also appeared in Xinjiang aiming to reproduce the *Tadhkira*, the most important of which is “Ancient Book Research,” a scientific project issued through cooperation between some local private offices to collect, organize, and publish ancient books. This project contributed to preserving the local heritage by reconciling the Uyghur national goals with the political goals of the PRC in organizing and cataloging the cultural heritage of the Uyghur minority **(Thum,2014,p.195)**. By revising a collection of manuscripts from the state archives and

translating them into the contemporary Uyghur language, the Kashgar Press published four *Tadhkiras* in 1988 (**Thum,2014,p.196**).

The biography of *Satuq Baghra Khan* was not the exclusive production performed by *Saifuddin Azizi*. Rather, in 1983 he presented the play *Amannisaخان: tarixiy diramma*¹²⁹, in which he tried to introduce new elements in the life and biography of *Āmānnisā Khan* from what was previously known (**Anderson,2012,p.71**). But in showcasing a return to traditions and group values while abandoning state-imposed modernist methods, we must mention the *Dolan Yashliri* play by the Uyghur writer *Zordun Sabir*¹³⁰. Presented in October 1979, this play tells the tale of a young Uyghur man who, by turning away from Uyghur cultural traditions in favor of the modernist principles of Mao's Cultural Revolution, encounters various conflicts that remain unresolved until he "accepts the ways of his indigenous people and discovers the beauty in their traditions," as stated in the summary. A major theme in this play is the conflict between the Uyghur

¹²⁹A play script written by *Saifuddin Azizi* in 1983, in which the writer attempts to link the twelve *Muqams* in Uyghur music between what they are today and what they were in the past during the life of *Āmānnisā Khan* in Xinjiang in the middle of the sixteenth century (**Anderson,2012,p.71**).

¹³⁰Uyghur writer (1937-1998) from Ghulja, whose works rose to prominence during the reform period in China. He studied classical Uyghur literature at university before being arrested and deported to the countryside as part of the Anti-Rightist Campaign in the late 1950s. Still, he was rehabilitated in the late 1970s and resumed writing, gaining widespread fame among the Uyghur public (**Steenberg,2021,p.176**).

past and the Chinese present (**Steenberg,2021,p.176**). It is worth noting that the play was not banned during the reformist period because of its criticism of Mao's previous period, which came in the context of the reformists' campaign against Mao's radicalism after his death. However, if the writer had criticized the reformist faction, it would have been natural for the play to have been banned at that time. As long as they didn't criticize the current leadership led by Deng, the Uyghurs were allowed a certain window of freedom in their historical and cultural writings. Throughout the Dengist era, numerous Uyghur authors and intellectuals started to articulate their cultural views in forms that had been repressed before (**Thwaites,2001,p.205**).

The spike in literary production within the Uyghur community illustrates the conflicting dynamics at play, marked by urbanization, construction initiatives, and the shift toward a consumer-driven economy, counterbalanced by a revival of cultural traditions, religious practices, and a focus on preserving their historical identity. Many 1980s literary works and novels dealt with the rebellious movements in Xinjiang during the 1930s and 1940s. It is possible to conclude that the literary heritage of the early twentieth century played a vital role in shaping the modern Uyghur identity

(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.7). The irony here is that the Uyghur literary awakening and heritage restoration would not have been possible without the help of the Chinese regime during the reform era. Nevertheless, in spite of the Chinese government's attempts, the Uyghurs remained determined to express their cultural heritage as distinct from that of the Han people (Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.2,7). For this reason, the Chinese government concluded that the policy of cultural adaptation it followed in the 1980s with ethnic minorities, especially the Uyghurs in Xinjiang, was an agent of ethnic unrest and conflict rather than a solution (Finley,2013,p.422).

3. Poetry Composition during the Reform Period

During a lecture in 1932, T.S. Eliot¹³¹ pondered what poetry is and what its benefit is to humans. He stated the following: “We do not know what poetry is or what it does or should do.” Consecutively, the English poet W.H. Auden¹³² argued that it is not possible to separate poetry from the

¹³¹English-American poet (1888-1965), literary critic, playwright, and a leader of the modernist movement in poetry. From the 1920s to the late 1900s, Eliot significantly shaped Anglo-American culture, and his innovative approaches to diction and style breathed new life into English poetry (Gardner,Tate&Davies,2024).

¹³²English poet and writer (1907-1973). He achieved early fame in the 1930s as a champion of the left during the Great Depression. Some of his poems warned against totalitarian regimes and capitalist societies alike (Spears,2024).

social and political events that occur in the societies in which poetry is written (**Then&Now,2018**). In China, during the early reform period, the government began a campaign to rebuild what the Cultural Revolution had destroyed, not only in stone but in the souls of the people. Thus, government policies during this period resulted in one of the "golden ages" not only for Chinese culture in general but also in the poetry and prose of the Uyghur people (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.851**). With the consolidation of his power in 1978, Deng heralded a new era by calling for a new openness to intellectual and cultural exploration. In Xinjiang, the reform period saw Uyghur writers begin to produce novels and poetry, circulating previously banned topics and ideas with great caution (**Bovingdon,2004,p.31**). Barking up the wrong tree, Uyghur poets in the second part of the 1980s aimed at modern literary trends completely alien to their society (**Freeman,2016**). Most of the Uyghur poems that were written during this period were abstract due to the influence of Chinese poetry¹³³ and avant-garde Western styles¹³⁴ on the entire culture of this period (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.852**). But modernist poetry¹³⁵ among

¹³³Uyghur poetry borrowed some styles of Chinese poetry, which has been described as vague, abstract, and misty (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.852**).

¹³⁴In the late 1800s, the avant-garde movement emerged in Europe, challenging the restrictive and stifling conventions that its proponents viewed as oppressive within the official cultural landscape, more like "the belief that art should always be difficult and ahead of its time." (**Britannica,n.d**).

¹³⁵Bookstores and market stalls in Ürümqi offer a large number of poetry collections for sale, attesting to the vitality of modern Uyghur poetry (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.851**).

the Uyghurs did not find listening ears and was disdained by readers who denounced its immaturity, and within a decade its popularity stooped sharply **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.852)**. Through a Western flavor, the Chinese attempt to modernize Uyghur culture during the 1980s achieved two results: First, an adverse reaction from some Uyghurs, who doggedly anchored themselves in the oral traditions that they considered much more reliable than those written and preferred their continuity. The second result was an obvious growing feeling of marginalization among the Uyghurs, and those challenges during the reform period were reflected in the poems that dealt with the topics of faith, fears, and doubts that spread like wildfire in the Uyghur society at that time **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.848-849)**. The opposition to the Chinese regime could not find a voice through official channels to express its dissatisfaction during the reform period. Instead, it trickled through the folds of historical narratives, lyrics of popular songs, humor, stories, and oral traditions, where the latter, which had not undergone state censorship, represented the most accurate reflection of the range of freedoms available to the Uyghur people **(Finley,2013,p.173-174)**. To delve into Uyghur poetry composition, I will briefly shed light on the lives and some of the works of three Uyghur poets

who enriched the poetic bibliotheca of the Uyghurs during and after the reform period: *Adil Tuniyaz*, *Abdurehim Ötkür*, and *Tahir Hamut Izgil*.

The reform period witnessed some Uyghur literary anthologies, including “Samples of Classical Uyghur Literature,” published in 1981, and “A Collection of Remnants of Old Uyghur Books,” published in 1984. The first selected group dates back to the literature of the Islamic era and was presented in contemporary colloquial language and gained wide fame outside educated circles. The second group combined translations of inscriptions and produced texts in the Uyghur alphabet that predated Islam, and they all constituted the oldest sources of information about the Uyghur cultural heritage that were made available to the cultured Uyghur class **(Finley,2013,p.31)**. Religion was rarely the main theme in Uyghur poetry during the reformist period. There are only indirect mentions of Islam, suggesting that even though it is a vital part of Uyghur society, it does not serve as the main subject in the poetry produced by Uyghurs at the time **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.847)**. Religion has been marginalized in modern Uyghur poetry because the public categorizes their daily religious practices as “culture” or “tradition.” Intellectuals consider Uyghur nationalism to be

the most important feature of their identity, superseding Islam, while religious symbols in their poems are primarily an expression of national identity (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.847,848**). The exception was the Uyghur poet *Adil Tuniyaz*¹³⁶, whose poems depict Islam in a way that is closer to Sufism and also shed light on local customs that align with the term “traditional Islam” (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.853**). *Tuniyaz's* poetry centers on national identity, which includes Islam, and sketches the vulnerability of the Uyghurs (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.863**). The poet introduces himself as a Muslim Uyghur, which highlights the fact that religion and nationalism often cannot be separated among the Uyghurs (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.868**). Some of *Tuniyaz's* published poetry: “One Poet’s Secret” *Boytaq Shairning Mexpiyiti*, “The Street by the Sea” *Déngizdiki Kocha*, “Eyes Under the Veil” *Chumbeldiki Kóz*, and others (**Elkun,2021**). In the poem “Eyes Under the Veil,” the poet presents to the reader the modern idea that the veil or “*niqab*” was imported from India and not from the Middle East. The poet highlights the exotic nature of the veil and takes it out of the context of Islamic

¹³⁶Born in 1970 to the family of a schoolteacher in Kashgar Province, *Tuniyaz* graduated from the Faculty of Arts at Xinjiang University and then worked as a correspondent for the Xinjiang People's Radio Station. In 2017, as part of its "reeducation camps" approach to detaining large numbers of Uyghurs, the Chinese authorities arrested *Tuniyaz*, his wife *Nezire Muhammad Salih*, and their son *Imran*. Their detention stemmed from *Tuniyaz's* act of translating some hadiths of the Prophet from Arabic into Uyghur, a transgression that the Chinese regime finds intolerable (**Elkun,2021**).

fundamentalism. Thus, *Tuniyaz* is keen to show his interest in Islamic traditions without raising the government’s suspicions (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.855). In the poem “Enter the March” *Üchinchi Aygha Kirish*, *Tuniyaz* uses the term “green tribe¹³⁷” *Yéshil Qewm*, where the green color points to Islam, and this indicates the importance of religion in the national identity of the Uyghurs (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.863). It is worth noting that *Tuniyaz* shocked¹³⁸ the Uyghur community when he published his poem “The Land of the City of Kashgar” *Qeshqerdiki Yershari*, thanks to which he gained a prominent place in the conscience of the Uyghur people. Excerpts from the poem “The Land of the City of Kashgar” from line four to line eight:

The stars are soaring at dawn - يۇلتۇزلار پەرۋاز قىلار تاڭ سەھەردە

The seasons are flying in the trees - پەسىللەر پەرۋاز قىلار دەرەمخلىردە

¹³⁷It should be noted that the light blue color that appears on the flag of the East Turkestan Independence Movement is usually considered the national color of the Uyghurs, which the poet did not refer to. Rather, he used green in order not to provoke the government by displaying slogans indicating separatist sentiment (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.863).

¹³⁸By highlighting the feeling of pain and sadness in most of the poem’s verses, the poet describes in his poem “The Land of the City of Kashgar,” the city that was filled with the corpses of angels, as a wound that does not heal. It is reasonable to believe that the noticeable feeling of melancholy signifies more than just a political loss; Kashgar, once a city defined by the Uyghur culture, now finds itself stripped of its traditional identity under Chinese rule. Rather, it has become living evidence of the weakness of the state of the Uyghur nation, and thus represents a bleeding wound in the shared collective consciousness of the members of that nation (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.861-862).

The city is soaring in the legend - بۇ شەھەر پەرۋاز قىلار چۆچەكلەردە -

The people here - بۇ يەردىكى ئادەملە -

Soar in our hearts - پەرۋاز قىلار يۈرەكلەردە -

(Elkun,2021)

In contrast to *Adil Tuniyaz*, who embraced Islam as a crucial component of his identity, the poetry of *Tahir Hamut Izgil*¹³⁹ indicates that he does not identify as a religious person. Through his work, he criticized established Sufi orders that have been foundational to Uyghur traditions and certain contemporary religious practices (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.857). His poem “I Came to Know” *Men Bildim* is the best example of the poet’s journey to enlightenment on the personal, religious, and national levels. When he meets with a Sufi dervish in the poem, *Izgil* protests against the belief that the practices of religion are more important than the principles of religion and its moral virtues. He also criticizes most of those practices that he sees as irrational, especially the pilgrimage to sacred cemeteries and

¹³⁹He was born in Kashgar in 1969, and his poems began to appear in Xinjiang in the mid-eighties, that is, before he reached the age of twenty. The Uyghur poet *Tahir Hamut Izgil* is considered among the most skilled modernist poets of his generation (Freeman,2016). *Izgil's* work has been translated into Chinese, Turkish, and Japanese, and his poetry has appeared in English in Western publications and journals, including The New York Review of Books and Berkeley Poetry Review. Dodging a bullet, *Izgil* was more fortunate than his counterpart *Adil Tuniyaz*, who was arrested. By pretending to be sick, *Izgil* took refuge in the United States, and there he completed his writings about the persecution and torture that the Uyghurs were subjected to during the era of Xi Jinping (LibraryofCongress,n.d.).

shrines and seeking blessings from them (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.857**). But

among the Uyghurs, religion is what leads them out of the wilderness.

Religion symbolizes the rich historical heritage of the Uyghurs' past.

Because these people fearfully look towards the future, they continue, during

the reform period and all other periods, to view religious traditions as a

source for hope, pride, and comfort (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,p.848**).

Celebrated as the father of contemporary Uyghur poetry and an emblematic figure of Uyghur nationalism during the reform period, the late *Abdurehim Ötkür*¹⁴⁰ was a poet, writer, and historian noted for his allegorical political poetry and literary contributions (**Finley,2013,p.187**). Two novels by *Abdurehim Ötkür* dealt dramatically with the heroic events of the 1930s and 1940s in Xinjiang (**Kamalov,2021,p.12**), namely “Paths” *Iz* and “The Awakened Land” *Oyghanhan Zimin*. Published in 1988, “The Awakened Land” probably left the deepest impression among the Uyghur people and was printed in a total of more than sixty thousand copies, making it the most

¹⁴⁰Born in Kumul in eastern Xinjiang in 1923, *Ötkür* graduated from Xinjiang University in 1942 and then worked as an editor for the *Altay Geziti* newspaper until 1949. From 1949 until 1980, he worked as a translator in several government offices, where he knew the Chinese, Russian, and English languages well. In 1980, he worked as a researcher at the Institute of Literary Studies of the Academy of Philosophy and Social Sciences in Xinjiang (**UyghurAcademy,2013**). He spent decades in prison for his nationalist activities and died of cancer in 1995 (**Baranovitch,2003,p.739-740**). One year later, an estimated 10,000 Uyghurs attended *Ötkür's* funeral in Ürümqi, and the funeral that day halted traffic for four hours as mourners carried the coffin on their heads and paraded around the city (**Finley,2013,p.174**).

widely read novel in the Uyghur language (**Thum,2014,p.194**). The poem is written in Arabic script, and on the cover there is an image of a bright red sun, which clearly symbolizes the awakening phenomenon (**Baranovitch,2003,p.740**). As for his other poem, “Paths” *Iz*, it embodies the thorny journey of the Uyghur ancestors to a safe place in the region. Some contemporary interpretations of that poem link it to the Uyghur struggle to preserve their language and culture in the face of Chinese assimilation policies (**Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.866**). The state seemingly allowed the publication of *Ötkür's* books and poems because they believed his cultural works addressed the era before Xinjiang's incorporation into the PRC, illustrating the Uyghur resistance to nationalists rather than to the CCP. More realistically, the state's permission to publish *Ötkür's* poetry can be viewed as a compromise with the Uyghurs to show good faith or to avoid increasing tension with them, but for the Uyghurs, *Ötkür's* poetry was a cultural space that allowed them to resist the dominant Han culture (**Baranovitch,2003,p.740**). The new folk singers borrowed the poetry of *Ötkür* and other nationalist writers in the lyrics of their songs, and they were able to convey nationalist sentiments that bypassed the intellectual circles in the cities and headed directly to the heart of the country, that is, the rural

areas to be precise, and there they created an emotional resonance among the people. These songs were able to transcend social and geographical divisions among the Uyghur people, playing a unifying role in Uyghur society (Finley,2013,p.187). Among the popular songs that were borrowed from Ötkür's poems was the poem "The Encounter" *Uchrashqanda*, which was sung by the famous *dutar* musician and popular singer *Abdurehim Heyit*¹⁴¹. In this poem, the poet meets a girl and asks her questions. These questions carry symbolism for the Uyghur people, like the moon and star on the light blue flag of the East Turkestan Republic. "The Encounter" *Uchrashqanda* may be understood as an allegorical piece of literature, where the girl epitomizes the Xinjiang region, a territory that the Uyghurs sadly perceive as their state that didn't materialize. Excerpts from the poem "The Encounter" *Uchrashqanda* from line forty-five to line sixty:

I ask, and the shackles? - دېدىم بىلەن زۇكچۇ؟

She says, it is on my wrist- دېدى قولۇمدا -

I ask, are you afraid? - دېدىم قورقارمۇ سەن؟

¹⁴¹Uyghur musician, composer, and folk singer (1962-), born in Kashgar. He gained popularity among the Uyghurs because of his songs that convey a nationalist spirit, which led to his arrest in 2019. The Times magazine called him 'the Man of Constant Sorrow,' and he was greatly admired in Xinjiang intellectual circles (Finley,2013,p.188,210).

ئۇ دېدى ياق-ياق - She says, I am not

دېدىم نېچۈن قورقماسسەن؟ - I ask, why are you not afraid?

دېدى تەڭرىم بار - She says, I have my God

دېدىم يەنچۇ؟ - I ask, what else?

دېدى خەلقىم بار - She says, I have my people

دېدىم يەنە يوقمۇ؟ - I ask, what more?

دېدى روھىم بار - She says, I have my soul

دېدىم شۇكرانمۇ سەن؟ - I ask, are you content?

ئۇ دېدى ياق-ياق - She says, I am not

دېدىم ئىستەك نەدۇر؟ - I ask, what are your wishes

دېدى گۈلۈمدۇر - She says, they are my flower

دېدىم چېلىشماققا؟ - I ask, and to war?

دېدى يولۇمدۇر - She says, it is my path-

(UyghurCollective,2017)

It is natural that in periods of political persecution, Uyghurs' contemplation of their own history prompted a feeling of frustration and the realization that they not only lost their country but also their past. Through their verses, the poets criticize the Uyghur community for its loss of traditions and failure to preserve local culture, and this criticism from within is far more effective than criticism issued by a government alien to them **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.850,868)**. In fact, history is a favorite subject for Uyghur poets because it provides an opportunity to blow their own horn and evoke the Uyghur golden era when their community enjoyed independence **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.850)**. Unlike their illustrious past, where writers created works delving into collective identity, the Uyghur community now experiences ongoing persecution, a theme that is evident in contemporary Uyghur poetry **(Bovingdon,2004,p.31)**. Because of the concerning political conditions of the Uyghur community, poets utilize everlasting national symbols, such as the city of Kashgar, the mecca of Uyghur nationalism, to express their political discontent while portraying religion as a recurring scene from their childhood that represents nostalgia for the old ways **(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.868)**. As for the Chinese government, it employs a carrot-and-stick approach towards Uyghur poetry. On the one hand, the

government responds harshly, dishing out long prison sentences, and on the other hand, it encourages “politically correct” Uyghur literature and cultural activities according to its own standards (Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.868).

4. Uyghur Musical Traditions, a Way of Life and a Tool for Resisting Assimilation

Since previous centuries, singing and dancing at weddings, holidays, gatherings, storytelling sessions, and listening to music, known to the Uyghurs as *mäshräp*, have remained an essential part of their social lifestyle and part of their national identity (Finley,2013,p.186). For the Uyghurs, music serves as a vital means of social interaction and is fundamentally communal in nature. It involves collective activities such as melody, singing, dancing, and gathering around the performer, who typically sits within the group while playing their instrument. From 1951 onwards, the CCP officially acknowledged *Muqam* as part of the Central Asian musical heritage, deeming it a traditional art of the Uyghur people (Thum,2018,p.9). As for the *Muqam*, it is a group of musical notes that speak to the group’s

traditions, its usual patterns, and how it develops musically. Each musical *Muqam* has a different character that conveys the mood of the group that performs it (Finley,2013,p.207). East Turkestan is where the musical masterpiece known as “The Twelve *Muqam*¹⁴²” *On Ikki Muqam* originated. This work reflects the national epic of the Uyghurs and traces its roots back to the fifth and sixth centuries, with its evolution into its current form occurring between the tenth and twelfth centuries (JibekJolyTV,2020). The Twelve *Muqam* are regarded as the greatest artistic achievements of the Uyghurs, characterized by their beautiful melodies, poetry, stunning aesthetics, and captivating dances, which can only be classified as a true representation of Uyghur culture (Abu-Rahma,2017). Each of the twelve *Muqams* consists of three parts: the melodies or the rhythm of the instruments, the narrative poems, and the dances. With twenty to thirty songs and pieces of music, the presentation of the *Muqam* takes between one and two hours, while the presentation of all the *Muqams* usually takes more than twenty continuous hours (Abu-Rahma,2017).

¹⁴²The twelve Uyghur *Muqams* are as follows: *Rak Muqam*, *Čäbbiyat Muqam*, *Segah Muqam*, *Čahargah Muqam*, *Pänjigah Muqam*, *Özhal Muqam*, *Äjäm Muqam*, *Uššaq Muqam*, *Bayat Muqam*, *Nava Muqam*, *Mušavräk Muqam*, and *Iraq Muqam* (UyghurNovel,2016). It represents a kind of synthesis of the musical heritage of all the peoples of Central Asia, even if its performance is limited to the Uyghur people in particular (JibekJolyTV,2020).

As for the reform period, one of the cultural initiatives that the government encouraged was to revive the Uyghur musical *Muqam* and promote it as a unique artistic creation of the Uyghur people. Limiting the musical *Muqam* in general, and not just the twelve Uyghur *Muqams*, to the Uyghur people generated controversy between the Uyghur elites and the rest of the Central Asian elites, who all share in the synthesis of the *Muqam* throughout history, and each nationality has a unique form of the *Muqam* within its own culture **(Thwaites,2001,p.208)**. During the 1980s, when *Saifuddin Azizi* presented the play *Amannisaخان: tarixiy diramma* to the public, the claim that *Amannisaخان*¹⁴³ is the one who collected the twelve shrines and presented them in a single form to her people was emphasized throughout the play and thus became an icon of the Uyghur people who preserved their musical traditions and symbolized their cultural greatness **(Anderson,2012,p.83)**. During the same era, the Third Ethnic Minority Games were held in Xinjiang in 1986. This event was attended by only members of ethnic minorities, excluding members of the Han nationality. The event highlighted the folklore of various nationalities rather than focusing solely on competitive sports. Television footage depicted minority

¹⁴³A village girl married to the Sultan of Khanate Yarkand in the middle of the sixteenth century, she was credited with compiling and preserving the twelve Uyghur shrines **(Anderson,2012,p.73)**.

members playing traditional musical instruments and singing in scenic mountainous regions, showcasing a public atmosphere of openness and the emerging new spirit of that time **(Finley,2013,p.99)**. In addition to *Muqam* pieces, the People's Theater and Xinjiang Opera also provided music, plays, and artistic performances as forms of entertainment for the public in Xinjiang during that time **(Cabras,2017)**.

Benefiting from the cultural exchange between East and West, Uyghur art flourished due to the intersection of the Silk Roads in Xinjiang, or East Turkestan, to become today a historical witness to the interplay of Chinese, Indian, Arab-Islamic, and Greek cultures **(Abu-Rahma,2017)**. In Central Asia, as in the entire world, the development of the musical culture of one national group did not lead to the creation of musical instruments exclusive to that culture alone. Rather, it led to the creation of instruments that were in harmony with the rest of the musical cultures of neighboring and similar communities, so each culture imported one or more musical instruments from a neighboring one by changing the forms of its sound and modifying its decoration in accordance with its local traditions **(JibekJolyTV,2020)**. Among the instruments in East Turkestan, the *rawap* stands out: a distinctive

stringed instrument that the Uyghurs brought in from eastern Persia.

Although the *dutar*, a string instrument brought from Persia and Central Asia, is commonly played among the Uyghurs, the distinctions between it and the *rawap* are largely confined to local variations **(JibekJolyTV,2020)**.

In contrast to the more cosmopolitan *rawap*, the *dutar* is a more local Uyghur musical instrument that happens to be also used in Iran and Central Asia. The Uyghurs utilized the *dutar* as a political opposition tool that reflects the group's feelings in their cultural struggle against Chinese control over their local culture **(Finley,2013,p.232)**; they doubled the length of the neck of this musical instrument, embodying their long history in the region **(JibekJolyTV,2020)**.

The Uyghur cultural struggle is not limited to the musical instrument and what it embodies in the collective consciousness of the Uyghur people. Rather, the popular singer and vocalist himself is a national hero and a figure of societal importance to the Uyghurs. In this regard, I will talk about two Uyghur singers who performed musical works during the reform period in Xinjiang. The first artist, *Bahargul*, represents a Uyghur musician presented by the Chinese government to the Uyghur, Chinese, and international

audiences. As a Uyghur cultural vocalist, she embraces a fully Chinese framework and advocates for Xinjiang's recognition as a Chinese province rather than an autonomous region with a distinct musical heritage. On the other side of the coin, the star of *Abdurehim Heyit* shone during the reform period as a popular singer; with popular songs, he bulldozed his way into all segments of the Uyghur people. *Heyit* was among a group of artists who were able to zigzag between the twisted lines set by the state regarding musical and cultural production so that his songs would not be banned. At the same time, his music struck a nationalistic chord among the Uyghurs. *Bahargul*¹⁴⁴, a believer in the Chinese state project and its perception of the Uyghur culture, uses her musical skills and sweet voice to deliver the Chinese regime's message to Xinjiang and the world (**Finley,2013,p.176**). Some of the phrases that *Bahargul* used in her songs in which she promoted the Chinese regime's narrative in Xinjiang: "I have traveled many places, but 'our Xinjiang' is the most beautiful place," in which the singer evokes the Han migration to Xinjiang and their permanent ownership of the region. Although she wears traditional Uyghur dress, *Bahargul* sings in Mandarin

¹⁴⁴She was born in Khotän in southern Xinjiang, where she joined the regional cultural troupe in 1977 as a dancer, solo singer, and presenter before becoming what is known as a "soldier-musician", i.e., a singer who performs musical duties in the military sectors of the Xinjiang Military Region Cultural Troupe in 1980 (**Finley,2013,p.176**).

with a vocal model that is closer to Chinese than Uyghur and refers to the point of view of the Han settlers in the region rather than the point of view of her local counterparts **(Finley,2013,p.176-177)**. Furthermore, *Bahargul* was invaluable to the authorities by taking on the role of cultural ambassador for China, participating in a singing delegation of Xinjiang artists during a trip to Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates in 1986 aimed at "polishing the image" of the Chinese state among Muslim nations and portraying China as a nation where Muslims thrive culturally and socially **(Finley,2013,p.180)**. While her songs intoxicated the Han community, they barely resonated with her Uyghur supporters, who opposed the Chinese cultural agenda in their territory. Despite being a Uyghur singer, she went down like the Hindenburg with a fatal blow in the perception of the Uyghur people once she divorced her Uyghur husband and married a Han individual **(Finley,2013,p.177,179)**.

In the 1980s, the popularity of cassette tapes alongside increased urbanization and movement among Uyghurs led to an intensifying sense of nationalism. Fueled by folk songs that reflect Uyghur traditions and evoke nostalgic feelings, this sentiment began to permeate from the urban elite to

the rural populace **(Finley,2013,p.190)**. “The Xinjiang rooster,” the name given to the popular Uyghur singer *Abdurehim Heyit*¹⁴⁵, who has a sturdy, resonant voice, was considered by the New York Times magazine to be one of the most important contemporary Uyghur musicians **(Finley,2013,p.211)**. For *Heyit*, music is one of the most important ways to inherit Uyghur culture and traditions across generations. In his music, he shifts from portraying Uyghur culture through a Chinese lens, including the Chinese language, phonetics, and expressions that align with the government's propaganda, to creating songs that draw inspiration from the Twelve Uyghur *Muqams* **(Finley,2013,p.207)**. *Heyit* often refuses to appear in official state-sponsored shows supported by the regime that rejects his popular songs, which classifies them as “vocal nationalism” **(Finley,2013,p.207,232)**. He argues that certain cultures are more compatible and can coexist better with certain cultures than others, specifically highlighting the distinct characteristics of both Uyghur and Han cultures **(Finley,2013,p.208)**. Uyghurs view certain popular songs, which the Chinese government frowns upon, as a form of resistance against Han colonialism and a demand for either Xinjiang

¹⁴⁵Born in the city of Kashgar, the fulcrum of the Uyghur historical legacy, *Heyit* began learning the *dutar* in his sixth spring. At the age of seventeen, he enrolled in a state-run music school, where he was encouraged to sing in an Italian operatic style because of his broad voice. He found that type of music alien to him and to the authentic Uyghur vocals present in his childhood, so instead, he moved to the Beijing Central Song and Dance Ensemble in 1980, which deals with ethnic minority music **(Finley,2013,p.206)**.

independence or increased autonomy (**Baranovitch,2003,p.738**). This genre of music largely masked the internal rifts within the Uyghur community and sought to establish boundaries that would distinguish Uyghur culture from the dominant Han culture in Xinjiang. Confucius once said: “In changing traditions and customs, there is nothing better than music.” (**Finley,2013,p.174,230**).

Unlike the Uyghurs who live in shared housing with the Han in the cities and always complain about the smells of cooking and frying pork that waft through the corridors of the residences and seep into their homes, the Han people object to the sounds of music, singing, dancing, and playing musical instruments that come from the Uyghur homes, which upsets them. Han people usually show a relative aversion to music and stay away from parties and noise (**Finley,2013,p.99**). The Uyghurs are known to be more open to music than the Han, and they tend to be sociable and show more pride in the group, unlike the Han individuals who may be considered more individualistic, like the people of Western Europe. Weddings and circumcisions, as well as pilgrimage trips to shrines, all depend on musical

performance and dancing. Indeed, music and group singing are a pillar of social activity among the Uyghurs (**Finley,2013,p.98**).

Image #10

Uyghur *Muqam* in Xinjiang

Uyghur music includes songs, dances, folk, and classical music and is characterized by the diversity of content, choreography, and instruments used. The reformist leadership during the 1980s encouraged Uyghurs to sing and dance as part of cultural adaptation policies.

<https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/uyghur-muqam-of-xinjiang-00109>

II. Linguistic landscape

1. An Overview of the Uyghur Language before the Reform Era

To understand the state of the spoken and written languages in a given region, the researcher must rely on the linguistic policies followed and implemented by the authorities there. In this regard, the linguist Elena Shohamy, a professor and chair of the language education program at the School of Education at Tel Aviv University, indicates that linguistic policies are mechanisms developed to implement the goals of those in power to impose their hegemony through language (Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.2). China provides legal protections to every minority language, regardless of its prevalence and status within Chinese society. However, the major minority languages in the autonomous regions must share space and resources with the primary Chinese language, Mandarin, in areas of government administration, courts, education, and media where Mandarin takes the lion's share (Dwyer,2005,p.7). At the

beginning of the twenty-first century in Xinjiang, the world witnessed how China began focusing more on the Uyghur youth to master the Chinese language, Mandarin, in hopes of easing the social and political tensions that have plagued Xinjiang throughout the reform era
(Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.1).

Mandarin is one of several languages and dialects spoken in China that belong to the Sino-Tibetan language family¹⁴⁶, while the Uyghur language is a Turkic language spoken by the Uyghur people, and it may also be considered a lingua franca among non-Uyghur groups in Xinjiang
(Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.5). According to historical records, the Uyghurs used different linguistic scripts in their writings at times simultaneously during their two-thousand-year presence in Xinjiang¹⁴⁷.
Among these languages were the Sogdian, the Runic¹⁴⁸, and ancient Uyghur

¹⁴⁶Comprising more than 300 major languages and dialects spoken mostly in East Asia, the Sino-Tibetan language family, formerly known as Indochinese, is a group of languages that includes both Chinese and Tibeto-Burmese **(Egerod,n.d).**

¹⁴⁷With the adoption of the Manichaean religion by Uyghur intellectuals in 762, which is the religion of settled and commercial societies in Persia and some of Central Asia, they needed many books to help spread this religion among the Uyghur public in order to contribute to transforming the lifestyle from a nomadic life to a new settled lifestyle based on merchant culture. To achieve this goal, Uyghur intellectuals needed to change their ancient Uyghur language, which is based on an alphabet of 38 letters, into the Sogdian language, consisting of only 18 letters **(Cakan,2011,p.144).**

¹⁴⁸Runic writing appeared somewhat late in the history of writing and is clearly derived from one of the alphabets in the Mediterranean region, where scholars have tried to conclude that it is among the Greek or Latin alphabets. It is a writing system that was written from right to left and was used by the Germanic peoples in northern Europe, Britain,

writing (**Janbaz&Saleh&Duval,2006,p.1-2**), then the Arabic text after their gradual conversion to Islam, which spread in that region between the tenth and the fifteenth century (**Dwyer,2005,p.19**). As for contemporary Uyghurs, they speak three dialects: the Lop dialect in eastern Xinjiang, the Khotanese dialect in southern Xinjiang, and the Central dialect spoken in central and northern Xinjiang (**Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.5**). They also have a vibrant vocabulary of metaphors from Turkic¹⁴⁹, Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages, so citing borrowed words has become inevitable even for academic writings. This offended some Uyghur intellectuals, with one academic complaining: “It is as if Uyghur is not a real language in itself but rather a mixture of foreign words strung together.” (**Cabras,2017**). The Uyghur language is no longer the lingua franca in Xinjiang, especially during the twenty-first century. Rather, Mandarin¹⁵⁰ took its place as a

Scandinavia, and Iceland from about the third century AD to the sixteenth or seventeenth century AD (**Britannica,n.d**).

¹⁴⁹From the thirteenth century to the 1930s and 1940s of the twentieth century, the Uyghurs used the Chagatai language in their writings. This has resulted in a valuable and unique cultural heritage, along with a vast body of literature, throughout the long history of the Uyghur people (**Reheman&Guo,2019,p.175**). Among the most prominent cultural achievements of the Uyghurs during the 1930s and 1940s of the twentieth century was the “Cultural Promotion Association,” *mädäniy aqartish uyushmisi*, founded by some Uyghur intellectuals. This association contributed to the opening of the first Uyghur language school in Xinjiang and worked on translating many books into the Uyghur language. The current status of the Uyghur language is due in many respects to the activities of that association in the period preceding the annexation of Xinjiang by the PRC (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.5**).

¹⁵⁰What is referred to as Putonghua Chinese includes several linguistic varieties distributed according to the regions of China: Mandarin, Wu, Minbei, Minnan, Xiang, Gan, and Hakka, in addition to hundreds of other dialects. The only official language of China is Standard Chinese, also known as Standard Mandarin, which refers to both the spoken and written language that is more formal, while Putonghua refers only to the spoken language that serves as a lingua franca. However, Putonghua and Mandarin are intertwined sometimes (**Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.4**).

common language **(Finley,2013,p.29)**. Chinese vocabulary also seeped through the cracks of the Uyghur language over time. Thus, the impact of the language policies imposed by Beijing on Xinjiang has become evident **(Dwyer,2005,p.27)**.

The truth is that contempt for the languages of ethnic groups along China's borders has been a long-standing practice, and the significant changes China experienced in the twentieth century have merely added a new facade to the ongoing dehumanization of these minorities. In the past, members of linguistic minorities not integrated into the Chinese system were considered “barbarians¹⁵¹.” Today, these minority communities are seen as 'exotic' by the Han and need to be introduced to Chinese civilization in order to thrive, grow, and become part of the Han's advancing scientific journey **(Dwyer,2005,p.8)**, which is made possible through Beijing's strategic language policies. In this regard, Wang Lequan, a Communist Party official in Xinjiang during the 1990s and 2000s, stated thus: “The languages of national minorities do not contain many expressions that may be suitable for

¹⁵¹The word is derived from the Greek language and was used among the early Greeks to describe all foreigners. The word barbarians may have a phonetic origin that means what the Greeks heard, which is the phonetic phrase “*barbar*,” with which the Greeks classified languages other than their own. The word quickly took on a very negative meaning throughout history and became associated with the vices and brutal natures that the Greeks attributed to their foreign enemies **(Britannica,n.d)**.

modern science and technology, rendering education in these concepts impossible. This way, Uyghur youth will be no worse than their Han peers when they grow up.” **(Finley,2013,p.43)**. During the period from the Great Leap Forward until the end of the Cultural Revolution, China abandoned the linguistic equality stipulated in the 1954 Constitution¹⁵². Putonghua became the main language used in the new Chinese Republic during the Mao era, in which the languages of ethnic minorities were neglected **(Dwyer,2005,p.8)**.

The writing system was changed for the Uyghur language three times during the twentieth century, from 1956 to 1982. The numerous alterations to the writing system were a component of the "divide and rule" strategy orchestrated by the Chinese government to exert control over the Uyghur population, as no other language in China has experienced such a high frequency of alterations **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.5)**. First, the writing system changed from Arabic to Cyrillic, then to Latin, and eventually the modified Arabic script was adopted, which is still used **(Grose,2010,p.98)**. In the 1950s, the authorities came up with a new writing system in which the

¹⁵²The third paragraph of Article III of the 1954 Constitution stated the following: “All nationalities shall enjoy freedom to use and promote the development of their own spoken and written languages and to maintain or reform their own customs.” **(Diamant,2021,Suppl.p.10)**.

Uyghur language was written in the Cyrillic system instead of Arabic, which they saw as having major defects. This change was announced in the Xinjiang Daily newspaper in December 1956 **(Reheman&Guo,2019,p.175)**. After the Sino-Soviet split, the Latin alphabet was adopted instead of Cyrillic due to the desire of the Chinese Communist Party to absorb and control cultural differences **(Thum,2018,p.9)**, also erasing the specter of Soviet influence on Chinese internal politics. The frequent alterations in script writing during the 1950s, along with the transition to the Latin alphabet, separated an entire generation of Uyghurs from the literature that had been created in Arabic script, causing difficulties in written communication with both younger and older individuals educated in the Arabic script **(Dwyer,2005,p.21)**. The Uyghurs' concern about losing their cultural identity, symbolized by Arabic script, along with their anxiety over becoming isolated from other Turkic groups in Central Asia, contributed significantly to the unsuccessful adoption of the Latin writing system. Adding insult to injury, the constant change of texts and the state of linguistic and cultural chaos created by that process fatigued the Uyghurs and aggravated the failure of the Latin writing system. The assimilation and integration of Chinese culture, which started with the use of Latin texts in

the late 1950s, represented the primary concern that the Uyghurs had regarding the rapid process of "Sinicization" they feared would impact their language and culture **(Janbaz&Saleh&Duval,2006,p.3-4)**. Regarding the linguistic aspect of the relationship between the regime that claims to carry a civilizational project and the people it governs, Stevan Harrell, a professor and chair of the Department of Anthropology at the University of Washington who specializes in China's environmental history, concluded that the frontier peoples do not have a voice except when the regime grants it to them. The regime only allows this voice to be heard if it serves its interests and promotes the narrative it aims to sell **(Finley,2013,p.173)**.

2. Linguistic Modifications in Xinjiang during the Reform Era

Language is the basic tool of human communication, that's why it is imperative to achieve a "harmonious linguistic environment" in order to create a harmonious society. This is what the Chinese regime did, as linguistic policies were evaluated in order to fit within the framework of a nationally harmonious Chinese society **(Schluessel,2014,p.337)**. Despite lacking general acceptance, a system of writing that employed Chinese

phonetics with the Latin alphabet remained in use among Uyghurs from the 1960s into the early 1980s (**Reheman&Guo,2019,p.175**). On the flip side, the notion of reusing the prior Arabic script was discussed by intellectuals within the Uyghur community (**Finley,2013,p.137**). Following a comprehensive survey held by the regime in Xinjiang amid the reform era, it was determined that the Arabic alphabet writing system would be reinstated. The People's Government issued a notification in November 1982 so that the Uyghur language became widely written in the Arabic alphabet in both education, publishing, and other aspects (**Reheman&Guo,2019,p.175**). Nearly all Uyghurs, if not entirely, embraced the reintroduction of the adapted Arabic script, viewing it as a means to safeguard the Arabic language and their Islamic faith amid the increasing non-Muslim demographic in their area (**Finley,2013,p.31**). Some of them also copied ancient religious manuscripts written in Arabic script (**Thum,2018,p.10-11**). Concurrently, the large-scale focus of the central government on the Uyghur language in Xinjiang has strengthened the perception among other minority groups, like Kazakhs and Tajiks, that they are experiencing oppression due to the cultural supremacy of Uyghurs as advocated by the regime (**Aryodiguno,2021,p.73**).

During the reform era, some other linguistic amendments emerged from a series of adaptive policies in the form of laws enacted in the 1982 Constitution and the 1984 Regional Autonomy Law to establish the rights of linguistic minorities (**Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.5**). In this context, Article 4 of the 1982 Constitution contained the same phrase stipulated in Article 3 of the 1956 Constitution: “All nationalities shall enjoy the freedom to use and promote the development of their spoken and written languages and to maintain or reform their own customs.” (**Constitute,2018**). While in its 134th article, the 1956 Constitution stated the following: “In an area where persons of a particular national minority live in an integrated community or several nationalities, the hearings shall be conducted in the language or languages commonly used in the local area. Indictments, sentences, and notifications are written, according to actual needs, in the language or languages commonly used in the region.” (**Constitute,2018**). Analyzing the mentioned article through the lens of Xinjiang's linguistic context, the recent wave of Han migration has caused Putonghua to establish itself as the primary language, or lingua franca, in the area. Although there is an emphasis on promoting the education of minority languages in their local contexts, the constitution regards Putonghua as more crucial for fostering

national unity and advancing China's scientific and cultural achievements **(Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.5)**. The following is stated in Article 19 of the Constitution: “The State shall encourage the use of Putonghua at the national level.” **(Constitute,2018)**. The 1984 Regional Autonomy Law even stressed the need for Han in minority areas to learn the common language of that region, both written and spoken, in its effort to combat any aspect of Han chauvinism. Article 49 of the Regional Autonomy Law stipulates the following: “Han nationality cadres must learn the spoken and written languages of local minority nationalities, and minority nationality cadres must also learn the Chinese language used throughout China.” **(CongressionalExecutiveCommissionOnChina)**. The Chinese regime appears to have balanced more between minorities and the Han in its regional autonomy law, but it does not appear to be promoting a monolingual policy **(Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.5)**. It instead identifies the minority language as the main administrative language in the area predominantly inhabited by that minority group **(Millward,2007,p.278)**. Article 21 stipulates that: “The language of the nationality that exercises regional autonomy may be used as the main language in that region.” **(CongressionalExecutiveCommissionOnChina)**. However, in the end, the

level of literacy in Xinjiang did not rise when the Chinese regime reformed the writing system during the reform period. On the contrary, the illiterate population doubled due to the failure of many Uyghurs to adapt to the new Arabic system's writing rules, getting confused between this linguistic system and that, which naturally led to the spread of illiteracy **(Reheman&Guo,2019,p.176)**.

1984 was a watershed year for language policies in Xinjiang. In parallel with encouraging the Han to learn minority languages in minority areas, the CCP of Xinjiang voted to expand Mandarin language curricula at all levels of education to impose its teaching on Uyghur students and other minorities, commencing at the primary levels after previously starting at the middle stages **(Dwyer,2005,p.36)**. Thus, the second half of the 1980s witnessed the process of gradually restricting the cultural independence of the Uyghurs and the decline of the Uyghur language towards a low status in the public sphere **(Cabras,2017)**. Thus, Mandarin language education was widely expanded, unlike minority languages, which were limited, especially when minority schools and Chinese schools were merged together **(Dwyer,2005,p.40-41)**. In 1979, the Uyghur-Chinese Dictionary in Latin text

was published by Xinjiang University, followed by the issuance of several bilingual dictionaries useful for Uyghurs learning and speaking Chinese in Xinjiang (Dwyer,2005,p.47). Looking at the positive aspect, there is a greater selection of educational materials for major minority languages today, even though the Chinese language continues to dominate (Dwyer,2005,p.45). As for the artistic landscape, Uyghur and other minorities' artists and actors were asked to learn the Chinese language and act out their dramatic roles by speaking it. As for specific works for minority consumption, the actor had to speak the Chinese language, and then the text would be dubbed into the Uyghur or other minorities' language. It goes without saying that this arduous process was intended to ensure political control over the content of the text presented to the public (Finley,2013,p.32). All these practices ultimately led to accelerating the process of Sinicization of minority languages (Dwyer,2005,p.49). Taking a look from above, it is possible to consider that the 1980s heralded a multilingual society in China for a short period, but this pluralism remained prey to the dominance of the Chinese language in a society that by no means provided an equal linguistic division (Dwyer,2005,p.45). As a result, the language issue continued to be a "point of contention" because the number

of minority individuals learning Mandarin far exceeded the Han individuals learning minority languages in return **(Finley,2013,p.32)**.

Proficiency in Mandarin increases the likelihood of improving the social and economic attainment of the Uyghur minority in a market environment that emphasizes individual qualifications **(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.351)**, and favors smooth linguistic communication between employees of private companies **(Finley,2013,p.135)**. The individuals living in Xinjiang's urban centers are the most knowledgeable and fluent in Mandarin, unlike their rural counterparts who lack proficiency in the language, thereby hindering their opportunities for social and economic growth **(Finley,2013,p.xix)**. The elevated illiteracy levels in the south also play a role in establishing the northern version of the Uyghur language, which is less affected by illiteracy, as the standard or official form of the language **(Dwyer,2005,p.27)**. The predominance of the Han ethnicity in northern Xinjiang results in their apathy towards acquiring the Uyghur language, particularly in areas where Han influence is significant. In contrast, Han cadres in the south must study the Uyghur language, showcasing the language's persistent growth among the Uyghur community

in that area **(Han,2010,p.251)**. In 1984, which is the heart of the reform period, the largest urban schools to the most marginalized rural primary schools were asked to modify their curricula and use Putonghua as the main language of education, which appeared as an imposition of that language on Uyghur students who had no choice in the matter. In addition, Uyghur teachers who lacked proficiency in the Putonghua language have had to take intensive courses in order to catch up with the new curriculum imposed **(Hann,2014,p.196)**. *Minkaohan* students faced challenges in learning about their cultural heritage due to the scarcity of resources in their mother tongue in their surroundings and schools, indicating that the regime may have sought to weaken Uyghurs' pride in their linguistic and historical identity **(Finley,2013,p.35)**.

Arienne M. Dwyer, a professor of linguistic anthropology and co-director of the Institute for Digital Research in the Humanities at the University of Kansas, concludes that China's bilingual policy in Xinjiang has encouraged the same pattern of "group polarization" that China originally wanted to demolish in the minds of the Uyghur people who opposed school integration processes as "linguistic genocide" **(Finley,2013,p.43)**. However,

learning the Chinese language is supported not only by the government but also by Uyghur families who prefer to send their children to schools that offer better education in the Chinese language (**Cabras,2017**), resulting in a violent reaction in the Uyghur community (**Han,2010,p.251**). Conversely, Chinese researchers argue that the reluctance of many Uyghurs to learn the Chinese language and to work in predominantly Han-majority environments, where many employers and employees hold advanced degrees and often harbor biases against Uyghurs, significantly contributes to the racial disparity in Xinjiang (**Cappelletti,2020,p.94**). On the issue of Chinese language dominance in Xinjiang, Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, posits that the Chinese regime has slowly but systematically succeeded in institutionalizing the Chinese language in multiple areas of education, employment, and administration in Xinjiang. Finley also considers that the Chinese regime's linguistic policy in Xinjiang has left an income gap between the Uyghurs and the Han in the region. Suppose the Uyghur individual desires progress and development. In that case, he is first obligated to master the Chinese language, which compounds an arduous struggle on the personal level for the Uyghur individual. Moreover, the Han

group tends to regard the Uyghur language as having no scientific or practical value, instead labeling it as having limited relevance in the urban environments they dominate and where they work **(Finley,2013,p.409)**.

It is rare for a country or regime to implement such a large number of linguistic reforms in such a short period of time over a specific geographical area defined by a number of mixed nationalities. Although linguistic planning is something that seems very natural in general, it has had a far-reaching impact on the culture of the Uyghur people, their education, their economy, their art, and the pace of modernization taking place in their society **(Reheman&Guo,2019,p.175)**. Teaching Mandarin in Xinjiang was not solely about promoting the Han civilizational agenda for the region; it was also connected by CCP cadres to the fight against the threefold ideology present in Xinjiang, in their view, which is: extremism - separatism - and terrorism¹⁵³. Chinese linguistic policies promoted Putonghua as the lingua franca in regions of China. It must also be considered as the language of science and progress, and its systematic use is necessary for socio-cultural

¹⁵³*Nur Bekri*, president of the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region from 2008 to 2014, raised eyebrows in a June 2009 speech on the introduction of bilingual education in Xinjiang when he claimed that teaching Mandarin to Uyghur children could "help fight terrorism." "Terrorists from neighboring countries mainly target Uyghurs who are isolated from the Han community because they cannot speak Mandarin," he stressed **(Arya,2010,p.196)**.

cohesion and mandatory for the unity of “Chinese identity”

(Han&Cassels-Johnson,2020,p.11). In this regard, the Uyghur writer

*Setiwaldi Kerim*¹⁵⁴ narrates a symbolic story linking the loss of the ability to speak an individual's language to the progress of nations through his own experience with brain damage that caused him to lose the ability to speak.

He draws a clear parallel between the individual and the nation, that is, between the possibility of regaining his ability to speak personally and the Uyghur path in searching for freedom and emancipation from the Chinese regime, which will only happen when the Uyghurs find their voice and remember how to speak their mother tongue, as he puts it

(Schluessel,2014,p.339).

¹⁵⁴A Uyghur professor and writer who worked to promote Uyghur literature during his work in Xinjiang. He also participated in a project to develop a textbook on Uyghur literature for both middle and high school students in Xinjiang. This matter was enough for him to be arrested, among a convoy of Uyghur professors and teachers, in 2017 by the Chinese regime and sentenced to 19 years in prison **(Hoshur,2023)**.

Image #11

"Xinjiang rooster"—a photo of popular singer *Abdurehim Heyit* singing and playing the *dutar* while wearing the traditional Uyghur *doppa* hat in collective Uyghur singing sessions during the 1980s, which witnessed a cultural integration of Uyghur music.

<https://thechinaproject.com/2022/05/27/uyghur-voices-in-istanbul/>

Image #12

A photo of some Uyghur students who participated in student protests in Ürümqi on June 15th, 1988, against the discriminatory education policies, birth control policies, and the effects of nuclear testing in the Lop Nur region.

<https://www.uyghurcongress.org/en/press-release-wuc-commemorates-1988-uyghur-student-protest/>

Conclusion of Chapter 4

By taking a basic look at the progression of historical literature in Xinjiang, we can observe that it is embedded in Islamic civilization¹⁵⁵ and closely related to the body of Persian-Turkish literature. Before becoming part of China, the area saw considerable literary endeavors, yet these were limited to certain genres introduced from the Islamic regions and lacked the diversity of genres that the Uyghurs had not previously experienced. Varying from the Uyghur literary production that spread during the Maoist era previously, Uyghur literary production in the reform era of the 1980s was allowed to be an embodiment of the Uyghur need, feeling, and will to return to local traditions and societal customs. When a minority that does not view itself as part of the broader state project alongside other minorities is permitted to create literary works on a larger scale than before, it is only natural for them to collectively emphasize their traditions and heritage. This stems from a desire to protect their cultural values, which

¹⁵⁵Arab and Persian historians didn't pay attention to ancient cultures before the entry of Islam into Xinjiang; even records written in previous languages were destroyed once Muslims invaded the Tarim Basin in Xinjiang (Sinor,Shimin&Kychanov,1999,p.206).

they believe are at risk of being eroded by new influences imposed by the state and the surrounding Han community in Xinjiang.

In fact, through my extensive research on the cultural aspects of Uyghur life, I cannot help but notice in their music a glow and enthusiasm for dancing and folk singing in organized groups such that the individual disappears and dissolves in the group that appears in the form of an “integrated unit.” After repeatedly watching videos showcasing the twelve Uyghur *Muqams*, I’ve come to a personal impression—one that deviates from scientific analysis—that the Uyghur people’s deep passion for singing, dancing, being happy, and living in the moment may not just be a cultural phenomenon related to “glorifying life” but could also be intrinsically tied to their biological makeup. While this type of cultural expression is generally seen as a representation of simplicity in life, I perceive it among the Uyghurs as more indicative of the “floating on the surface” traits associated with both individuals and groups and an integral part of their “Uyghurness.” These people’s Uyghurness is their way of collectively slaying their childhood dragon: resisting the Han culture imposed on them.

In drawing the points concerned with linguistic policies in Xinjiang, it is possible to say that the reform period in the 1980s was adaptive and absorptive at the same time. The Chinese regime allowed the Uyghurs to use the Arabic language in their written system as they wanted, but their language will always remain in danger after the regime later forced the Uyghurs to learn the Putonghua language at primary educational stages. During the concurrent 2020s, the Chinese regime adamantly rejects the reintroduction of the Latin writing system to the Uyghur language, despite some demands to abandon the Arabic script due to the complications that may arise with it during the use of technology tools and social media apps and the switch to the Latin alphabet, which may help the Uyghurs aptly brave the requirements of the markets in China and abroad with the English language that controls most aspects of globalization, including work, study, trade, and communication. Evidently, China is presenting an image to the world today in which all aspects of Uyghur culture and identity are deemed outdated and reactionary, particularly their language written in Arabic script, which they assert is inadequate for scientific and practical progress. China reflects this message back to the Uyghurs, indicating

that to develop like other ethnic minorities, they must accept the Sinicization imposed upon them and regard Putonghua as their main language, which means "parting ways" with their native language.

Image #13

The Third Ethnic Minority Games were held from August 10 to 17, 1986, in Ürümqi, the capital of Xinjiang. This 9-day event attracted 777 athletes from 55 ethnic minority groups in China and included a total of 7 competitions and 115 performances. This was the first time the event included the use of a badge, flag, and crest.

<https://musculoskeletalkey.com/a-history-of-the-national-traditional-games-of-ethnic-minorities-of-china-1953-2011/>

Chapter 5

Sinicization Programs, Han Condescending view of the Uyghurs, and Preferential Policies in Xinjiang

I. Civilizational Projects: “Sinicization Programs”

1. The Evolution of the Chinese Centralization Concept from the Late Qing Dynasty Until the Establishment of the PRC

2. Sinicization Programs during the PRC Era: A Model of Ethnic Supremacy with the Aim of Assimilation

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Chapter 5: Sinicization Programs, Han Condescending view of the Uyghurs, and Preferential Policies in Xinjiang

I. Civilizational Projects: “Sinicization Programs”

1. The Evolution of the Chinese Centralization Concept from the Late Qing Dynasty Until the Establishment of the PRC

From the 1895 Treaty of Shimonoseki¹⁵⁶ to the 1901 Boxer Protocol¹⁵⁷
and the 1931 Japanese occupation¹⁵⁸ of Manchuria, leading up to the 1937
Nanjing atrocities of the Second Sino-Japanese War¹⁵⁹, each of these treaties

¹⁵⁶The inaugural humiliating treaties for China, under which China ended its war with Japan in 1894-1895. China relinquished its control over Korea and acknowledged its autonomy, while also ceding the island of Taiwan, or Formosa, to Japan and was compelled to pay significant reparations to Japan (**Britannica,2024**).

¹⁵⁷A treaty imposed by the major powers on China after the elimination of the Boxer movement in 1901. Under pressure, China submitted an official apology to Japan and Germany for the killing of their diplomats and was obligated to send Chinese students to study at Western institutions, especially in the U.S. and the U.K. (**Al-Quzi&Hallak,2001,p.98**).

¹⁵⁸During an official reception in Tokyo in October 1978, Emperor Hirohito apologized to Deng for the Japanese army's war atrocities in China. Deng's visit to Japan marked the first time a high-ranking Chinese politician had met a Japanese emperor in 2,500 years (**Vogel,2012**).

¹⁵⁹During and after its occupation of Nanjing during the 1937 war, the Japanese army committed brutal atrocities, killing thousands of Chinese civilians and surrendered soldiers, resulting in more than one hundred thousand deaths. This massacre was called the "Rape of Nanking" (**Britannica,2024**).

and events was merely one of the chapters of a cruel national tragedy that China was subjected to during what was known and stored in the common Chinese national consciousness as the “Century of Humiliation¹⁶⁰.” A century that rendered China's intellectuals victims of the inferiority complex that was fueled by all these mentioned events and many more (Gernet,1996,p.646). In coping with the era of humiliation, China developed the “Han Supremacy” as a defense mechanism. China attributes this principle, or this biased assumption, to an ancient history in which China, through most of the empires it embodied, was a dominant superpower that controlled the world with its commercial surplus and creative inventions that accelerated the global knowledge train. Alessandra Cappelletti, an associate professor at the Department of International Relations at Xi’an Jiaotong Liverpool University who specializes in sinology, posits that through the bias of the surplus power of the central people or national group in the state, all the rest of the usually weak marginal nationalities are subjugated. Cappelletti suggests that combining this with resource

¹⁶⁰The “Century of Humiliation” starts with the First Opium War between China and Britain in 1839. The massive invasion of alien traditions into Chinese culture was only one part of the takeover of China, which had an advantage in trade relations with Western countries, which made it vulnerable to Western ambitions. Through witnessing many wars and revolutions since that year, such as the Second Opium War, the Taiping Rebellion, the Boxer War, the 1911 Revolution, the Japanese invasion, and the Chinese Civil War, China's sense of humiliation did not end until the establishment of the PRC in 1949 (Gernet,1996,p.646).

exploitation in marginalized ethnic areas while preventing social disturbances and the predominance of one ethnicity could justifiably indicate that “internal colonialism” is indeed a reality in this society **(Cappelletti,2020,p.18)**. In China, the superiority of Han culture is firmly established in the Chinese worldview, and Han leaders have long recognized China's absorptive capacity. In a similar way, the sage Mencius¹⁶¹ commented, “I have heard of someone using the methods of our great land to change barbarians, but I have never heard of any change being achieved by barbarians.” **(Moneyhon,2003,p.505)**. This matter can be considered one of the first indications in the Chinese heritage of the concept of modification programs, and in the case of China, it is translated into “Chinese programs.”

Uradyn Bulag, an associate professor of anthropology at Hunter College and the Graduate Center of the City University of New York, has identified China as a mosaic of many regional nationalities whose historical homelands were merged into a unified Chinese state. These political entities were domesticated from sovereign states on China's outskirts to ruled minorities within it **(Finley,2013,p.8)**. And to complete the merging process,

¹⁶¹Chinese philosopher (371 BC-289 BC) who is considered the second sage of the Confucian tradition. He expanded on Confucian thought by pointing out that human nature is inherently good **(Moneyhon,2003,p.505)**.

the Chinese narrative claimed that these nationalities were merely branches dangling from the Chinese nationality tree. This concept was the cornerstone of threading a Chinese narrative based on the assimilation of these homelands and their transformation into Chinese nationality, which is cemented by a previously mentioned claim made by Wang Enmao about the branching of Uyghur nationality from the tree of Chinese nationality instead of Turkish. In the years leading up to the founding of the PRC, the CCP presented a different kind of rhetoric based on unifying the Chinese nation by expanding its family¹⁶² (**Moneyhon,2003,p.510**). The unique heritage of the Uyghurs has been reshaped to fit within the framework of Chinese history, losing its status as a cohesive and independent entity, and now appears as a small branch of the larger Chinese nation (**Dwyer,2005,p.21**). Regardless of whether the Uyghurs call for more Chinese assimilation, increased autonomy, or Xinjiang independence, almost no one is satisfied with the status quo, and their resistance to the mechanisms of the Chinese narrative remains alive (**Moneyhon,2004,p.16**).

¹⁶²Thus, China's nationalist policies were aligned with Stalin's policies in this direction. After identifying the national minorities and classifying their characteristics and differences, it sought to integrate them into one large family under the umbrella of Chinese nationality (**Moneyhon,2004,p.6**).

The Sinicization process emerged early in the period preceding the twentieth century; it was neither the product of the philosophy of the CCP nor the fruit of Mao's Socialist Thought¹⁶³ or Deng's reform and openness. The concept of race in China is primarily shaped by Han centralism, referred to as Sinocentrism, which finds its roots in historical imperial ideologies¹⁶⁴ (**Kamalov,2021,p.3**). It is possible to frame the stereotypes developed by the Han people to describe the Uyghur people with reference to the concept of Sinocentrism (**Finley,2013,p.84**). The Chinese viewed their interactions with frontier peoples as instrumental in evolving them from “raw” and uneducated groups into fully civilized societies; as part of the process of developing Muslim subjects in China, the Qing dynasty elites attempted to force them to accept the Confucian principle of “filial piety,” which they monopolized as a special Confucian ideal (**Finley,2013,p.84-85**). In the late nineteenth century, the issue took a more violent turn, as Han military leaders began to impose the violent assimilation of Muslims, including the

¹⁶³Maoism differs from Marxism-Leninism in that the former focuses on peasants, unlike the latter, which focuses on urban workers in order to lead the communist revolution in society. Mao instilled in the Chinese peasants a proletarian consciousness and made their physical strength alone sufficient for revolution. While there wasn't a significant Chinese working class compared to the numerous peasants, Mao revolutionized the peasant population and converted them into a proletariat by the 1940s (**Britannica,n.d.**).

¹⁶⁴The followers of ancient Confucianism sought to classify peoples as closer to the center, that is, the Chinese imperial court in the interior, or more distant from it based on the amount of culture that those peoples could display. Culture was defined according to Confucian standards and terminology (**Finley,2013,p.84**). It must also be mentioned that on a daily basis, Muslims were described using disrespectful terms, and Islam was called the small religion, in contrast to Confucianism, which was known as the great religion (**Finley,2013,p.85**).

Uyghurs, into Han culture. In the late Qing dynasty, Xinjiang came under the influence of Han dominance, and the Muslims were Sinicized alongside a process that continued throughout the twentieth century **(Tynen,2021,p.4-5)**.

Copying the Confucian beliefs that Chinese nationalists had wrested from the Chinese Empire's clutches, the Chinese Republic's revolutionary ideals called for a progressive approach to the concept of national and racial equality. To show this alleged equality, the five-color flag was initially adopted as the national flag of the Republic of China from 1912 until 1928. This flag included five horizontal lines representing a union of five races **(Finley,2013,p.85)**, where the white color represented the Muslims in China. Despite being politically different, Sun Yat-sen, Chiang Kai-shek, and Mao Zedong all shared a similar stance on the principle of Chinese centralism **(Hyer,2005,p.19)**. The first, Sun Yat-sen¹⁶⁵, believed that China was a unified nation inhabited by one people, and with time, the various races in China would dissolve and merge into one Chinese nation **(Hyer,2005,p.20)**.

¹⁶⁵At the dawn of the twentieth century, the weakness of the longing for a unified homeland in China, alongside strong loyalties to family, clan, and nationalism, concerned Sun Yat-sen, a pivotal figure in Chinese nationalism. His ideas and rhetoric resonated within the foundational beliefs and doctrines of the CCP **(Moneyhon,2003,p.510-511)**.

The second leader, Chiang Kai-shek¹⁶⁶, who identified with the ideas of his predecessor Sun, insisted that China absorb all of its historical regions and not give up any of those lands. He considered the following: “The Chinese nation lived and thrived on the river basins. No region can be separated from that nation, and therefore no region can be independent in its own right.” **(Hyer,2005,p.20)**. The latter, Mao Zedong, approached the situation differently during the period that preceded the establishment of the PRC, in which he needed the support of ethnic minorities. He supported the right to self-determination for ethnic minorities and the idea of forming a union between the minorities and the Han nationality, but on a voluntary basis for both parties. Rather, he went further and granted Chinese Muslims the right to establish their own homeland **(Hyer,2005,p.22-23)**.

However, once the CCP came to power, the falsity of these allegations became apparent, and the party leadership abandoned previous calls for the right to self-determination for minorities and instead repeated the overused slogan that “China is a large family composed of all nationalities”

¹⁶⁶Military commander and Chinese nationalist leader (1887-1975). He headed the Kuomintang government from 1928 to 1949 and was then exiled to Taiwan to rule it until his death. Before Japan invaded China, he tried to unify China by fighting warlords in the north and communists in the cities **(Britannica,2024)**.

(Hyer,2005,p.23). “All nationalities within the borders of the PRC are equal. They must establish Chinese unity so that the state becomes a fraternal family composed of all its nationalities.” In his speech during the founding of the republic, Mao tried to instill the idea that the “big brother,” that is, the Han nationality represented by the state, had arrived to help its “younger brothers,” that is, the ethnic minorities, develop their languages, religious beliefs, and traditions **(Moneyhon,2003,p.511)**. Therefore, the PRC perceived Sinicization, which sought to condense and unify the histories and identities of ethnic nationalities under the framework of Han culture, as vital for establishing national cohesion and safeguarding national security within China **(Dwyer,2005,p.21)**. It is worth noting that the Sinicization process has paid off in some areas and failed in others; China has succeeded in Sinicizing both Manchuria and Inner Mongolia, but the process backfired in Tibet and Xinjiang. This led China to increase its control and adjust its policies, officially promoting extreme nationalism as a way to assert state legitimacy over those regions **(Arya,2010,p.198)**.

2. Sinicization Programs during the PRC Era: A Model of Ethnic Supremacy with the Aim of Assimilation

During the PRC period, the idea of national equality was fundamentally undermined by the theory of the "Five Stages of Chinese History," in which the Han ranked highest on the scale of development and growth among China's ethnicities. This theory is taught as a scientific fact in China's national school curriculum, which indicates that Han bias against minorities is still ingrained in the mentality of China's national policymakers **(Finley,2013,p.86)**. The "Five Stages of Chinese History" was not the only new addition to these curricula during the period of the People's Republic. Rather, the matter went beyond that, and Han historians intervened in the histories of minorities and modified them to suit the official Chinese narrative. Moreover, the link between the Uyghurs and the neighboring Turkic world was rejected by Chinese historians, who ultimately came to accept—though with hesitation—that today's Uyghurs may also be descendants of the ancient Uyghurs alongside other ethnicities **(Kamalov,2021,p.7)**. After becoming part of the People's Republic, theorists have replicated historical examples from the Han and Tang periods to

demonstrate the treatment of Xinjiang in contemporary times. This indicates that Xinjiang has always been an integral part of a cohesive Chinese nation that has existed for millennia **(Thum,2014,p.4)**. During Mao's socialist regime and Deng's reform period, the Uyghurs in China saw substantial shifts in their traditional lifestyles; some accepted these modern developments, whereas others regarded them as an organized endeavor to assimilate their culture into Chinese society **(Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.14)**. The key aspect of these changes was the effort to Sinicize Uyghur history, portraying them as integral components of imperial China, which was supported by certain books and research during the reform era. One notable book among these is by the Han academic Feng Jiasheng, published in 1981. This work serves as a relevant illustration of Sinicization efforts, detailing how the Qing dynasty regarded the integration of the Xinjiang region into imperial China's territories during the eighteenth century as a natural progression, avoiding words like "annexation," "invasion," or "occupation" **(Kamalov,2021,p.8)**. Accordingly, China's conquests are depicted in Chinese literature as titanic efforts by Chinese emperors to unify the “Celestial Empire¹⁶⁷” and retrieve its subjects under the pretext of preserving

¹⁶⁷In ancient times, imperial China was called the Celestial Empire, according to which it was the center of the universe and all other countries and peoples were subjects of the Son of Heaven, the Emperor **(Kamalov,2021,p.8)**.

the global order (**Kamalov,2021,p.8**). On the other hand, the tools of progress imposed by the Chinese state appear as means of imposing Chinese hegemony, and as such, the literature of the 1980s urging modernization is seen as detrimental to efforts made locally to preserve the culture and heritage of the indigenous Uyghur people (**Zelcer-Lavid,2018,p.14**).

The Chinese government's strict regulation of foreign researchers in Xinjiang has directed research attention towards Ürümqi, the capital primarily inhabited by Han people, leaving south Xinjiang, home to most Uyghurs, comparatively under-researched. Distorted perceptions of Uyghur culture and heritage result from the research focus on Uyghurs in Ürümqi only (**Thum,2018,p.16**). The city does not reflect a true image of the capital of an “autonomous” region for the Uyghur people due to the mixing of their culture in a Han-dominated society. Visitors to the city’s museums cannot avoid the huge paintings showing smiling locals in traditional dress offering gifts to their PLA liberators. The message to Uyghurs from the state, which has named their city’s landmarks and streets¹⁶⁸, such as New China Avenue,

¹⁶⁸Ürümqi has become a city alien to Uyghur culture. Despite this, Uyghurs are expected to show gratitude to the state and praise and thank the CCP leaders for the city's "blessing of development" (**Mukherjee,2010,p.430**). Uyghur individuals languishing in prisons/re-education camps in Xinjiang during Xi Jinping's rule are also required to replace the phrase "Thank God," which Muslims usually use after eating, with "Thanks to the PRC and praise to Xi Jinping" (**documentaries-news-now,2023**).

New People's Avenue, Victory Avenue, and Liberation Avenue, is clear: everything they have is the state's creation, and they should be grateful for it **(Mukherjee,2010,p.430)**. So in distorting concepts and modifying nomenclature, the Chinese point of view gained the upper hand in the struggle among Han and Uyghur scholars to determine the history of the Uyghurs. The Chinese state was able to suppress Uyghur historians whose interpretations of their people's past deviated from the standards acceptable to China **(Tursun,2008,p.95)**.

Among these programs was the state's insistence on putting single girls from rural Xinjiang to work in factories in eastern China. The rural girl who was uprooted from her society in order to work in the East loses her traditions and religion, according to some analyses, in the hope that she will be treated equally with the rest of the Han people. However, she begins to learn the language and adapt easily to the Han environment **(Cappelletti,2020,p.96)**. In this way, they elevated their social position by distancing themselves from Islam and embracing "secular Sinocentrism" **(Zang,2012,p.88)**. These girls had to accept the Chinese programs if they

sought to gain the respect of the Han and achieve social equality with them **(Finley,2013,p.86)**.

The central government aims to foster intermarriage between Han and Uyghur individuals through its Sinicization strategy, believing it will contribute to regional stability and development. This has led some Uyghur families to marry off their daughters to Uyghur men at a young age to deter them from meeting Han people in the future **(Cappelletti,2020,p.97)**.

Additionally, the state adopted a strategy of recording Uyghur names on passports and official documents in the Chinese writing system, including rearranging the sequence to place the surname ahead of the given name, similar to the format used in traditional Chinese naming. However, this contradiction between the name on the document and the name that the Uyghurs use in daily life creates many problems for them when they travel to foreign countries **(Finley,2013,p.89)**. Through the Sinicization programs, the Beijing government aims to modify the demographic balance of the region, thus weakening the Islamic identity and the Uyghurs' sense of belonging to the region and its heritage. Beijing also seeks to exploit Xinjiang's huge resources for the benefit of the provinces and residents of

China's interior and coastal regions (**Cappelletti,2020,p.96**). While Chinese researchers see these Sinicization programs as an opportunity to lift the young Uyghur workforce out of poverty and backwardness and train them in modern environments in order to transfer skills that will be redirected and recycled into the regional economy in Xinjiang, Western and Uyghur intellectuals see them as a clear pattern of “internal colonialism” (**Cappelletti,2020,p.96**). In this setting, internal colonialism refers to the power and control wielded by a relatively small group—the Han, as embodied by the Chinese regime—over a significant subjugated population consisting of various groups, such as the Uyghurs and other ethnic minorities, who find themselves excluded from the developmental process and denied opportunities for social advancement (**Cappelletti,2020,p.289-290**).

In summary, much like the Western colonialists who presented Christianity, capitalism, and democracy as benevolent offerings to those oppressed by the colonial rule, the Chinese colonizers provided socialist “liberation” from local customs for ethnic minorities by promoting cultural assimilation into Han society (**Byler,2018,p.92**). As outlined before, the

findings from the Sinicization projects and the implementation of Chinese language instruction displayed a range of effects, from nearly full acculturation of ethnic minorities into Han culture to varying levels of partial assimilation, culminating in instances of symbolic resistance and refusal of ethnic integration **(Finley,2013,p.368)**. Or in practical terms, integration rejection is what happened in Xinjiang during the mid-1980s until its end, coinciding with the events in Tiananmen Square. But the idea that the Uyghurs are doomed to assimilate with the Han only in a one-way process is considered too simplistic. In fact, Uyghurs experience a variety of cultures, including local Uyghur culture, Han culture, and a number of global cultures flowing from Central Asia, Russia, America, Turkey, and the Arab world in the process of expanding their horizons and their perspectives **(Finley,2013,p.381)**.

By borrowing the findings of Eric Hyer, an associate professor of political science and the coordinator for Asian studies at Brigham Young University, in his research into the civilizational conflict taking place in Xinjiang, the Uyghurs, unlike many other nationalities in China, resisted cultural assimilation and preserved their “Uyghurism” **(Hyer,2005,p.26)**.

The preservation of "Uyghurism," or the maintenance of ethnic identity among the Uyghurs, doesn't inherently lead to heightened separatist sentiments. However, during China's reform era, a link was observed between growing awareness of Uyghur culture and efforts to protect it, alongside increased protests against the regime and cultural assimilation efforts (**Moneyhon,2003,p.507**). The Sinicization programs served as the official mechanism that expedited the rise and enhancement of racial consciousness among the ethnic groups subjected to "Sinicization," essentially aiming to civilize them (**Moneyhon,2003,p.507**). This view has lingered for too long; it maintains its belief that everything that is Chinese is linked to progress and occupies the center, and everything that is not is feudal and reactionary and is pushed to the far background (**Stroup,2021,p.1235**).

II. The Link between Orientalist View and Preferential Policies

1. The Chinese Man's Burden: The Template of “Orientalism” in Western China

Napoleon's expedition to Egypt in the late eighteenth century was marked by significant events and transformations that spanned from the Islamic East to the European West; however, the Western perspective on the Near East laid the foundations for an Orientalist viewpoint that remains relevant into the twenty-first century. Once Napoleon and his henchmen arrived in the East and felt their superiority over the local population, they became the first "Orientalists" in history (**Bloom,2004,p.2**). In theory, Orientalism was only the study of the East, but Edward Said¹⁶⁹ assumed it was actually another aspect of European imperialism. According to this theory, instead of conducting an abstract and apolitical study of the East,

¹⁶⁹American philosopher and university professor of Palestinian origin (1935-2003). He transformed the idea of Orientalism with his book published in 1978, where he detailed the impact of the Western perspective on the East and its interaction with various factors and traits. Said argued that the West's early studies of the Arab and Islamic region were biased and projected a false, stereotypical view of it, thereby facilitating Western colonial policy in the Middle East (**Britannica,n.d**).

Europeans projected their own vision of the East that was divorced from reality (**Mortimer-Murphy,2020,p.11**). Donald Rosenthal, an American writer, critic, and Orientalist, summarizes the idea that Edward Said is trying to convey about Orientalism: “A way of thinking to define, classify, and express the supposed inferiority of the civilization of the Islamic East. In short, it is part of the vast control mechanism of colonialism designed to justify and perpetuate European domination over it.” (**Bloom,2004,p.2**). But it was not only the Europeans who projected a distorted view on other people with whom they came into contact within the political, economic, and social systems. The perception of superiority often stems from various individuals and nationalities, reflecting how one group views another. This attitude may be widespread among a culture or specific to a few individuals, particularly in today’s modern era where technology has enhanced interaction between different populations, making their differences more apparent.

In China's imperial past, different labels were arbitrarily applied according to the characteristics of different populations. The term “Han” has long been used to refer to the population associated with the region dating

back to the origins of Chinese culture, and in this way, the concept of what is Chinese and what is not has not clearly emerged throughout history **(Cappelletti,2020,p.273)**. Early Chinese historians wrote about how the ways of the ancient peoples on the borders of Central Asia and Inner Asia were in no way compatible with Chinese customs. The ways and methods of the individuals of those peoples were viewed as backward and deviant ways, far removed from those followed in imperial China **(Dwyer,2005,p.1)**. During its modern history, the Chinese state asserts that the ethnic minorities liberated by the PLA were living according to backward methods and a feudal system in uncivilized and unproductive lands before their socialist "liberators" arrived from eastern China. Thus, the Chinese regime's account of the period of the PRC continues in the narrative: "Ethnic minority communities then entered into close harmony with the Han people, the minorities' 'big brother,' which led to the creation of increasing levels of happiness and progress in their regions." **(Byler,2018,p.18-19)**. In this regard, Mao made a comparison between the Han people and minority regions by focusing on the merging and adaptability of the knowledge and experiences of the more developed and widespread Han society with the extensive, resource-laden, and sparsely populated lands inhabited by

minorities. In the narrative encouraging the Han to venture westward to "develop the Chinese West," the minority regions are depicted as barren territories filled with abundant, untapped resources that are eager for the Chinese nation's ambition to utilize them. Here lies the role of the Han people in providing assistance to the backward ethnic communities that need to learn the sciences aced by the Han (**Liu&Peters,2017,p.267**). Historically and politically influenced, the Han people generally hold a condescending, Orientalist perspective towards the Uyghur community in Xinjiang. This Orientalist view includes many aspects that contribute to consolidating that view in the collective political and social consciousness of the Han people: Han chauvinism—the strangeness of the Uyghur people from the Han point of view, who see the relationship with the Uyghurs in terms of the concept of “we-vs.-them”—the” sexual element that is often present in the dynamics of different peoples, which seeks to feminize the other who is different—the aspect of insult, humiliation¹⁷⁰, and hatred, the latter of which exist on both sides, not just the Han, and are predominantly individual in nature and cannot be generalized to an entire group on either side.

¹⁷⁰On March 8, 2018, during International Women’s Day, the regional government in Xinjiang mandated that Uyghur men publicly wash the feet of women in public squares, a move aimed at undermining their masculinity and reflecting the state's assertion of promoting gender equality in China (**Byler,2018,p.14**).

In a similar analysis of the concept of “the white man’s burden¹⁷¹” that is clear in Western literature, the Chinese Han scholar He Jiangcheng considered that Han people accepted their national responsibility to help ethnic minorities according to each minority's needs **(Sautman,1997,p.4)**. June T. Dreyer, a professor of political science at the University of Miami, documents how the “Han burden” of helping other nationalities was fraught with problems and difficulties, not least the need for Beijing to regularly warn and admonish cadres for their arrogance, persecution, and oppression of minority members during the process of “taking their shared responsibility” as Han people. The disillusioned Han youth who were exiled from the countryside to Xinjiang during the Cultural Revolution harmed Muslims in Xinjiang and mocked their beliefs and customs **(Finley,2013,p.87)**. The responsibility to assist ethnic nationalities and protect their unity has been addressed in the preamble of the Chinese Constitution **(Mukherjee,2010,p.421)**. The following was stated: “In the struggle to preserve the unity of the nationalities, it is necessary to combat

¹⁷¹A poem by British writer and poet Rudyard Kipling, which he used to urge the imperial ambitions of both the United Kingdom and the United States to do their best to impose their colonialism on peoples who were less "white" and less developed than themselves. The name of the poem, "The White Man's Burden," was used by Western media enthusiastic about colonial projects to promote a civilizing mission that required every Englishman, or more broadly every white man, to bring European culture to the pagan indigenous peoples in their uncivilized world outside Europe and North America **(Stewart,2024)**.

the chauvinism of the great nation, the chauvinism of the Han, and it is also necessary to combat the chauvinism of the local nationalities.”

(Constitute,2018). The notion that the superior race in China is accountable for the other inferior races creates a link between the introductory remarks of the Chinese Constitution and the regime’s belief that Han culture represents modernity, whereas Uyghur culture embodies ignorance and a lack of progress **(Cappelletti,2020,p.46)**. Han cultural chauvinism often leads to describing Uyghurs as lazy and childish, or ignorant and superstitious, and most importantly, as ungrateful for the economic development that the Han have brought to Xinjiang **(Han,2010,p.254)**. Furthermore, the Han assume that the Uyghurs are terrorists affiliated with fundamentalist groups and deliberately distance themselves from them **(Stroup,2021,p.1236)**. Many Uyghurs claim that attitudes of racial and cultural superiority have become common as the Han population in Xinjiang grows. For example, recent Han immigrants do not respect the Uyghur language **(Smith,2000,p.10)** because they consider themselves better than the locals **(Lüthi,2013,p.164)**. They have become unwilling to adapt to the Uyghur culture but rather expect the Uyghurs to adapt to their superior culture **(Smith,2002,p.7)**. It has been observed that middle-aged Uyghurs fluent in Mandarin tend to be more

receptive to Chinese propaganda and show greater acceptance of Han chauvinism in Xinjiang, leading some individuals in this demographic to adopt a negative view of Uyghur culture akin to that of their Han counterparts. This is because middle-aged Uyghurs are motivated by a strong desire to safeguard their families, and they wish to avoid a return to the era of ethnic and religious oppression that marked the Cultural Revolution; in contrast, the younger generation, who did not experience that time, feels they have nothing to lose and are more closely tied to their cultural traditions due to the continuous contact with Han individuals **(Smith,2000,p.19)**.

As for the reform period, efforts to weaken Han chauvinism were concentrated in Chinese politics and society during its first half. On the occasion of the thirtieth anniversary of the founding of the PRC in late September 1979, reformist party leaders recalled both Mao's 1956 speech during the "Hundred Flowers Campaign"¹⁷²,” titled “On the Ten Major

¹⁷²Identifying with Khrushchev's period of openness within the Soviet Union, Chinese leaders in 1956 launched the Hundred Flowers Campaign with the famous phrase: "Let a hundred flowers bloom, and a hundred schools of thought compete." **(Finley,2013,p.71-72)**.

Relationships¹⁷³," and his 1957 article, "On the Correct Handling of Contradictions among the People." By emphasizing this speech and article, the leaders showcased their endorsement of Mao's policy against "Han chauvinism," which they positioned as a foundational element of the general minorities policy that the socialist state ought to implement via a step-by-step integration process and adjustment to its ethnic minority groups (Clarke,2007,p.43). As time progressed, the direction of policies in China changed to promote greater openness toward ethnic minorities. These earlier statements were solidified into a formal policy by the CCP, which, in 1981, reaffirmed Mao's 1950s vision by declaring that Han chauvinism was a greater danger to China than the chauvinism displayed by ethnic minorities (Clarke,2007,p.56). Coupled with allowing the ethnic nationalities to continue their cultural traditions in their own societies, the process of weakening Han chauvinism emerged as the "first solution" to ending the impasse of ethnic conflict in China (Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.349). In addition to Mao's speeches, during this period the Party published Zhou Enlai's posthumous speeches, in which he focused on resisting both local

¹⁷³He demonstrated that China's approach to the socialist revolution would leverage the vast capital from rural farmers, in stark contrast to the Soviet Union's reliance on the urban working class of St. Petersburg and Moscow (Clarke,2007,p.43).

nationalism and Han chauvinism (**Millward,2007,p.277**). While he argued in those speeches that cultural adaptation is a progressive act through which nations grow and move towards prosperity and flourishing (**Hyer,2005,p.25**). But despite the state imposing conciliatory policies towards national minorities, Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, posits that Han chauvinism persisted and perhaps worsened during the reform period in an unexpected way (**Finley,2013,p.87**). The 1984 mandate for compulsory bilingual education combining Mandarin and minority languages could be seen as a facet of the increasing Han chauvinism that the reformist leadership claimed they were working to counteract on both cultural and social fronts in China (**Hann,2014,p.197**).

When anthropologists engage in the study of ethnic minorities in China, they tend to be more interested in specific forms of historiography than in the narrative of history, and they are also keen to understand how historians' critical analysis of political and social life contributes to changing classifications of modern ethnic identities in society or the state (**Huang,2009,p.2**). Anthropologists argue that ethnic identity politics and

classifications, everywhere and not just in China, cannot be understood outside the general and dominant effort to create a concept of modern citizens who are seen as more civilized than others, namely, the backward traditional minorities who inhabit areas adjacent to the modern citizens **(Huang,2009,p.2)**. For a variety of reasons, Xinjiang's minorities have not been considered sufficiently qualified to build their own nation-state **(Hyer,2005,p.24)**. Indeed, Xinjiang was seen as not being a suitable buffer zone to ensure China's security **(Beller-Hann,2022,p.95)**. When it comes to traditional dress, the distressing memories of the Cultural Revolution have not faded from the shared memory of ethnic minorities. The Red Guards focused on minorities outside the Han majority, compelling them to rid themselves of their conventional and cultural attire, including various decorations, hats, and ethnic-specific clothing items **(Bovingdon,2004,p.20)**. Ethnic attire was replaced with green and blue revolutionary uniforms in order to erase any element of difference that was referred to as backwardness and impose forced assimilation on the minorities **(Gladney,2003,p.460)**. This colonialist viewpoint is reinforced by the CCP largely through cultural portrayals, including the presentation of traditional Islamic dress codes in Xinjiang found in travel brochures and publications **(Thwaites,2001,p.139)**.

In this way, intentionally or unintentionally, the CCP contributes to raising popular suspicions in China towards the Islamic communities on its territory (Stroup,2021,p.1244). It should also be noted that the images that the CCP was keen to show are of a small portion of women who chose to wear the *hijab*. Through this, the CCP hopes to show the “otherness” of the Uyghur people and to emphasize that they occupy the position of “other” in the concept of “we-vs.-them,” not only from the Chinese point of view but also from the Western point of view, which sees Islam as an intruder in their societies (Thwaites,2001,p.139).

Image #14

Alexa Olesen “The Five Unnatural Patterns”

A 2014 government advertisement in Karamay, predominantly populated by Han people, depicted various styles of *hijabs* and *niqabs*, stating that individuals wearing them are prohibited from using public transportation in the city during the post-reform period.

<https://foreignpolicy.com/2014/08/06/in-one-xinjiang-city-beards-and-muslim-headscarves-banned-from-buses/>

Image #15

Chinese programs have succeeded in turning Xinjiang into a discotheque to attract tourists and show that the Uyghurs are good at singing and dancing only.

<https://www.chinafile.com/investing-tourism-xinjiang-beijing-seeks-new-ways-control-regions-culture>

The Uyghur people, in addition to being “the other” and different from the Han people in China, have also been labeled “exotic” in the eyes of the Han community. The internal Orientalist system created by the CCP is fundamentally based on a myth-making process that emphasizes the colorful and exotic nature of the other, albeit a dangerous specimen, evidencing simplicity and superficiality in the eyes of the more sophisticated and more complex Han people (Stroup,2021,p.1244). Thus, China rediscovered its minorities, which it quickly succeeded in transforming into an “exotic” cultural commodity for internal consumption and external marketing

(Baranovitch,2003,p.731). In fact, Uyghur lives often mattered only when they contributed to the fulfillment of Han desires. The Uyghur bodies were limited to meet the desires of the eyes of tourists coming to China with the aim of seeing male and female dancers who were foreign to the Han and who presented traditional folkloric dance performances in the Uyghur areas. They were also useful as workers and employees in the tourist bazaar spaces owned by the Han as well **(Byler,2018,p.279)**. As for more complex, responsible, and sophisticated work, the belief among Han people is that the Uyghurs do not possess the necessary discipline in the capitalist system. As Tang Lijiu, an economic advisor for the Xinjiang region, said, the Uyghurs are not suitable to enter the large industrial production line because of their simple lifestyle, and for many Han businessmen, the Uyghurs were just too big a problem that it would be better not to have at the middle and upper levels of work **(Byler,2018,p.42)**. The "Uyghur exoticism" emphasized by the Han highlights various negative characteristics, such as the idea that Uyghurs are unable to keep pace with twenty-first-century modern life. Thriving on banditry in historical context, Uyghurs descend from peoples who find it easier to steal and plunder in order to secure something instead of working hard to obtain it, according to some of the Han people's

assumptions. According to the Han, the Uyghur people also have some exotic positive characteristics¹⁷⁴ that are limited to singing, dancing, and presenting folkloric performances that indicate the culture of the ethnic group to which they belong and which they have inherited from generation to generation. The Han believe that rural Uyghurs excel in traditional handicrafts, which makes them an ethnic minority distinct from the Han both geographically and socially, as well as culturally **(Cappelletti,2020,p.46)**. The visit of Han individuals to the Uyghur countryside in Xinjiang deepens their view of the difference between the Han world and the Islamic-Turkish Uyghur world. They start by tasting a different type of food that the Han are usually familiar with and, secondly, speaking a language different from that used in the cities of Xinjiang in the countryside. Whenever Han people visit Uyghur restaurants¹⁷⁵, they will see mosque paintings featuring the Islamic crescent depicted in Arabic calligraphy, while the melodies of Uyghur folk music fill the air both inside and outside the eateries

¹⁷⁴The Uyghurs have emerged as an alien element to China but a powerful tourist attraction and source of revenue for the state **(Cappelletti,2020,p.272)**, which has turned Xinjiang into a huge “Disneyland” the size of a province and its Uyghurs into a sight to behold **(Steenberg,2021,p.180)**.

¹⁷⁵This experience is not limited to Han people visiting rural Xinjiang. During the reform period, Uyghur restaurants spread like wildfire in China’s inner cities, such as Beijing, Shanghai, and Guangdong, etc., which was enough to transfer the Han experience of Uyghur alienation to Han cities in the interior of China. Moreover, these restaurants competed in offering and selling “exotic products”; for example, in addition to the food that was alien to the Han people, these restaurants featured belly dancing performed by beautiful young Uyghur women, thus preserving the traditional representation of the Han view of Uyghurs in China **(Baranovitch,2003,p.732)**.

(Baranovitch,2003,p.731). The alienation of the Uyghurs who “invaded” Beijing during the reform period was exacerbated during the lifting of restrictions on internal movement, who were seen as outsiders because of their different appearance and their almost exclusive association with selling Turkish “*shish kebab*” food. Thus they became an easy target and a focal point for the general hatred and suspicion that urban dwellers began to feel towards all the strangers who flooded their cities and, in their view, threatened their modernity and stability (Baranovitch,2003,p.734), especially the Uyghurs, who were strangers and further away on the “scale of difference¹⁷⁶” from the Han.

Certain radical ideologies within the Han community that advocate the belief that Uyghurs are fundamentally different from humans have been found to exceed acceptable boundaries. So that a newspaper in Beijing in 1988, that is, even at the final stages of the reform period, published a stunning report about “humanoids inhabiting the Taklamakan Desert in Xinjiang whose tails dangle from their backs,” referring to members of a

¹⁷⁶The Han people might perceive the Hui as being more similar to them due to shared ethnic ties, despite the Hui being Muslims, whereas the Uyghurs, Mongols, and Manchus, given their greater ethnic differences, are probably seen as less relatable and positioned lower in the hierarchy of distinctions from the Han.

poor and marginalized community isolated in an area within the Khotan oasis in southern Xinjiang. This attracted widespread attention throughout China and bolstered the “we-vs.-them” equation that resides in the collective mind and consciousness of the Han people **(Beller-Hann,2022,p.101)**. Some Uyghur researchers tried to refute the insulting stigma that the magazine tried to spread about this poor and primitive society, based on numerous visits to the region; a Uyghur researcher who lived with the members of the aforementioned community described the human and spiritual values he found among its members, including the ideals of morality, solidarity, generosity, self-denial, and asceticism. This was developed due to their closeness to nature and their relative isolation from the state, the market, and tempting material life, which reinforced in them those moral virtues and human values. However, the contemporary triumph of modernity over simplicity has brought about social hardship and negative consequences that have struck at the very heart of their community **(Beller-Hann,2022,p.101)**. Thus, the official Chinese narrative prevailed here, as this simple, marginalized Uyghur community proved that its members are not truly prepared to keep pace with modernity and that the civilizational wave would

drown these individuals in a spiral of losing social values without gaining in return the benefits of modernity of knowledge, easy living, and progress.

Eric Berkowitz¹⁷⁷, a journalist and researcher specializing in the history of sexual behavior among individuals and societies, said that the European warrior who came to the East part of the Crusades¹⁷⁸ viewed the Muslim fighter as deviant in feminine behavior. This made it easier for him to combat him physically and fight him out of moral and religious conviction (**Berkowitz,2013,p.171**). Berkowitz moves to South and Latin America during the period of exploration of the New World, and there he describes how the Europeans exploited the women of the “exotic” societies found in the New World in a window of sexual freedom after fleeing their original societies in Puritanical Britain¹⁷⁹ and the rest of Europe. Thus, the

¹⁷⁷Eric Berkowitz established this relationship in his book, *Sex and Punishment: 4000 Years of Judging Desire*. This book is classified as a comprehensive encyclopedia in which the researcher recounts the history of sexual relations in all its forms and the types of punishment that societies imposed to punish all types and forms of sexual behavior that deviate from the norm set by society, starting with the Mesopotamian civilization two thousand years BC until the trial of the writer and playwright, Oscar Wilde in Britain in the late nineteenth century.

¹⁷⁸A series of military campaigns organized by popes and Western Christian kingdoms to reclaim Jerusalem and the Holy Lands from Muslim control and then defend those gains. There were eight major official crusades between 1095 and 1270 (**Cartwright,2018**).

¹⁷⁹A religious reform movement in the late 16th and 17th centuries that sought to "purify" the Church of England of the remnants of Roman Catholic papacy that the Puritans claimed had infiltrated the Church of England following the religious settlement reached early in the reign of Queen Elizabeth I. The Puritans became known in the seventeenth century for a spirit of moral and religious seriousness and strictness that shaped their entire way of life, and through the Reformation of the Church they sought to make their way of life the pattern followed by the entire nation. Their efforts to convert the nation contributed to causing the Civil War in England in the mid-17th century and to establishing the colonies in America as practical models of the Puritan way of life (**Britannica,n.d**).

American continent became a playground full of women available to fulfill the desires of the white man coming from Europe for a period of more than three centuries, according to his imagination. Sexual relations between the settler man and the women of the indigenous peoples were also fraught with the politics of power, authority, and domination, as sex was a tool to “conquer” the women of the colonized society by the white settler **(Berkowitz,2013,p.253)**. The sexual dimension of the condescending view through which the settler of a region attempts to feminize the men of its society and project negative patterns towards the behavior of its women is not limited to the white man only, but the Han man in China sees minority communities as an arena to vent his lusts and desires while expressing his negative judgments at “the other.” Referring to China, Dru C. Gladney, a professor of anthropology at Pomona College and a leading expert on the peoples and cultures along the past and present Silk Roads, posits the following: “The minority in China is to the majority what the female is to the male, as the Third World is to the First World.” The widespread definition of the “minority” as alien and primitive presents the majority as advanced and modern **(Liu&Peters,2017,p.269)**. The sexual dimension begins with the body and its characteristics, such that the massive and solid

physique, although it suggests strength and fighting spirit, has been associated with the demonic creatures depicted in Buddhist icons. The immensity and enormity offended the Han belief¹⁸⁰ that the body must balance the opposing cosmic forces of *Yin*, the feminine principle represented by fat, and *Yang*, the masculine principle represented by bones (Finley,2013,p.94). The bias of “civilization vs. barbarism” still exists, as the feeling of “cultural and aesthetic superiority” emerged in the past among the Han people, who grew up with stable social systems, in contrast to the nomadic lifestyle of Inner Asian warriors from Turks, Mongols, and others (Finley,2013,p.95). In addition, the Han people describe the tendency of Uyghur males to settle disputes through physical combat as “uncivilized” behavior because they, the Han, were raised according to Confucian norms, which call for maintaining social harmony and tranquility and rejecting violence and fighting (Finley,2013,p.126).

The sexual dimension of the Han’s condescending view of minorities is not limited only to the relationship between them, but rather it appeared in

¹⁸⁰This perception proves how each civilization has derived its own concept of good and evil, right and wrong, the familiar and the strange, according to the characteristics of its people. The bodies of the East Asian races, which are closer to weakness than strength and hugeness, are considered to be a mirror of goodness, unlike the huge bodies that are considered a symbol of evil and “Satan.” If the bodies of the yellow race were inclined to strength and enormity, they would boast of strength and associate physical weakness with strangeness.

the practices of the People's Republic, which accommodated Han bias in an official context. In China, sexual relations—what a man typically does to a woman—have long been seen as a metaphor for hegemony imposed by the state on peoples on the periphery (**Finley,2013,p.340**). As for Uyghur women, the Chinese regime presented them, in addition to other ethnic minority women, as an exotic delight for onlookers in their brightly colored traditional folkloric clothing. During the reform era in Xinjiang's restaurants, a notable trend emerged where Uyghur women are often depicted in stereotypes, including some veiled women who perform dances for Han customers, reinforcing a sense of dominance over the minority group and carrying sexual undertones (**Tursun,2017,p.12**). As part of the Communist Party's Orientalist minority policy, the state presented *Āmānnisā Khan* as a historical figure to the Chinese public and as a cultural embodiment of Uyghur women. In addition, it restored her grave to become a shrine for believers and published a *Tadhkira* in her name. The CCP's interest in a female figure who enjoyed limited power in her time is consistent with China's narrative: the female replaces other male figures and occupies a space in the legacy of those minorities, and thus China's Orientalist attempt to feminize the "other" succeeds by marketing female historical figures that

symbolize that culture (Thum,2014,p.235). The official attempts to feminize the other in Xinjiang developed as time progressed during the reform period, and this appeared in the content of what was published by the Xinjiang magazine for ethnic nationalities, *Xinjiang Minzu Wenxue*. In 1981, this official magazine issued an article in which the author elaborates on the historical contributions of the Xinjiang region to world literature, and the author also links Xinjiang's central Silk Roads to its role in bringing together Buddhist, Islamic, and Christian cultures. The fact that this article was published in 1981 indicates that the political atmosphere permitted some degree of expression of Uyghur desires, framing Uyghur culture as a separate entity among the world's various cultures. But it seemed that this relatively open climate had begun to turn into an Orientalist bias against the Uyghurs by 1983, when a painting was republished in the second issue of the magazine depicting a woman wearing an Islamic *hijab* but at the same time showing a curvaceous body and bare arms in a way reminiscent of the Orientalist paintings painted by Western artists, such as Eugène Delacroix¹⁸¹

¹⁸¹ Artist and painter (1798-1863) and one of the greatest French romantic painters and Orientalists during the nineteenth century. Eugène Delacroix fervently led the movement of Orientalist art with his impressive paintings that drew from his experiences in Morocco, capturing the beauty of North Africa through vivid scenes infused with warm colors typical of its dry desert environment (Martet,2018).

and Jean-Auguste-Dominique Ingres¹⁸², during the nineteenth century¹⁸³ (**Thwaites,2001,p.207**). Even the 1979 painting "Awakening of Tarim" by Chinese artist Zhao Yixiong¹⁸⁴ also shows parallels with European Orientalist art paintings. This painting depicts a naked woman with features of the Uyghur nationality prevailing, lying on a group of traditional and modern images, and around her are visible oil platforms, airplanes, and nuclear facilities¹⁸⁵, while minarets and camel caravans come from between her thighs. According to an analysis by Dru C. Gladney, a professor of anthropology at Pomona College and a leading expert on the peoples and cultures along the past and present Silk Roads, the painting heavily linked nationalism, women, and tradition and implied that Xinjiang could only be modernized by shedding the traditional culture and the Islamic religion. Jo

¹⁸²French artist and painter (1780-1867). His painting "The Turkish Bath" in 1862 and 1863 represented an achievement in this type of nude art, as he painted females lying on the floor in an Ottoman harem (**Shelton,2024**).

¹⁸³From Napoleon's campaign in the East until Henri Matisse's stay in North Africa in the early twentieth century, this was the period in which Orientalism knew its golden age (**OrientalismInEurope,2011**). So that the French were able to document and classify this backwardness in the East according to their description through drawing and art, where curious Europeans aspiring to know and discover the East flocked to drawings, pictures, and paintings that documented the East from a Western perspective and which were sold in European markets (**Bloom,2004,p.40**). Most of the artistic paintings painted in the nineteenth century about the East show women either wearing Islamic outfits or naked in positions that arouse lust (**Martet,2018**). To address their frustration with the difficulty of accessing Muslim women for drawing—due to the isolation of Islamic society from Western men—artists resorted to hiring prostitutes or relying on their imagination, resulting in a skewed representation of Eastern women that reflected the artists' hopes rather than reality (**Bloom,2004,p.3**).

¹⁸⁴Han Chinese artist (1934-) and member of the Chinese Artists Association. During the 1970s, he studied the peoples in the Silk Roads regions of Turpan, Kashgar, and elsewhere (**ChineseNewArt**). Through his art and paintings, he contributed to deepening the sexual dimension of the Han view of minority peoples, and this was evident in the negative patterns that swarmed the "Awakening of Tarim" painting.

¹⁸⁵An expression of the geography of the Xinjiang region, where the Lop Nor nuclear facility and oil wells are located. Xinjiang is rich in oil reserves. This is one of the most important reasons why China does not neglect it.

Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, goes further in analyzing the painting and suggests that it can be viewed as a representation of the sexual subjugation of Uyghur women by Han men, which also symbolizes the political control over the Uyghur nation as a whole **(Finley,2013,p.340-341)**. The Orientalist view of the Uyghur people, in the name of cultural and artistic renaissance, portrays them as exhibition halls for tourist purposes rather than as people in their own right, on the one hand. On the other hand, the Chinese authorities, by imposing political monitoring of the process of cultural and artistic renaissance that may occur in Xinjiang, may obtain support from the more conservative forces in the Uyghur community, which may help them suppress modern social and cultural developments in the Uyghur community **(Thwaites,2001,p.139)**. An unconventional “coincidence marriage” occurs between the Chinese regime and the conservative group in Uyghur society in this region.

In singing, as in painting, China feminizes minorities within an orientalist perspective and a broad modernist project. This was clearly demonstrated by the Han Chinese songwriter Wang Luobin, who spent many

years in northwest China and became referred to as the "King of Song in Western China." Many of Wang's famous "Xinjiang Folk Songs" depict a Han man falling in love with local girls in the Xinjiang region, and these songs are full of detailed physical illustrations of these beautiful girls with curvaceous bodies that stir the lust of the Han men. In addition to the element of sensuality, Wang Luobin's songs are also likely responsible for much of the widespread association of the Xinjiang region with beautiful girls in the minds and imagination of the Han people, and this is very consistent with the trend in Chinese culture to feminize ethnic minorities **(Baranovitch,2003,p.732-733)**. One of the songs written by Wang Luobin was criticized by Uyghur intellectuals because of the focus of the lyrics on the physical topic, namely, "Lift Up Your Veil and Let Me See Your Face." **(Harris,2004,p.12)**. The writer directly encouraged Xinjiang women to ditch the *hijab*, which enabled Wang to kill two birds with one stone: provoking jealousy among Uyghurs linked to Han men serenading their women and disrupting their religious identity through interference with their traditional garments. Male interference in women's lives and attempts to impose their perceptions, outlooks, and aspirations on them embody a concept that transcends nationalism and ethnicity in China. In this regard,

the phenomenon of “leftover women¹⁸⁶” is prominent in the Chinese scene. This is the increasing number of working, highly educated, unmarried women of marriageable age, i.e., around thirty years old. They are pejoratively labeled as “leftovers” due to society's belief that these women have been “sexually used” before and are now considered discarded goods in the marriage market, highlighting a misguided societal prejudice that perceives women solely as physical entities, focusing only on their prior relationship history. Like women in China as a whole, this bias applies fully to minority and Uyghur women, of course. The societal desire that aspires for women to have a lower professional status than men continues in contemporary China, and men in society still have the right to impose restrictions that they want on women's bodies, which indicates that Chinese society is still a masculine society (**Tursun,2017,p.15**). On the other hand, Han scholars who have studied the Uyghur community in Xinjiang and who represent the official views of the state responsible for this situation continue to pretend that the patriarchal system stems only from the practices and teachings of Islam and that the Chinese state has nothing to do with it. Rather, they argue that reformist leaders have improved the status of women

¹⁸⁶A book bearing the same title, “Leftover Women,” is an academic study on gender discrimination in China that was written in 2014 by the American researcher specializing in gender relations in China, Leta Hong Fincher.

and alleviated male influence in society during the reform era
(Beller-Hann,1998,p.12). Han scholars seem to overlook the state initiatives
that highlight the feminization of ethnic minority groups, portraying their
women as areas to fulfill the desires of Han men who are colonizing the
Xinjiang region.

Image #16

Zhang Yixiong's 1980 "Awakening of Tarim"

A painting of Chinese Orientalist art during the reform period. A naked girl with features of the Uyghur nationality embodies the Xinjiang region through Chinese eyes.

<https://aaa.org.hk/en/collections/search/archive/joan-lebold-cohen-archive-artists-16045/object/zhang-yixiong-zhao-yu-and-zhong-ming-set-of-7-photographs>

Feelings of hatred, arrogance, and the urgent need to humiliate the “strange other” often surface within the relationship that brings together members of the Han and Uyghur nationalities. These characteristics go in both directions and are not limited to any people or nationality alone. A significant number of Han people, who regularly call for the socialist assimilation of all classes and the accommodation of minorities, commonly raise the following question in relation to the Uyghur population: “Why do they hate us so much after we have done so many good things for them?” **(Byler,2018,p.47)**. Due to the pervasive stereotypes associated with the Uyghur people, including labels like "backward" and "terrorist," a Han person who advocates for them is viewed as an outsider **(Byler,2018,p.202)**. For their part, the Uyghur people do not hesitate to show disgust and contempt towards the Han people whenever possible. Many of them spit on the ground when they pass by members of the Han people, and some sellers in Uyghur markets and bazaars refuse to deal with them, and when they do, they charge exorbitant prices from them. This discrimination is mutual between the two parties and is gradually getting worse **(Han,2010,p.254)**. The label of the Uyghur terrorist, rooted in the consciousness of the Han people, is also present in the West’s perceptions of Islam and Muslims, often

(Zelcer-Lavid,2022,P.855). Indeed, some metaphors for the Han idea of superiority over the Uyghurs and other minorities were mixed with metaphors dating back to far-right populist movements in Europe and the world. As a result, the merging of these two currents of discourse among the Han and the European right expands the popular reach of anti-Islamic discourse worldwide **(Stroup,2021,p.1237)**. Han Chinese researcher Yao Zhongwo, in research published in the Chinese magazine “Leadership Science” *Lingdao Kexue*, links Islam and its complexities in practice to the slow maturation of Muslim minority cadres in China. Minority cadres were portrayed as maintaining economic, cultural, and religious backwardness **(Sautman,1997,p.19)**. In addition, some Han Chinese researchers have coined a new term, “rural disease.” These researchers argued that this term is sufficient to understand how farcical and absurd the state's ethnic minority programs are, in which states “go above and beyond” to improve the situation of minorities and to educate them. The reason is that this disease, as they claim, forces these minorities to retreat and revert back to their "innate backwardness" no matter what level of formal progress has been reached and no matter how many tricks the state has up its sleeve **(Finley,2013,p.90)**.

The persistent emphasis by Han scholars, intellectuals, and even the general public on portraying the Uyghur people as backward, whether inherently or not, arises from a desire to belittle them in specific contexts and recurring situations to showcase their own superiority. The common stereotype among the Han that all ethnic minorities are “good at singing and dancing” and nothing else is certainly an aspect of their collective humiliation. Moreover, the intention of the Chinese state, which officially adopts the bias¹⁸⁷ of comparing the “persistent primitiveness” of minority cultures in northwest China negatively with the “modernity” of the Han, is as clear as the sun when it confines those minorities to dancing and singing only (**Finley,2013,p.99,181**). Examples of respect for Islamic dietary practices and the introduction of some Islamic festivals during the reform period in a Han-dominant setting in Xinjiang fostered the belief that peaceful coexistence between Han and Uyghur people is achievable in modern China (**Grose,2010,p.102-103**). Nonetheless, the coexistence encompassed numerous situations where negative stereotypes were aimed at others, resulting in humiliating content and an intense display of hatred against

¹⁸⁷A character representing and stereotyping ethnic minorities in Xinjiang appears in the early 21st-century Chinese film “Crouching Tiger, Hidden Dragon.” This character appears in the film as a dirty, unkempt bandit who lives in a desert cave in Xinjiang, rides a horse, and earns his living by stealing and plundering. These traits were used to clearly distinguish him from the other civilized Han characters in the film (**Finley,2013,p.121**).

them. This hatred is embodied in obscene expressions where names of animals are slung at each other; the Han consider the Uyghurs to be “bed bugs” to indicate their filth, while the Uyghurs refer to the Han in their private gatherings with the phrase “pigs¹⁸⁸” because the Han eat a lot of pork, which causes an unpleasant odor during the cooking process that disturbs the Muslims of Xinjiang. Those studying the Uyghurs from outside the region describe some events they personally encountered, demonstrating the stereotyping process occurring between the two factions. Gardner Bovington, an assistant professor in the Department of Central Eurasian Studies at Indiana University Bloomington, recounts an incident that happened with an old Uyghur man on a bus shared by Uyghurs and Han while he was doing his research in Xinjiang. When he noticed the crowding on the bus, this old man joked that the main problem in Xinjiang is that “sheep and pigs are forced to live together in one barn,” inciting a wave of laughter among other Uyghurs who may have shared the same view of the Han (Finley,2013,p.105,120). The Han people in Xinjiang, through their engagement with the Uyghurs, slowly developed a preference for lamb, resulting in greater purchases and escalating demand that contributed to a

¹⁸⁸ Activists referred to police officers as "pigs" when they encountered them during marches in the civil rights movement in the USA.

marked rise in its price during the reform period. In this regard, Jo Smith Finley, a professor of Chinese studies at Newcastle University and an expert in Uyghur studies, speaks of how the Uyghurs are strongly resisting the rising cost of lamb, their traditionally favored dish, as a result of heightened demand from the Han population. One of them says to her that “the Uyghurs sell “*shish kebab*,” but only the Han can buy and eat it.” (Finley,2013,p.68). As for the issue of “*shish kebab*,” which has become a cultural stereotype about the Uyghurs in China, a joke was circulated during the reform period that expresses the Han’s annoyance at the spread of the Uyghurs in internal China, in addition to showing the negative cultural stereotype about the Uyghur people: “When Neil Armstrong¹⁸⁹ landed on the moon, he found Uyghur men selling “*shish kebab*” on its surface.” (Millward,2007,p.293). In one of the endless political debates at Xinjiang University, where Uyghur students suffer from widespread racial discrimination, on the subject of the Uyghur historical precedence and right in Xinjiang, a Han professor states the following: “Xinjiang has belonged to China for several thousand years. Several tens of thousands of years ago, even before monkeys turned into

¹⁸⁹American astronaut (1930-2012) and the first man to set foot on the moon during the successful NASA Apollo 11 mission in 1969 (Britannica,2024).

humans, Han monkeys came to Xinjiang to teach Uyghur monkeys how to eat peaches and pick leaves!” (Veg,2008,p.146).

This condescending view is not limited to the Han people only but also extends to urban and emigrant Uyghurs who developed a sense of superiority over the Uyghurs of the countryside and the rest of the Uyghurs. This perception is supported by Alessandra Cappelletti, an associate professor at the Department of International Relations at Xi’an Jiaotong Liverpool University who specializes in sinology, who believes that Uyghurs residing in eastern China or overseas, upon returning to their native villages in Xinjiang, experience stringent social limitations and frequently express criticism towards what they view as the outdated and regressive attitudes of their relatives and friends in the region (Cappelletti,2020,p.277-278). Differences within the Uyghur community surpass the city versus countryside dichotomy and present a geographical aspect, as the core identities of Northern and Southern Uyghurs diverge significantly. The Uyghurs in the north, who are more educated and modern, look with disdain on the Uyghurs of the south as primitive, backward, and religious extremists. Likewise, the Uyghurs of the north do not accept in any way their children

marrying into Uyghur families in the south (**Shichor,2005,p.128-129**). From the geographical dimension to the socio-economic dimension, the boundaries of differentiation among the Uyghurs are widening and narrowing in a society dominated by Han concepts of what is advanced and what is backward, of everything that is modern and contemporary, and of everything that is traditional and reactionary. The wealthier Uyghurs who graduated from Chinese-language schools in Xinjiang and were able to find prestigious jobs in government institutions felt enormous pressure to demonstrate their absolute loyalty to the state and to publicly agree with their Han colleagues on the backwardness of Uyghur communities in general. However, no matter how much they fawned over their Han counterparts and made efforts to identify with them in order to prove that they were individuals different from the general Uyghur community, they were never able to be considered truly equal to the Han (**Byler,2018,p.280**).

On the other hand, the Uyghurs, who cling to their customs and are reconciled with their society, look down on the Mandarin-speaking *Minkaohan*, whom they accuse of being too culturally similar to the Han. The ethnic differences in the features of the Chinese-speaking Uyghurs make it impossible to consider them Han. A sarcastic saying from the Uyghurs

themselves says that the *Minkaohan* Uyghurs are the 14th ethnic group in Xinjiang (**Han,2010,p.251-252**). But not everyone is reconciled with their society and can be proud of their identity, and this was clearly demonstrated through a field study conducted by Alessandra Cappelletti, an associate professor at the Department of International Relations at Xi'an Jiaotong Liverpool University who specializes in sinology, in which she detailed how the Uyghurs were forced to lie about their identity through certain details. Although Uyghurs generally express pride and confidence in showcasing their cultural traits, Cappelletti pointed out some occasions where Uyghur people identified themselves as Hui when questioned about their ethnicity. They later clarified that identifying as part of the Hui ethnicity simplifies matters for them, as it signals to the other party that they are Muslims while avoiding the immediate disappointment of having to engage with the complexities associated with being Uyghur (**Cappelletti,2020,p.277**).

In the context of the Chinese colonial initiative in Xinjiang, the aim wasn't to bolster the connection among the Uyghurs and promote their unity but instead to impose Han chauvinism on the Uyghurs and facilitate Chinese settlement in the urban areas and the wider region (**Byler,2018,p.160**). As

time has passed, more Uyghurs have come to see that effective communication and interaction with Han people can occur if the Han admit the failures of China's racial equality policies, even with special policies for minorities, and if they honor the Uyghurs' rights to their linguistic, cultural, and religious expressions **(Finley,2013,p.401)**. A key concern for the Uyghur people is the Han's failure to honor their native tongue in Xinjiang, where the Chinese language has become the prevailing standard, even though most Uyghurs assert that daily interactions should occur in the Uyghur language inside their homeland **(Smith,2000,p.22)**.

The negative patterns in Xinjiang can be depicted from above as a two-way highway between the Han and Uyghur peoples, apparent in the labels given by one party to the other and vice versa. The Han chauvinistic representations of the Uyghurs and their superior view of them have supported the growth of deep popular hatred of the Uyghurs towards the Han people **(Finley,2013,p.128)**. The condescending view of the Uyghurs deepens the bias of the Han majority in China so that the individual among them becomes completely certain that the position of the Uyghur people in the Chinese system is commensurate with deprivation and fits the social

marginalization and geographical remoteness of the region inhabited by Uyghurs. The most appropriate description of the Uyghurs' position in the political equation in China was given by Ildikó Bellér-Hann, associate professor at the Department of Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies at the University of Copenhagen and a specialist in Turkic and Central Asian Studies, which is "Highlanders," and this description is not limited to the geographical dimension only (**Beller-Hann,2022,p.98**). Thus, the view of the Uyghurs remained stuck in the same cycle, sharpened by a bias that already exists among the Han majority. On the one hand, it is gradually fed by the Uyghurs' strangeness and their view of them as different. On the other hand, it is exacerbated by the Uyghurs' greater adherence to their "Uyghurness," a special ethnic identity and a unique culture, and a return to the past traditions that include religious practices, which certainly increased the amount and level of their difference from everything that is familiar in Chinese society. In conclusion, the view of the Uyghurs in China is a mixture of fascination and distortion, such that they are often portrayed as people of different colors and flavors, aliens who excel in music, dance, and folklore, but they are also backward and uncivilized (**Baranovitch,2003,p.732**).

2. Preferential Policies for the Uyghurs are at the Heart of China's "Enlightenment Mission"

In his famous book, “The Descent of Man, and Selection in Relation to Sex,” Charles Darwin¹⁹⁰ explained how his idea of natural selection that governs nature, such that the fittest survive¹⁹¹ and pass their genes to the next generation while the weak rot and die, had obvious implications for human societies to which the same concept could be applied. Through this method, the civilized races existing in European societies, which are referred to as the Caucasian race, are better apt to survive and develop, unlike the “savage” races of lower rank elsewhere (**DiscoveryScience,2020**). Through Darwin's previously mentioned idea, which Herbert Spencer later picked up and explained, the term "Social Darwinism" arose and spread widely during the “Fin De Siècle¹⁹².” Later in Europe, these ideas were even abandoned due to

¹⁹⁰English naturalist (1809-1882) whose scientific theory of evolution by natural selection became the basis of modern evolutionary studies. Darwin was a devout countryman, but he struck human narcissism with a punch and shook his devout Victorian society when he suggested that animals and humans shared a common ancestry (**Desmond,2024**). To clarify, the idea of evolution preceded Darwin, as it is present in the ideas of Lamarck and Al-Jahiz, who spoke about the interconnectedness between all creatures, but it was Darwin who linked evolution to the process of natural selection.

¹⁹¹The phrase “survival of the fittest” was never used by Charles Darwin but was coined by the British philosopher Herbert Spencer (1820–1903), who believed in biological evolution and who more than promoted the ideas of Social Darwinism but without giving it any name or term.

¹⁹²The period that extended from the end of the Prussian-French War in 1870 until the beginning of World War I in 1914, during which there was a widespread feeling that European civilization, especially in France and Britain, was on its way to annihilation due to the dominance of an artistic climate characterized by despair and pessimism, despite the emergence of aesthetic art during that era (**Britannica,n.d.**).

their association with Nazi philosophy¹⁹³ during the end of World War II. The ideas of Social Darwinism spread like wildfire among intellectuals and scientists¹⁹⁴ of Europe who believed that the inferior societies made up of the indigenous peoples of Africa, Asia, and Oceania would eventually disappear, self-annihilate, and would not be able to keep up with the contemporary world that was in the making at the time. From here we can deduce the main idea that I will try to explain: the concept of contributing to facilitating life matters and offering a helping hand from one race to another, or from one nationality to another, in a way that includes superiority in dealing between the party that helps and the party that cannot develop except through assistance. Although these ideas are racist¹⁹⁵, obsolete, and invalid, those who publicly speak them today in the West are punished. However, some in China have modified it in various manners to uphold the official narrative that characterizes ethnic minorities as incapable of self-rule and constantly

¹⁹³One of the ideologies upholding the superiority of the Aryan race over all other races. It came under the banner of Social Darwinism and linked the concept of social evolution with its idea that inferior races would automatically die out and the Aryan Germanic race would remain dominant in the world. Even the Nazi prejudice against European Jews was linked to the race or ethnicity of the Jews as an ethnic group branching off from the Semitic peoples and had nothing to do with the Jewish religion (**Britannica,2024**).

¹⁹⁴The sociologist and philosopher Auguste Comte called on the West to continually help other backward races and open the way for them to acquire true sciences. He even went further and divided the races according to backwardness: after the white man came the Arab Muslims, the Turks, and the Persians, who believed in monotheism, and then the polytheist Indians. At the bottom of the ranking come the Asian yellow race and the African Black race (**Petitjean,2005,p.8**).

¹⁹⁵Among these outdated ideas, we mention a quote by the German ethnologist Friedrich Hellwald: Just as the struggle in nature for survival is the driving principle of biological evolution, so in history, the destruction of weaker nations by stronger ones is one of the axioms of progress.” (**DiscoveryScience,2020**).

reliant on aid. The state, through preferential policies, demolishes the gap between minorities and the Han majority at all levels. Although the goal of preferential policies was to impose real and substantive equality, the related discourses are steeped in the ideology of “social progress” among the Han elite and tend to reinforce their stereotypes about the backwardness of ethnic minorities **(Finley,2013,p.39)**. In this regard, the Han have always maintained a higher level of development than other ethnic minorities; these minority groups aligned themselves with the Han in pursuit of a lifestyle and pathways for advancement as outlined by the official state narrative on social development **(Sautman,1997,p.4)**. As for preferential policies that were introduced by the state to contribute to the improvement and development of marginalized and disadvantaged groups in society at the expense of gender, race, color, or religion, Barry Sautman, a professor emeritus with the Division of Social Science at the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, sees such policies in a positive light. According to Sautman, the combination of preferential policies for ethnic minorities in China and state initiatives aimed at advancing their rights may foster political and social stability **(Cappelletti,2020,p.14)**. Sautman contends that the variety of languages and the unique challenges encountered by minority

groups significantly hinder the complete integration into a Han-dominated society. Therefore, Sautman believes that these individuals need support and assistance from the state in their efforts to undergo the process of social and economic integration into society (**Cappelletti,2020,p.273**). On the flip side, many professors and scholars, mostly of Han descent, argue that the preferential policies for ethnic minorities in China yield no benefits and, in fact, represent an injustice to the Han majority, who suffer losses across multiple areas because of the principle of embracing “ethnic diversity”. For instance, Han professor Ma Rong argues that preferential policies for ethnic minorities have constituted a source of social and economic instability in China, such that the Han have begun to feel discrimination compared to their Uyghur counterparts and other minorities (**Cappelletti,2020,p.14**).

Preferential policies could be divided into the following categories: The quota of minorities in education and reducing the minimum required for university and college entrance exams—family planning¹⁹⁶—economy—the share of minority officials and cadres in local governments (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.348**).

¹⁹⁶Following the alarming population surge in China after World War II, along with the resulting social and economic challenges for the government and society, Deng, influenced by the ideas of Thomas Robert Malthus, implemented a groundbreaking policy in 1979: the One-Child Policy (**Zeng&Hesketh,2016**).

Nowhere is the condescending view towards minorities more evident than in the field of education. By giving minority groups special treatment through policies like setting aside a quota and lowering the minimum grades needed for them to get into college, the government makes it clear that they think these minority groups can't succeed on their own and need help from the government. In the United States, for example, proponents of preferential policy programs support a system of quotas in higher education that guarantees opportunities for disadvantaged groups, such as African Americans, to be admitted to universities (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.347**). This support is based on the consideration that there is a group present in society that always needs state assistance to be nearly as competitive as the majority and compete with it on the political, social, and economic levels. As long as this marginalized group receives appropriate education, its competitiveness will improve (**Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.348**). The same is true in China, where the CCP has enacted many policies that theoretically aim to improve ethnic minorities' opportunities to obtain higher education. First, the standards for the university entrance examination that minorities must take were lowered, and “bonus points” were added for minorities exclusively. This policy, which assigns people according to their affiliation

to a particular race or nationality that has a lower success rate than others to enter university, may be interpreted as clear evidence that members of minorities in China are viewed as less intelligent and less able to learn without state assistance. The university admission scores for Uyghur students who underwent the *Minkaomin* Uyghur language education system are much lower than those set for Han students **(Han,2010,p.252)**. Second, a system was established in Xinjiang universities to have a quota¹⁹⁷ made for members of ethnic minorities among the number of students accepted into universities. Moreover, the CCP has provided numerous financial subsidies to support the education of students from Xinjiang, assisting those who cannot afford university expenses in the region **(Grose,2010,p.100-101)**. In addition to these contributions, specially designated institutes and universities have been established for students of minorities only **(Tang&Hu&Jin,2016,p.348-349)**. Minority students were also given additional points to enter universities based on their region of origin, their nationality, the nationality of their parents, and the academic degree the student intends to obtain **(Finley,2013,p.39)**. For instance, a Uyghur student who studied in Han schools will receive two hundred bonus points if he has

¹⁹⁷During the 1990s, about fifty percent of admission quotas at Xinjiang University were allocated to students from ethnic minorities, especially Uyghurs **(Han,2010,p.252)**.

a Uyghur father and mother, but if he only has one Uyghur parent, he will receive only one hundred points (**Grose,2010,p.101**). Uyghurs were indirectly instructed to receive their education in Standard Chinese, which meant that those who studied in Standard Chinese generally accumulated more bonus points than those who learned in their native Uyghur language; one of the consequences of this policy was the further institutionalization of Standard Chinese in ethnic minority areas in China (**Finley,2013,p.39**). State subsidies allow exceptional students from rural areas, educated in Uyghur language schools, to pursue opportunities that were once mostly available to urban schoolchildren taught in standard Chinese language schools (**Hann,2014,p.194**).

Similar to the issue of education, the issue of family planning has gained great importance at the center of China's preferential policies for ethnic minorities. Since its establishment, the PRC has not interfered in the personal affairs of the Uyghurs, so it passed the 1950 Marriage Law, which allowed the traditional laws at the time to impose themselves in Islamic societies regarding polygamy, divorce, and the age of marriage that differed from that which had been permitted to the Han (**Sautman,1997,p.5**). Family

planning laws came into effect in Xinjiang only in 1988, ten years after they were compulsory in the whole of China. Even after the law took effect in Xinjiang, urban Uyghur couples were permitted two children, whereas rural ones could have three. This favorable policy led to resentment and anger among the Han, who were bound by a strict "one-child" policy **(Han,2010,p.252)**. Certain extremist Han theorists have gone to the extent of viewing China's family planning policies and minority favoritism in childbearing as a deliberate scheme created by liberals to limit the population growth of the Han group across the nation. Scenes of cheer and applause for the achievements of reformist leaders in minority areas, especially the Muslim communities of Xinjiang, rubbed salt in the bleeding wounds of Han chauvinism **(Stroup,2021,p.1244-1245)**. Preferential policies can strengthen group identity around the world and in the countries that employ them, and certainly this has been the case for Xinjiang Uyghurs; their common identity was strengthened due to preferential policies **(Han,2010,p.252-253)**.

Concerning the economy, as noted before, ethnic minority regions like Xinjiang only gained access to substantial state aid in the 1990s, while the

interior regions enjoyed such support from the very beginning of the reform era. Regarding the Xinjiang region, in 1988 the Chinese State Council approved a nine-point preferential policy to achieve rapid growth in foreign trade in the Xinjiang region. Among these points, five cities in Xinjiang were exempted from paying customs duties, including Turpan and Aksu. Cross-border trade procedures were also simplified, and the regional government in Xinjiang was given more authority and freedom to deal with foreign trade partners. As a result, commercial activities actually began to flourish along the border by the end of the 1980s **(Cappelletti,2020,p.46)**. In addition, members of minorities are now entitled to fully paid leave during the period of their holidays, even in areas outside their autonomous regions, and special meals have also been provided to Muslims during their holidays, taking into account their religious privacy with regard to food **(Sautman,1997,p.5)**. Even though the preferential policies for ethnic minorities undeniably benefited some individuals, they did not remedy the underlying issues they were meant to address, and as a result, the economic gap between the Han and the minorities persisted **(Finley,2013,p.58-59)**.

Ethnic minority cadres in the CCP and in regional government bodies have long suffered from lopsided representation, being underrepresented in Han-dominated areas of China, while in autonomous minority areas they were overrepresented. The reform period was marked by attempts to correct and address the problem of imbalance in the representation of ethnic minority cadres. In 1983, the National People's Congress in China issued a law requiring that at least 12% of its representatives be from ethnic minorities (**Sautman,1997,p.17,25**). The ultimate goal of these preferential policies in the representation of cadres in official government bodies became "actual equality," whereby the proportion of party cadres from a certain minority must correspond to the proportion of that minority within the autonomous region (**Sautman,1997,p.4**). The attempt to set a quota for minorities was nothing more than an attempt to frame minorities in the heart of the negative pattern in China, which sets a minimum requirement for them at all levels, even in the matter of their individuals reaching positions and posts in political bodies. It appears as if the state is the one pushing some of their individuals to reach those positions by imposing the quota system. Chris Hann, a social anthropologist who has done field research in socialist and post-socialist Eastern Europe and the Turkic-speaking world

and honorary director of the Max Planck Institute in Germany, speaks on the issue of the preferential policies enacted by the Chinese state being based on negative patterns; he considers it ironic when the rural Uyghurs who hold organizational positions in the CCP, even if they are at the middle and lower levels, are referred to as superior and are considered the cornerstone of the Uyghur intellectual class **(Hann,2014,p.202)**.

Overall, Barry Sautman, a professor emeritus with the Division of Social Science at the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, believes that preferential policies in Xinjiang are not as disastrous as most comparative scholars portray them. Sautman also urges other scholars to take into account the scale and comprehensiveness of the preferential policy program in that region, though he acknowledges that preferential policies will ultimately help erode indigenous culture in Xinjiang **(Sautman,1997,p.38-39)**. Sautman argues that ethnic inequality in Xinjiang decreased in the field of education, such that ethnic minority students learned better in higher education schools and universities during the 1980s thanks to preferential policies promoted by the reformist leadership. Moving from education to work, Sautman recognizes that conditions for minorities in

the employment sector are far from perfect, yet preferential policies have successfully broadened and diversified the ethnic middle class in China **(Sautman,1997,p.17)**. However, many ethnic minority intellectuals cast doubt on these preferential policies, seeing them as a guarantor of the undermining of the cultural values of minorities who are educated in institutions of higher education and work in the environment of a one-sided culture, Han culture **(Sautman,1997,p.33)**. In addition, some minority intellectuals fear that by lowering standards and expectations, preferential policies will limit the ambition of the Uyghur people, making them less competitive in the long run with other ethnic groups **(Finley,2013,p.39)**. These measures are regarded as having adverse effects, leading to the perception of the Uyghurs as a subjugated race in the view of Han thought leaders, who suggest that the Uyghurs' dependency on foreign aid could obstruct their efforts to promote development and modernization locally. Han researchers like Yuhui Li, who have undertaken field studies in Xinjiang, have challenged the Chinese government's unified model that is uniformly imposed on all minority groups, ignoring their variances. They argue for a change to a bottom-up approach tailored to the unique circumstances of each ethnic community **(Cappelletti,2020,p.111)**. In

conclusion, and unexpectedly, those preferential policies that were at the forefront of the Sinicization programs and which originally aimed to integrate the Uyghurs into Han society as had been hoped for, backfired, and on one hand, it created new borders and contributed to strengthening existing borders among the Han and Uyghurs (Han,2010,p.249). On the other hand, it produced a stronger bond between Uyghurs and made them more proud of their culture and less accepting of integration into a Han-dominated society.

Image #17
First page of the book "Dīwān Lughāt al-Turk" by Mahmoud Kashgari.

<https://www.azernews.az/nation/234996.html>

Conclusion of Chapter 5

Despite differing cultural values, political and economic perspectives, and diverse beliefs in religion and ideology, both China and the West maintain a significant awareness and strong emphasis on the identity of their own societies as superior to the "other." Both of them often supported the point of view that they were more cultured, educated, and knowledgeable, and that they were at the forefront of development socially, culturally, and even biologically, if they were compared to the Islamic world, that is, in the Middle East if it's Europe, or Xinjiang if we are talking about China. As European ideas infiltrated East Asia in the mid to late 19th century, during what is known as China's "century of humiliation," China adopted several notions and opinions, including misconceptions about superiority, from those Europeans who looked down on its own people.

Cases of concealment of identity among the Uyghur people are sufficient to prove that the superior view of the Han over the Uyghurs has become prevalent in Uyghur society and entrenched in the minds

and souls, albeit partially and limited to some positions in Uyghur society. When an individual is forced to lie in order to conceal his Uyghur identity, even if it is in order to make daily life matters easier, then the result of Han dominance over society appears on the surface. It is clear that decades of Uyghurs being exposed to Han superiority were enough to destroy the self-image and feelings of pride among some of the Uyghur people, and this matter is observed by researchers coming to Xinjiang to study the Uyghur community.

Once a barren desert, Xinjiang waited for the Han man, who carried the responsibility of China's ethnic minorities, to sow the seeds of knowledge, science, and development in a manner reminiscent of the white European man and his burden. Everything in Xinjiang contributed to keeping the Uyghurs at the lowest point on the scale of difference, and because they appeared to the Han as backward, they were viewed and referred to in a negative manner within the Orientalist view. At the core of this gaze, the Han saw the bodies of Uyghur women as a playground that existed to consolidate their control, as in the settler/colonial project in Xinjiang. Concurrently, in the context of the

same project, Uyghur men needed to be feminized in that scenario for Han settlers to uphold their centuries of dominance. Without the slightest doubt, the 1980s, at the heart of the reform period, was the decade that the Chinese state attempted to reduce Han chauvinism and dry up its sources. The goal was to make a good, ideal Utopian society with the idea of a reformist leadership influenced by Western ideas. This would ensure more equality between Chinese minorities as long as none of them crossed the red lines and threatened China's strategic security and internal harmony. However, the Uyghurs reacted negatively to this openness, leading the state's approach to shift in the opposite direction, aiming to dismantle the local minority chauvinism that emerged alongside Han chauvinism by the end of the reform period. In terms of preferential policies, China would likely not have enforced them amidst strong resistance from the Han ethnic majority, who argue these policies are discriminatory if the Uyghurs in the Chinese narrative were considered developed and proficient people who do not need governmental backing in areas such as education, science, or political representation. The necessity of providing preferential policies for the Uyghurs stems from the state's belief in the Uyghurs' backwardness,

and thus it extends a helping hand from the big brother of the Chinese ethnicities, that is, the Han people or the state that represents them, in order to put these people on the path of civilization and progress in their view.

Through preferential policies, the Uyghur people are drowning in a closed loop that links cause and effect in the midst of a bidirectional causality equation. These policies further demonstrate the primitiveness of the Uyghurs in the eyes of the Han, whose members wonder why the state is introducing policies in which the Uyghur minority, in addition to other minorities, is preferred over the Han. These individuals conclude that the preferential policies are due to the backwardness of the Uyghurs and their inability to achieve their aspirations on their own without official assistance. Given the ongoing negative attitudes toward the Uyghurs, there is a pressing necessity for China to uphold preferential policies that will help alleviate their difficulties and empower them, making it challenging for the Uyghurs to escape the interconnected cycle established in prior decades, especially after the reform period ended. Under Xi Jinping's leadership, the official

narrative in China has shifted away from the historical focus on implementing socialism during Mao's time and establishing a robust economy within an open and reformed framework during Deng's time. Instead, the definition of Chinese identity has narrowed to encompass solely the Han people, their history, heritage, and cultural essence.

Conclusions

After completing this study, the following becomes clear:

1. The Uyghurs in Xinjiang have consolidated their shared identity, and the existing borders between them and the Han have been strengthened due to preferential policies, contrary to the state's goal of assimilating and Sinicizing them. Also, by setting a relative quota for the Uyghurs, the state appears to be determined to negatively stereotype the Uyghurs and limit their ambition in order to make them less able to compete in the long term with the rest of the ethnic components of China. The Uyghurs are walking in a vicious circle. On the one hand, the existing prejudice against the Uyghurs

among the Han majority is strengthened by the otherness of the Uyghurs, and on the other hand, the Uyghurs' adherence to their Uyghurness" is strengthened, so the rift between the two groups widens and the chances of normal coexistence between them in Xinjiang diminish. **A two-way correlation emerges between the Han's negative view of the Uyghurs and preferential policies for the Uyghur people.**

2. The rise of separatism among the Uyghurs during the reform era, which aimed to assimilate them into Chinese society in Xinjiang, ironically heightened the Han people's fear of the "other." **This has led to claims that the political openness initiated by the government in the 1980s was a key factor in amplifying the Uyghurs' feelings of separatism.** Today, when analyzing the 1980s in China, it has become apparent that the political and cultural openness in Xinjiang played a key role in reopening the previously shut-off channels among the Uyghurs, creating a political environment that challenged the state and resisted both cultural assimilation and Han migration into the region.

3. **The government's political goal** during the reform period was "**Han acculturation**," that is, the assimilation of Uyghur culture into the Han majority. However, the government's goal collided with the Uyghur intransigence, as Han migration did not find a foothold among the local population in Xinjiang within the spatial and cultural boundaries of the Uyghurs, who feared becoming a minority within their own territory.

4. **In their political and social mobilization** during the reform period, the Uyghurs split into two ideologically and geographically distinct camps. In northern Xinjiang, the mobilization centered around a democratic nationalist line similar to Western democracies, while in the rural south, the mobilization centered around Islamic principles to replace the Western values demanded by the communities of northern Xinjiang.

5. **In the economic aspect**, the state postponed Xinjiang until the 1990s in order to benefit from state support. The state's focus shifted to promoting development in the eastern coastal areas, as stated in the Sixth and Seventh Five-Year Plans. Xinjiang and other inland areas became a source of raw materials and minerals. Xinjiang based its development on the

two pillars of the economy: the black one, which indicates oil, and the white one, which indicates cotton.

6. **Due to the economic disparity** and uneven development between regions, ethnic and national differences between the Uyghurs and the Han were reinforced, and the chances of any integration of the Uyghurs within the state were reduced due to this clear economic rift during the 1980s.

7. The reform period saw an explosion of Uyghur language publications, and new publications on Uyghur literature, history, and culture were published, but with Han nationalism as the cornerstone of the education project for other ethnicities. During the reform period, the Uyghurs could access and revive their rich cultural heritage with the help of the Chinese regime and the Han people, the Uyghur people's "big brother."

8. **In Uyghur poetry and prose**, government policies during this period allowed for a "golden age" of Uyghur poetry and the continuation of oral traditions. However, opposition to the Chinese regime was hidden in the folds of historical narrative, folk song lyrics, and poetic phrases and verses.

9. The **Uyghur language** is no longer the lingua franca in Xinjiang; Mandarin has taken over. Chinese vocabulary has invaded the Uyghur language, and the bias that considers the Uyghur language incompatible with modern science has crystallized. The foreign language currently adopted in China is essentially a negative paradigm that intertwines the doctrines of the Han majority as illustrated by the Chinese state. This mindset conveys the Han's arrogant perception of the Uyghurs, categorizing them as "other," "different," and "foreign," while also enforcing preferential policies that aim to assimilate the Uyghurs to the Han's level in various spheres, thereby attempting to minimize their otherness.

Epilogue

Prior to embarking on this research and while I was filtering through various ideas to select a research topic, my views on the connection between the Chinese state and the Uyghur people, similar to anyone who hadn't thoroughly explored the underpinnings of that relationship, were rife with misconceptions and unfounded theories. Even if the intention of China's reformist leaders was to turn the Uyghurs into Chinese, reading many references that dealt, even marginally, with the subject of the reform period and its impact on Xinjiang made me believe that these leaders wanted to improve the condition of the Uyghurs in most aspects, regardless of their ultimate goal of cultural assimilation. They hoped to restore stability in China by normalizing the country's political situation and putting an end to the mass hysteria that had been practiced during Mao's era. By juxtaposing the reform era with the subsequent time, the events at Tiananmen Square underscored the collapse of reform policies in China, a failure that was inevitably evident in Xinjiang too. The Uyghurs did not benefit from that golden period to improve their conditions, and the regime did not succeed in

Sinicizing them. The result was a no-win situation for both parties. However, I also want to point out that the Uyghurs during the 1980s, a decade of political chaos and turmoil in Xinjiang, were part of the failure to benefit from the period of openness and reform. Another insight I gained is that the Arab world, as a vanguard in the broader Islamic world, also carries the weight of neglect and indifference towards the difficulties faced by the Turkish Muslim Uyghur population. Most of the Arabic articles and sources I've examined are not appropriate for use in my thesis due to a lack of detailed information on specific topics in their historical basis. This difficulty is not confined to the largely enigmatic ancient history of the Uyghurs but also pertains to their modern history, which is relatively easy to access through literature and references written in English. In addition, the major calamity is that the Arab and Islamic countries are appeasing China and are willing to defend it in the face of the West's allegations in the United Nations and the Human Rights Council of violating human rights in Xinjiang. Indeed, various Arab states are even sending tourist missions to propagate the official Chinese viewpoint that everything in Xinjiang is normal, overlooking the reality of detention camps and forced assimilation practices imposed on the Uyghur community since the 2010s! But to end on

a more positive note, we hope that this study will be a research gateway so that we can all know more about the history of the Uyghur people in Xinjiang during China's reform period and understand the challenges they went through following China's attempt to impose Sinicization on them.

I hope that this study will help to pique Arab and Islamic interest in researching more about the history and heritage, as well as the present challenges and suffering of the Uyghur people. During Mao's rule, the Uyghurs were subjected to marginalization, and during the reformist period, they were subjected to economic discrimination and attempts at sinicization. As of the 2020s, many members of the Uyghur community are miserably languishing in camps and "get subtracted from society," just like what happened to Professor *Rahilä Dawut* and others.

Image #18

Lisa Ross Photography - Professor *Rahilä Dawut*

The educated and enlightened class, mainly scholars and professors, pose as the most dangerous group for totalitarian authoritarian regimes—Professor *Rahilä Dawut* lost her freedom only because she helped in spreading the identity and culture of her Uyghur people to the world.

<https://duihua.org/life-sentence-for-professor-rahile-dawut-confirmed/>

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